

Coronaviruses • SARS • MERS • COVID-19

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[<https://www.academia.edu/42128715/>](https://www.academia.edu/42128715/>)

This scanning electron microscope image shows SARS-CoV-2, isolated from a patient in the United States, emerging from the surface of cells cultured in the lab. (NIAID-RML/de Wit/Fischer)

[<https://nature.us17.list-manage.com/track/click?u=2c6057c528fdc6f73fa196d9d&id=53abec294e&e=4fa403eb88>](https://nature.us17.list-manage.com/track/click?u=2c6057c528fdc6f73fa196d9d&id=53abec294e&e=4fa403eb88)

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Coronaviruses in general

MONTO Arnold S., COWLING Benjamin J., PEIRIS J.S. Malik

°2014 [pdf]

Coronaviruses,

in: KASLOW Richard A., STANBERRY Lawrence R., LE DUC James W. (eds.) °2014 [pdf]: *Viral Infections of Humans: Epidemiology and Control.*

Boston, MA: Springer, pp. 199-223, 5 figs., 3 tables, 226 refs.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-7448-8_10

https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4899-7448-8_10

[Abstract: Coronaviruses of humans were first identified more than 60 years ago from individuals with respiratory infections, mainly mild. Two different viruses, 229E and OC43 were initially recognized. Because of difficulty in isolating them using standard techniques, many of the early studies of their occurrence were seroepidemiologic. They were confirmed to be worldwide in distribution, and, in the North Temperate Zone, mainly occurring in the winter season. With the development of the reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technique, two additional distinct viruses have been identified, HKU1 and NL63. The four viruses have now been recognized as important in the etiology of common respiratory infections, second only to the rhinoviruses.

In 2002, a previously unrecognized betacoronavirus emerged from a zoonotic reservoir in Southern China and spread during the following year to several major cities of the world. The resulting illness was termed Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) because of its potential lethality. More than 8,000 probable cases were reported during 2003, mainly from Hong Kong and mainland China, producing social and economic disruption in those areas affected. A constant feature of the outbreak was the importance of nosocomial spread. In spite of an estimated basic reproductive number higher than influenza, the outbreak was ended, in large part because of control of in-hospital transmission. In 2012, another betacoronavirus has emerged in the Arabian peninsula which is producing a somewhat similar illness, termed Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), also marked by extensive nosocomial transmission. The outcome of this emergence is currently unknown.

Keywords. Osteoporosis, Corticosteroid, Pneumonia, Influenza, Diarrhea.]

CUI Jie, LI Fang & SHI Zheng-Li [石正麗]

2019

Origin and evolution of pathogenic coronaviruses,

in: Nature Reviews Microbiology 17: 181-192.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-018-0118-9>

[Abstract: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) are two highly transmissible and pathogenic viruses that emerged in humans at the beginning of the 21st century. Both viruses likely originated in bats, and genetically diverse coronaviruses that are related to SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV were discovered in bats worldwide. In this Review, we summarize the current knowledge on the origin and evolution of these two pathogenic coronaviruses and discuss their receptor usage; we also highlight the diversity and potential of spillover of bat-borne coronaviruses, as evidenced by the recent spillover of swine acute diarrhoea syndrome coronavirus (SADS-CoV) to pigs.

Sections: Abstract / Introduction / Coronavirus diversity

Animal origin and evolution of SARS-CoV

Variability of SARS-CoV in humans and civets

Variability of bat SARSr-CoVs

Receptor usage of SARS-CoV and SARSr-CoV

Origin and evolution of MERS-CoV

Variability of human and camel MERS-CoV

Variability of bat MERSr-CoVs

Receptor usage of MERS-CoV and MERSr-CoV

SADS-CoV

Conclusions and future perspectives

References / Acknowledgements / Author information / Ethics declarations / Additional information / Supplementary information / Glossary / Rights and permissions / About this article / Further reading]

JOHNS HOPKINS CENTER FOR HEALTH SECURITY

2020

Coronaviruses: SARS, MERS, and COVID-19.

January 21, 2020. Agent Fact Sheet. [2p., 10 refs.]

<http://www.centerforhealthsecurity.org/resources/fact-sheets/pdfs/coronaviruses.pdf>

KAMPF Günter, TODT Daniel, PFAENDER Stephanie, STEINMANN Eike

°2020 [pdf]

Persistence of coronaviruses on inanimate surfaces and its inactivation with biocidal agents,

in: *Journal of Hospital Infection* [pre-proof; 13 p.; 3 tables.]

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhin.2020.01.022>

Summary: Currently, the emergence of a novel human coronavirus, temporary named 2019-nCoV, has become a global health concern causing severe respiratory tract infections in humans. Human-to-human transmissions have been described with incubation times between 2-10 days, facilitating its spread via droplets, contaminated hands or surfaces. We therefore reviewed the literature on all available information about the persistence of human and veterinary coronaviruses on inanimate surfaces as well as inactivation strategies with biocidal agents used for chemical disinfection, e.g. in healthcare facilities. The analysis of 22 studies reveals that human coronaviruses such as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) coronavirus, Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) coronavirus or endemic human coronaviruses (HCoV) can persist on inanimate surfaces like metal, glass or plastic for up to 9 days, but can be efficiently inactivated by surface disinfection procedures with 62-71% ethanol, 0.5% hydrogen peroxide or 0.1% sodium hypochlorite within 1 minute. Other biocidal agents such as 0.05-0.2% benzalkonium chloride or 0.02% chlorhexidine digluconate are less effective. As no specific therapies are available for 2019-nCoV, early containment and prevention of further spread will be crucial to stop the ongoing outbreak and to control this novel infectious threat. Keywords: coronavirus, persistence, inanimate surfaces, chemical inactivation, biocidal agents, disinfection.]

LU Guangwen, WANG Qihui, GAO George F.

°2015 [pdf]

Bat-to-human: spike features determining 'host jump' of coronaviruses SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and beyond, (Feature Review)

in: *Trends in Microbiology* 23(8): 468-478, 3 figs., 2 tables.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2015.06.003>

[Highlights: • Bats are natural reservoirs of many coronaviruses that can infect humans.

- Mechanisms of cross-species transmission of coronaviruses are important scientific questions.
- The coronaviral spike protein is an important viral determinant of cross-species transmission.
- Receptor-binding characteristics and cleavage priming of the spike protein are summarized.

Abstract: Both severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) are zoonotic pathogens that crossed the species barriers to infect humans. The mechanism of viral interspecies transmission is an important scientific question to be addressed. These coronaviruses contain a surface-located spike (S) protein that initiates infection by mediating receptor-recognition and membrane fusion and is therefore a key factor in host specificity. In addition, the S protein needs to be cleaved by host proteases before executing fusion, making these proteases a second determinant of coronavirus interspecies infection. Here, we summarize the progress made in the past decade in understanding the cross-species transmission of SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV by focusing on the features of the S protein, its receptor-binding characteristics, and the cleavage process involved in priming. Keywords: coronavirus; interspecies transmission; viral and host determinants; spike (S); SARS-CoV; MERS-CoV.]

PETROSILLO Nicola, VICECONTE Giulio, ERGONUL Onder, IPPOLITO Giuseppe, PETERSEN Eskild

°2020

COVID-19, SARS and MERS: are they closely related? (Narrative Review)

in: *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, 28 March 2020, In Press,

Journal Pre-proof. [23p., 2 tables, 52 refs.]

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2020.03.026>

[Abstract: Background: The 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) is a new human coronavirus which is spreading with epidemic features in China and other Asian countries with cases reported worldwide. This novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) is associated with a respiratory illness that may cause severe pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). Although related to the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), COVID-19 shows some peculiar pathogenetic, epidemiological and clinical features which have not been completely understood to date.

Objectives: We provide a review of the differences in terms of pathogenesis, epidemiology and clinical features between COVID-19, SARS and MERS.

Sources: The most recent literature in English language regarding COVID-19 has been reviewed and extracted data have been compared with the current scientific evidence about SARS and MERS epidemics.

Content: COVID-19 seems not to be very different from SARS regarding its clinical features. However, it has a fatality rate of 2.3%, lower than SARS (9.5%) and much lower than MERS (34.4%). It cannot be excluded that because of the COVID-19 less severe clinical picture it can spread in the community more easily than MERS and SARS. The actual basic reproductive number (R0) of COVID-19 (2-2.5) is still controversial. It is probably slightly higher than the R0 of SARS (1.7-1.9) and higher than MERS (<1). The gastrointestinal route of transmission of SARS-CoV-2, which has been also assumed for SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV, cannot be ruled out and needs to be further investigated.

Implications: There is still much more to know about COVID-19, especially as concerns mortality and capacity of spreading on a pandemic level. Nonetheless, all of the lessons we learned in the past from SARS and MERS epidemics are the best cultural weapons to face this new global threat. Keywords: Coronavirus; COVID-19; Emerging infections; MERS; SARS.]

WEISS Susan R.
 2020 [pdf]

Forty years with coronaviruses, (Viewpoint)

in: JEM Journal of Experimental Medicine 217(5): e20200537.

[4 p., 1 fig., 27 refs.] <<https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.20200537>>

[I have been researching coronaviruses for more than forty years. This viewpoint summarizes some of the major findings in coronavirus research made before the SARS epidemic and how they inform current research on the newly emerged SARS-CoV-2.]

Figure 1. **Timeline for coronavirus research.** Major findings in coronavirus research (gray boxes) as well as identification of human coronaviruses (red boxes) are indicated along the timeline.

SARS-Cov • Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus

SARS-CoV: Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus

German: schweres akutes respiratorisches Syndrom (SARS)

LEUNG Ping Chung, OOI Eng Eong (eds.)

©2003

Sars War: Combating The Disease.

New Jersey; London; Singapore; Hong Kong: World Scientific.

[(6)+150p.; ill.; ISBN-10: 981-238-438-3 (pbk).]

[Synopsis: In this book, the global SARS outbreak is traced and described, with a focus on the regions where the most infections have been identified. An overview of the whole saga is presented: how the disease spreads; how governments react; how societies and people cope; and how health experts work fervently to identify the virus and search for a cure. In addition, the book contains guidelines on what a person or organisation can do to reduce the risk of contracting the deadly illness. It includes precautionary measures disseminated by the WHO and preventive herbal concoctions recommended by Chinese physicians, presented in an easy-to-read manner. Furthermore, insights of experts are provided. This book is available in English and Chinese, both simplified and traditional. –

On 12 March 2003, the World Health Organisation (WHO) issued a global alert on the outbreak of a new form of pneumonia-like disease with symptoms that are similar to those of the common flu. This illness, officially known as severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), is potentially fatal and highly contagious, and has spread quickly to many parts of the world in a matter of a few weeks. Aided by globalisation and the ease of air travel today, the disease has now been reported in many countries, such as China, Hong Kong, Vietnam, Singapore, Canada, the US and some parts of Europe, with a large number of infections and a significant number of deaths. In this book, the global SARS outbreak is traced and described, with a focus on the regions where the most infections have been identified. An overview of the whole saga is presented: how the disease spreads; how governments react; how societies and people cope and how health experts work fervently to identify the virus and search for a cure. In addition, the book contains guidelines on what a person or organisation can do to reduce the risk of contracting the deadly illness. It includes precautionary measures disseminated by various health authorities and preventive herbal concoctions recommended by Chinese physicians, presented in an easy-to-read manner. Furthermore, insights of experts are provided. This book aims to give critical information on SARS. It is a must for people who want to find out more about the disease and how to reduce the risk of contracting it.]

reviews:

• SAIMAN Lisa ‘2003: *Journal of Clinical Investigation* 112(10): 1457.

<<https://dx.doi.org/10.1172/JCI20362>>

<<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC259137/>>

[(full text) Leung Ping Chung and Ooi Eng Eong have presented a heartfelt account of their battles with severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) during the initial appearance of this new pathogen in their countries in early 2003. Leung works at the Prince of Wales Hospital in Hong Kong and Ooi at the Environmental Health Institute in Singapore. Both cared for patients with SARS and contributed to the public health efforts to combat and control this global epidemic. Leung and Ooi briefly trace the course of the epidemic in the first chapter. Unfortunately, due to changes in the clinical case definition, delays in confirmatory laboratory testing, and delays in reporting, the numbers cited are now outdated. However, the importance of demanding complete transparency by governments in order to avoid the further spread of SARS is justifiably highlighted in several places. This reviewer would have welcomed Leung and Ooi’s insights regarding the cast of government officials who denied or validated the epidemic’s importance and who hindered or assisted in its control.

The descriptions of the mass quarantines and the use of legislative means to enforce quarantines are of great interest, particularly to a Western reader. For instance, when over 200 cases of SARS were discovered in an apartment complex in Hong Kong, the building was cordoned off and police officers wearing protective masks, gloves, and gowns set up barricades to prevent anyone from entering or leaving the building. Leung and Ooi include a personal vignette of the difficulties in obtaining groceries for residents caught unprepared by the mandated quarantine. In Singapore, the Infectious Diseases Act, which mandated quarantine of all persons who had contact with SARS patients, was invoked. Hefty fines were levied for those persons who did not comply with the quarantine. The fear and paranoia of the general population are detailed as are the frenzied demands for masks and, in efforts to strengthen the immune system, vitamins and Chinese medicinal herbs.

The relative contributions of such drastic means in curtailing the outbreak remain unknown, and these measures are not recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO). The recommendations and contributions of the WHO are outlined, albeit briefly, as is the dramatic

success of the unprecedented coordinated international diagnostic and control efforts. Unfortunately, these efforts are described only through April 3, 2003, leaving the reader with an incomplete story. The WHO didn't declare that the epidemic was over (for the 2002–2003 season at least) until July 2003.

The abundant photographs are vivid portrayals of the impact of SARS on the countries in Asia that were most affected. Signs proclaiming school closings, pictures of airplane crews and passengers on buses wearing masks to protect themselves, and numerous photographs of cleaning staff — all wearing masks and gloves — disinfecting elevators, public buildings, and train stations are shown.

Perhaps due to the speed with which this book was written and published, there are several redundancies and numerous inaccuracies and unproven conclusions. For example, Leung and Ooi state that the case fatality rate is 4%, but in fact the rate is more than double that at 10.9%. They also imply that convalescent serum from recovering patients might be a useful therapy. There are no published reports of the efficacy of this treatment, which was used only by Leung and Ooi and not by others who treated patients with SARS. To date, there are no specific therapeutic interventions for SARS; supportive care is the standard.

The intended audience for this book is unclear. The book is too technical for a lay person, yet there are numerous recommendations for personal hygiene and general health in addition to recipes for traditional Chinese remedies. The redundancies, as well as changes in tone and reading level, are distracting.

Despite the book's flaws, physicians, epidemiologists, and historians alike will find aspects of *SARS war: combating the disease* of interest. Readers should not expect totally objective science, but a tangled description of what occurred during a very complex and difficult situation for all; there were no precedents to rely on. As Leung and Ooi state, "Overreacting became a public health policy guideline in efforts to identify, contain, and control the epidemic." While this book suffers from a lack of skilled editing and peer review, it honestly captures what it was like "on the ground" in Singapore and Hong Kong during the darkest days of the SARS outbreak. While other, more comprehensive books on SARS will no doubt be published in the future, this book presents a stirring chronicle.]

LOH Christine & CIVIC EXCHANGE (eds.)

2004

At the epicentre: Hong Kong and the SARS outbreak.

Edited by Christine LOH & Civic Exchange.

Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press.

[312p.; ISBN: 9622096832.]

reviews:

• HANSON Marta E. 2006, in: *China Review International* 13(1): 218-224.

SONG H.D., TU C.C., ZHANG G.W., *et al.*

2005

Cross-host evolution of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus in palm civet and human,

in: *PNAS* 102(7): 2430-2435.

doi: 10.1073/pnas.0409608102.

CARMICHAEL Ann G.

°2006 [pdf]

SARS and plagues past,

in: DUFFIN Jacalyn & SWEETMAN Arthur (eds.) 2006: *SARS in Context: Memory, History, and Policy*. Toronto: McGill-Queen's University Press, Part II, *History. Historians of Disease Reflect on Sars*, pp. 3-28.

DUFFIN Jacalyn & SWEETMAN Arthur (eds.)

2006

SARS in Context: Memory, History, and Policy.

Toronto: McGill-Queen's University Press.

HONG KONG MUSEUM OF MEDICAL SCIENCES SOCIETY; STARLING Arthur *et al.* (editorial committee)

2006

Plague, SARS and the story of medicine in Hong Kong.

Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press.

[xiv+368p.; ill.; ISBN: 9789622098053.]

[Blurb: The volume covers Hong Kong's medical development in the period from 1841 to early 2005, including the history of hospitals and medical education, and the role of the Bacte-

riological Institute. It is a record of how the health care system has evolved and how the territory has been able to cope with the massive increase in population. –

Content: Ch. 1. *History of infectious diseases in Hong Kong: a story of discovery and challenge.*

Ch. 2. *The evolution of Hong Kong's hospitals : prevention or cure?*

Ch. 3. *The bacteriological institute and its contributions to Hong Kong.*

Ch. 4. *Hong Kong's battle against tuberculosis.*

Ch. 5. *Health-care issues in a changing society.*

Ch. 6. *The development of medical education.*

App. I. *Hong Kong medical and health agencies and principal officers.*

App. II. *Ten leading causes of death in Hong Kong at 2002.*

App. III. *Number of medical students enrolled in and graduating from the Chinese University of Hong Kong.*

App. IV. *Number of medical students graduating from the University of Hong Kong.*

App. V. *Practitioners in different specialties in Hong Kong.*]

reviews:

• HANSON Marta E. °2008, in: *Bulletin of the History of Medicine* 82(2): 500-501.

<<https://doi.org/10.1353/bhm.0.0001>> [pdf]

OOSTRA M., DE HAAN C.A., ROTTIER P.J.

2007

The 29-nucleotide deletion present in human but not in animal severe acute respiratory syndrome coronaviruses disrupts the functional expression of open reading frame 8,

in: *J Virol.* 2007; 81:13876-13888. doi: 10.1128/JVI.01631-07.

HANSON Marta E.

*°2008 [pdf]

The Art of Medicine: Maoist public-health campaigns, Chinese medicine, and SARS, (Perspectives)

in: *The Lancet* 372 (Oct. 25, 2008): 1457-1458, 3 figs.

<[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(08\)61610-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(08)61610-4)>

[(public-health campaigns; SARS)

1457: "On Labour Day May 1, 2003, *The Beijing Times* published a poster titled *Declare War on SARS!* (figure 1). The five-character phrase grammatically recalls the five-character slogan of the Communist Revolution "Serve the People!". A young man dressed in proletariat blue raises his right fist and breaks through the top border calling the masses to unite behind the government to conquer SARS. His posture mirrors that of a young barefoot doctor in a 1970 public-health poster for the prevention of respiratory tract infections (figure 2). The red cross has moved from the barefoot doctor's first-aid satchel to a surgical cap replacing the old red star on Maoist military caps. A white face mask, which became the international symbol of the SARS epidemic, now covers his mouth."]

*°2010

Conceptual Blind Spots, Media Blindfolds: The Case of SARS and Traditional Chinese Medicine,

in: LEUNG Angela Ki Che & FURTH Charlotte (eds.) °2010: *Health and Hygiene in Modern Chinese East Asia. Policies and publics in the Long Twentieth Century.* Durham; London: Duke University Press, pp. 228-254.

[(SARS and TCM)]

POWERS John H., XIAO Xiaosui (eds.)

°2008 [pdf]

The Social Construction of SARS. Studies of a health communication crisis.

(Discourse Approaches to Politics, Society and Culture; v. 30)

Amsterdam / Philadelphia: John Benjamins.

[p.; ISBN 978 90 272 0618 3 (Hb; alk. paper).]

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TSENG Yen-fen & WU Chia-ling

©2010

Governing Germs from Outside and Within Borders. Controlling the 2003 SARS Risk in Taiwan,

in: LEUNG Angela Ki Che & FURTH Charlotte (eds.) ©2010: *Health and Hygiene in Modern Chinese East Asia. Policies and publics in the Long Twentieth Century*. Durham; London: Duke University Press, pp. 255-272.

[(SARS 2003, Taiwan)]

LAU S.K., FENG Y., CHEN H., *et al.*

2015

Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) coronavirus ORF8 protein is acquired from SARS-related coronavirus from Greater horseshoe bats through recombination, in: *J Virol.* 2015 Oct; 89(20): 10532-10547.

doi: 10.1128/JVI.01048-15.

SHI C.S., NABAR N.R., HUANG N.N., *et al.*

2019

SARS-Coronavirus Open reading frame-8b triggers intracellular stress pathways and activates NLRP3 inflammasomes,

in: *Cell Death Discov.* 2019; 5: 101.

doi: 10.1038/s41420-019-0181-7.

PETROSILLO Nicola, VICECONTE Giulio, ERGONUL Onder, IPPOLITO Giuseppe, PETERSEN Eskild

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COVID-19, SARS and MERS: are they closely related? (Narrative Review) in: *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, 28 March 2020, In Press, Journal Pre-proof. [23p., 2 tables, 52 refs.]

<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2020.03.026>>

[Abstract: Background: The 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) is a new human coronavirus which is spreading with epidemic features in China and other Asian countries with cases reported worldwide. This novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) is associated with a respiratory illness that may cause severe pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). Although related to the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), COVID-19 shows some peculiar pathogenetic, epidemiological and clinical features which have not been completely understood to date.

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Implications: There is still much more to know about COVID-19, especially as concerns mortality and capacity of spreading on a pandemic level. Nonetheless, all of the lessons we learned in the past from SARS and MERS epidemics are the best cultural weapons to face this new global threat. Keywords: Coronavirus; COVID-19; Emerging infections; MERS; SARS.]

Traditional Chinese medicine

HOEVER Gerold, BALTINA Lidia, MICHAELIS Martin, KONDRATENKO Rimma, BALTINA Lia, TOLSTIKOV Genrich A., DOERR Hans W., CINATL Jindrich
2005

Antiviral Activity of Glycyrrhizic Acid Derivatives against SARS-Coronavirus,
in: *Journal of medicinal Chemistry* 48(4): 1256-1259.

<<https://doi.org/10.1021/jm0493008>>

<<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/jm0493008>>

[Abstract: Glycyrrhizin (GL) was shown to inhibit SARS-coronavirus (SARS-CoV) replication in vitro. Here the anti-SARS-CoV activity of 15 GL derivatives was tested. The introduction of 2-acetamido- β -d-glucopyranosylamine into the glycoside chain of GL resulted in 10-fold increased anti-SARS-CoV activity compared to GL. Amides of GL and conjugates of GL with two amino acid residues and a free 30-COOH function presented up to 70-fold increased activity against SARS-CoV but also increased cytotoxicity resulting in decreased selectivity index.]

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Triterpene einschließlich Steroide,
 in: HÄNSEL Rudolf, STICHER Otto (eds.) 2010⁹: *Pharmakognosie – Phytopharmazie*. (Springer-Lehrbuch) Berlin; Heidelberg: Springer, pp. 833-938. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-00963-1_24> [pdf]

[Zusammenfassung: Die Triterpene gehören zur Naturstoffgruppe der Isoprenoide (vgl. Kap. 23). Sie stellen eine außerordentlich umfangreiche Klasse von Terpenen dar. Sie werden in diesem Kapitel zusammen mit den sich davon ableitenden Steroiden zusammengefasst. Die Muttersubstanz aller Triterpene ist der azyklische C₃₀-Kohlenwasserstoff Squalen. Seine Zyklisierung wird durch Epoxidierung einer endständigen Doppelbindung eingeleitet. Da die Squalen-2,3-Epoxidstufe vor der Zyklisierung obligat durchlaufen werden muss, enthalten nahezu alle Triterpene und Steroide in Position C-3 eine Sauerstofffunktion. Vom Squalen ausgehend lassen sich zwei Hauptwege erkennen: Der eine führt zu den tetra- und penta-zyklischen Triterpenen, der andere über Cycloartenol zu den Cucurbitacinen und via das wichtigste Stoffwechselintermediärprodukt, das Cholesterol, zu den Phyosterolen, Cardenoliden und Bufadienoliden sowie zu den Steroidsapogeninen.

873: Tabelle 24.6 *Arzneidrogen mit Saponinen sowie Reinstoffe/Reinstoffgemische und ihre Verwendung.*]

■ Tabelle 24.6

Arzneidrogen mit Saponinen sowie Reinstoffe/Reinstoffgemische und ihre Verwendung

Arzneidroge/Reinstoff	Stammpflanze (Familie)	Saponintyp (Aglykone)/Verwendung	Seite
Bruchkraut (DAC 2003)	<i>Herniaria glabra</i> L. (Caryophyllaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Medicagensäure, Gypsogensäure, 16-Hydroxymedicagensäure)	–
Efeublätter (PhEur 6)	<i>Hedera helix</i> L. (Araliaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Hederagenin, Oleanolsäure)	886
Ginsengwurzel (PhEur 6)	<i>Panax ginseng</i> C. A. MEYER (Araliaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Protopanaxadiol und -triol, Oleanolsäure)	892
Goldrutenkraut (PhEur 6; zwei verschiedene Monographien)	<i>Solidago virgaurea</i> L. bzw. <i>S. gigantea</i> AIT. und <i>S. canadensis</i> L. (Asteraceae)	Triterpensaponine (Polygalasäure, Bayogenin)	1145
Mäusedornwurzelstock (PhEur 6, revidiert 6.1)	<i>Ruscus aculeatus</i> L. (Convallariaceae)	Steroidsaponine (Neoruscogenin, Ruscogenin)	908
Primelwurzel (PhEur 6)	<i>Primula veris</i> L. oder <i>P. elatior</i> (L.) HILL (Primulaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Protoprimulagenin A, Priverogenin B, Priverogenin-B-22-acetat, Anagalligenin A)	874
Ringelblumenblüten (PhEur 6)	<i>Calendula officinalis</i> L. (Asteraceae)	Triterpensaponine (Oleanolsäure)	861
Roskastaniensamen (DAB 2007)	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> L. (Sapindaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Protoaescigenin, Barringtogenol C)	890
Sarsaparillwurzel	<i>Smilax</i> -Spezies (Smilacaceae)	Steroidsaponine (Sarsapogenin, Smilagenin)	905
Seifenrinde (Helv 10.2, DAC 2005)	<i>Quillaja saponaria</i> MOL. (Rosaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Quillajasäure)	888
Seifenwurzel, rote	<i>Saponaria officinalis</i> L. (Caryophyllaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Quillajasäure, Gypsogenin)	–
Senegawurzel (PhEur 6)	<i>Polygala senega</i> L. (Polygalaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Presenegenin)	874
Süßholzwurzel (PhEur 6)	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> L., <i>G. inflata</i> BAT., <i>G. uralensis</i> FISCH. (Fabaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Glycyrrhetinsäure u. a.)	877
Wassernabelkraut, asiatisches (PhEur 6)	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) URBAN (Apiaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Asiatsäure, 6-Hydroxyasiatsäure, Madasiatsäure, Terminolsäure, Centellsapogenol A)	883
Wollblumen (PhEur 6)	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i> L., <i>V. densiflorum</i> BERTOL. und <i>V. phlomoides</i> L. (Scrophulariaceae)	Triterpensaponine (Verbascogenin; 13β,28-Epoxyoleanen)	757
Aescin (DAC 2003)	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> L. (Sapindaceae)	Venenmittel	890
Asiaticosid	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) URBAN (Apiaceae)	Wundheilmittel	884
Digitonin	<i>Digitalis purpurea</i> L. (Plantaginaceae)	Reagens	902
Diosgenin	<i>Dioscorea</i> -Spezies (Dioscoreaceae)	Grundstoff für Semisynthesen von Steroiden	904
<i>Gypsophila</i> -Saponine	<i>Gypsophila</i> -Spezies (Caryophyllaceae)	Standardsaponin zur Bestimmung der hämolytischen Aktivität	–
<i>Quillaja</i> -Saponine	<i>Quillaja saponaria</i> MOL. (Rosaceae)	Adjuvans	888

880: **Glycyrrhizin/GZ** “• Anwendung von GZ als Virustatikum. In neuerer Zeit steht insbesondere die antivirale Wirkung der GZ im Vordergrund des Interesses. GZ hemmt in vitro das Wachstum einer ganzen Reihe von DNA- und RNAViren, wie z. B. das HIV-1-, Hepatitis A, B, C, (HAV, HBV, HCV), Herpes simplex Typ 1- (HSV-1) und das Epstein-Barr-Virus, ferner Flaviviren (Gelb- und Dengue-Fieber, Hirnhautentzündung) und Coronaviren (SARS-CoV = SARS-associated coronavirus). GZ erwies sich von fünf getesteten Substanzen (neben GZ = Ribavirin, 6-Aza-Uridin, Pyrazofurin, Mycophenolsäure) als diejenige mit der größten Wirksamkeit gegen die Vermehrung des SARS-CoV. GZ verminderte dabei nicht nur die Virusreplikation, sondern auch die Adsorption des Virus an und die Penetration in die Wirtszelle. Am wirksamsten war GZ, wenn die Substanz sowohl während wie auch nach der Adsorptionsphase an die Wirtszelle verabreicht wurde. Als Wirkungsmechanismus wird die Hemmung bzw. die Induktion von Botenstoffen des Zellstoffwechsels postuliert. Neben HSV-1 ist GZ in der Lage, die latente Infektion beim Kaposi-Sarkom assoziierten Herpesvirus (KSHV) zu beenden. GZ reduziert dabei die Synthese eines viralen Latenzproteins, was schlussendlich zur Apoptose

der infizierten Zellen führt. Ob GZ oder GZDerivate zur Behandlung von Krankheiten eingesetzt werden können, welche durch latente Virusinfektionen verursacht werden, ist im Augenblick nicht absehbar. Dasselbe gilt für Derivate von GZ, z.B. GZGlykopeptide, welche die Aktivität gegen SARS-CoV stark erhöhen. Bisher wurde GZ an Patienten mit HIV-1 und chronischen HBV- und HCV-Infektionen verabreicht (vgl. dazu Übersicht von Fiore et al. 2008 und darin zitierte Literatur).”

MERS-CoV • Middle East Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus

MERS-Cov: Middle East Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus

German: Nahost-Atemwegssyndroms (MERS)

Anthony S.J., Gilard K. i, Menachery V.D., Goldstein T., Ssebid B. e, Mbabazi R., Navarrete-Macias I., Liang E., Wells H., Hicks A., Petrosov A., Byarugaba D.K., Debbink K., Dinnon K.H., Scobey T., Randell S.H., Yount B.L., Cranfield M., Johnson C.K., Baric R.S., Lipkin W.I., Mazet J.A., *Further evidence for bats as the evolutionary source of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus*, mBio 8 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00373-17>.

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PETROSILLO Nicola, VICECONTE Giulio, ERGONUL Onder, IPPOLITO Giuseppe, PETERSEN Eskild

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COVID-19, SARS and MERS: are they closely related? (Narrative Review)
in: Clinical Microbiology and Infection, 28 March 2020, In Press,
Journal Pre-proof. [23p., 2 tables, 52 refs.]
<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2020.03.026>>

[Abstract: Background: The 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) is a new human coronavirus which is spreading with epidemic features in China and other Asian countries with cases reported worldwide. This novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) is associated with a respiratory illness that may cause severe pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). Although related to the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), COVID-19 shows some peculiar pathogenetic, epidemiological and clinical features which have not been completely understood to date.

Objectives: We provide a review of the differences in terms of pathogenesis, epidemiology and clinical features between COVID-19, SARS and MERS.

Sources: The most recent literature in English language regarding COVID-19 has been reviewed and extracted data have been compared with the current scientific evidence about SARS and MERS epidemics.

Content: COVID-19 seems not to be very different from SARS regarding its clinical features. However, it has a fatality rate of 2.3%, lower than SARS (9.5%) and much lower than MERS (34.4%). It cannot be excluded that because of the COVID-19 less severe clinical picture it can spread in the community more easily than MERS and SARS. The actual basic reproductive number (R_0) of COVID-19 (2-2.5) is still controversial. It is probably slightly higher than the R_0 of SARS (1.7-1.9) and higher than MERS (<1). The gastrointestinal route of transmission of SARS-CoV-2, which has been also assumed for SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV, cannot be ruled out and needs to be further investigated.

Implications: There is still much more to know about COVID-19, especially as concerns mortality and capacity of spreading on a pandemic level. Nonetheless, all of the lessons we learned in the past from SARS and MERS epidemics are the best cultural weapons to face this new global threat. Keywords: Coronavirus; COVID-19; Emerging infections; MERS; SARS.]

SARSr-CoV • Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronaviruses

LI Wendong, SHI Zhengli, YU Meng, REN Wuze, SMITH Craig, EPSTEIN Jonathan H., WANG Hanzhong, CRAMERI Gary, HU Zhihong, ZHANG Huajun, ZHANG Jianhong, MCEACHERN Jennifer, FIELD Hume, DASZAK Peter, EATON Bryan T., ZHANG Shuyi, WANG Lin-Fa

°2005 [pdf]

Bats are natural reservoirs of SARS-like coronaviruses,

in: Science 310(5748): 676-679, 3 figs., 1 table.

<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/310/5748/676>>

[Abstract: Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) emerged in 2002 to 2003 in southern China. The origin of its etiological agent, the SARS coronavirus (SARS-CoV), remains elusive. Here we report that species of bats are a natural host of coronaviruses closely related to those responsible for the SARS outbreak. These viruses, termed SARS-like coronaviruses (SL-CoVs), display greater genetic variation than SARS-CoV isolated from humans or from civets. The human and civet isolates of SARS-CoV nestle phylogenetically within the spectrum of SL-CoVs, indicating that the virus responsible for the SARS outbreak was a member of this coronavirus group.]

ROBERTS A., D. Deming, PADDOCK C.D., CHENG A., YOUNT B., VOGEL L., HERMAN B.D., SHEAHAN T., HEISE M., GENRICH G.L., ZAKI S.R., BARIC R., SUBBARAO K.

2007

A mouse-adapted SARS-coronavirus causes disease and mortality in BALB/c mice,

in: PLoS Pathog. 3 (2007) e5.

<<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.0030005>>

GRAHAM R.L., BARIC R.S.

2010

Recombination, reservoirs, and the modular spike: mechanisms of coronavirus cross-species Transmission,

in: J. Virol. 84 (2010) 3134-3146.

<<https://doi.org/10.1128/JVI.01394-09>>

GE Xing-Yi, LI Jia-Lu, YANG Xing-Lou, CHMURA Aleksei A., ZHU Guangjian, EPSTEIN Jonathan H., MAZET Jonna K., HU Ben, ZHANG Wei, PENG Cheng, ZHANG Yu-Ji, LUO Chu-Ming, TAN Bing, WANG Ning, ZHU Yan, CRAMERI Gary, ZHANG Shu-Yi, WANG Lin-Fa, DASZAK Peter & SHI Zheng-Li [石正麗]

°2013 [pdf]

Isolation and characterization of a bat SARS-like coronavirus that uses the ACE2 receptor,

in: Nature 503: 535-538, 4 figs. [Extended data: 5 figs., 5 tables.]

<<https://doi.org/10.1038/nature12711>>

[Abstract: The 2002–3 pandemic caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) was one of the most significant public health events in recent history¹. An ongoing outbreak of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus² suggests that this group of viruses remains a key threat and that their distribution is wider than previously recognized. Although bats have been suggested to be the natural reservoirs of both viruses^{3,4,5}, attempts to isolate the progenitor virus of SARS-CoV from bats have been unsuccessful. Diverse SARS-like coronaviruses (SL-CoVs) have now been reported from bats in China, Europe and Africa^{5,6,7,8}, but none is considered a direct progenitor of SARS-CoV because of their phylogenetic disparity from this virus and the inability of their spike proteins to use the SARS-CoV cellular receptor molecule, the human angiotensin converting enzyme II (ACE2)^{9,10}. Here we report whole-genome sequences of two novel bat coronaviruses from Chinese horseshoe bats (family: Rhinolophidae) in Yunnan, China: RsSHC014 and Rs3367. These viruses are far more closely related to SARS-CoV than any previously identified bat coronaviruses, particularly in the receptor binding domain of the spike protein. Most importantly, we report the first recorded isolation of a live SL-CoV (bat SL-CoV-WIV1) from bat faecal samples in Vero E6 cells, which has typical coronavirus morphology, 99.9% sequence identity to Rs3367 and uses ACE2 from humans, civets and Chinese horseshoe bats for cell entry. Preliminary in vitro testing indicates that WIV1 also has a broad species tropism. Our results provide the strongest evidence to date that Chinese horseshoe bats are natural reservoirs of SARS-CoV, and that intermediate hosts may not be necessary for direct human infection by some bat SL-CoVs. They also highlight the importance

of pathogen-discovery programs targeting high-risk wildlife groups in emerging disease hotspots as a strategy for pandemic preparedness. –

Editorial Summary: *A SARS-like virus in bats*

Peter Daszak and colleagues identify two novel coronaviruses from Chinese horseshoe bats that are closely related to severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV), the cause of a pandemic during 2002 and 2003. / They also isolate a live virus from these bats that has high sequence identity to SARS-CoV and that can infect human cells using ACE2, the same receptor that is used by SARS-CoV. The results provide the strongest evidence to date that horseshoe bats are natural reservoirs of SARS-CoV.]

YANG Li, WU Zhiqiang, REN Xianwen, YANG Fan, HE Guimei, ZHANG Junpeng, DONG Jie, SUN Lilian, ZHU Yafang, DU Jiang, ZHANG Shuyi & JIN Qi

©2013 [pdf]

Novel SARS-like Betacoronaviruses in Bats, China, 2011,

in: *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 19(6): 989-991, 2 figs.

<<https://dx.doi.org/10.3201/eid1906.121648>>

<<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3713832/>>

[Abstract: To clarify the evolutionary relationships among betacoronaviruses that infect bats, we analyzed samples collected during 2010–2011 from 14 insectivorous bat species in China. We identified complete genomes of 2 novel betacoronaviruses in *Rhinolophus pusillus* and *Chaerephon plicata* bats, which showed close genetic relationships with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronaviruses. Keywords: Coronavirus, Chiroptera, SARS virus, China, viruses, bats.]

Figure 1. Phylogenetic tree of novel betacoronaviruses based on the nucleotide sequence of the *RdRp* gene. The following coronaviruses (CoVs) and GenBank accession numbers were used: bat severe acute respiratory syndrome CoV Rm1 (bat SARS-CoV Rm1; DQ412043), bat SARS-CoV Rp3 (DQ071615), bat SARS-CoV Rf1 (DQ412042), bat SARS-CoV HKU3 (DQ022305), SARS-CoV isolate Tor2/FP1-10895 (SARS-CoV Tor2; JX163925), SARS-CoV BJI182-12 (SARS-CoV BJI182; EU371564), SARS-CoV (NC004718), civet SARS-CoV SZ3 (AY304486), civet SARS-CoV SZ16 (AY304488), bat CoV HKU9 (BtCoV-HKU9; EF065513), bat CoV HKU4 (BtCoV-HKU4; EF065505), bat CoV HKU5 (BtCoV-HKU5; EF065509), human betacoronavirus 2c EMC/2012 (HCoV-EMC; JX869059), human CoV OC43 (HCoV-OC43; NC005147), HCoV-HKU1 (NC006577), bat coronavirus HKU2 (BtCoV-HKU2; NC009988), bat coronavirus 1A (BtCoV-1A; NC010437), HCoV-229E (NC002645), HCoV-NL63 (NC005831), bat CoV HKU8 (BtCoV-HKU8; NC010438), scotophilus bat CoV 512 (BtCoV-512; NC009657), avian infectious bronchiolitis virus (IBV; NC001451), beluga whale CoV SW1 (BwCoV; NC010646). Scale bar indicates genetic distance estimated by using TN93+G+I model implemented in MEGA5 (www.megasoftware.net).

Figure 2. Phylogenetic tree of novel betacoronaviruses based on the deduced amino acid sequence of spike protein. SARS, severe acute respiratory syndrome; CoV, coronavirus; HCoV, human CoV; BtCoV, bat CoV; BWCoV, beluga whale CoV; IBV, avian infectious bronchitis. Scale bar indicates genetic distance estimated by using WAG+G+I+F model implemented in MEGA5 (www.megasoftware.net).

HAN H.-J., WEN H.-l., ZHOU C.-M., CHEN F.-F., LUO L.-M., LIU J.-w., YU X.-J.
 2015 *Bats as reservoirs of severe emerging infectious diseases,*
 in: *Virus Res.* 205 (2015) 1-6.
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LU Guangwen, WANG Qihui, GAO George F.
 2015 [[pdf](#)] *Bat-to-human: spike features determining 'host jump' of coronaviruses SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and beyond,* (Feature Review)
 in: *Trends in Microbiology* 23(8): 468-478, 3 figs., 2 tables.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tim.2015.06.003>

[Highlights: • Bats are natural reservoirs of many coronaviruses that can infect humans.
 • Mechanisms of cross-species transmission of coronaviruses are important scientific questions.
 • The coronaviral spike protein is an important viral determinant of cross-species transmission.
 • Receptor-binding characteristics and cleavage priming of the spike protein are summarized.]
 Abstract: Both severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) are zoonotic pathogens that crossed the species barriers to infect humans. The mechanism of viral interspecies transmission is an important scientific question to be addressed. These coronaviruses contain a surface-located spike (S) protein that initiates infection by mediating receptor-recognition and membrane fusion and is therefore a key factor in host specificity. In addition, the S protein needs to be cleaved by host proteases before executing fusion, making these proteases a second determinant of coronavirus interspecies infection. Here, we summarize the progress made in the past decade in understanding the cross-species transmission of SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV by focusing on the features of the S protein, its receptor-binding characteristics, and the cleavage process involved in priming. Keywords: coronavirus; interspecies transmission; viral and host determinants; spike (S); SARS-CoV; MERS-CoV.]

MENACHERY Vineet D., YOUNT Boyd L. Jr, DEBBINK Kari, AGNIHOTHRAM Sudhakar, GRALINSKI Lisa E., PLANTE Jessica A., GRAHAM Rachel L., SCOBAY Trevor, GE Xing-Yi, DONALDSON Eric F., RANDELL Scott H., LANZAVECCHIA Antonio, MARASCO Wayne A., SHI Zheng-Li [石正麗] & BARIC Ralph S.
 2015 [[pdf](#)] *A SARS-like cluster of circulating bat coronaviruses shows potential for human emergence,*
 in: *Nature Medicine* 21(12): 1508-1513, 4 figs; Supplementary Figures 1-6 and Supplementary Tables 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.3985>
 [This article has been corrected. See *Nature Medicine* 2016 April; 22(4): 446.]

[Abstract: The emergence of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS)-CoV underscores the threat of cross-species transmission events leading to outbreaks in humans. Here we examine the disease potential of a SARS-like virus, SHC014-CoV, which is currently circulating in Chinese horseshoe bat populations¹. Using the SARS-CoV reverse genetics system², we generated and characterized a chimeric virus expressing the spike of bat coronavirus SHC014 in a mouse-adapted SARS-CoV backbone. The results indicate that group 2b viruses encoding the SHC014 spike in a wild-type backbone can efficiently use multiple orthologs of the SARS receptor human angiotensin converting enzyme II (ACE2), replicate efficiently in primary human airway cells and achieve in vitro titers equivalent to epidemic strains of SARS-CoV. Additionally, in vivo experiments demonstrate replication of the chimeric virus in mouse lung with notable pathogenesis. Evaluation of available SARS-based immune-therapeutic and prophylactic modalities revealed poor efficacy; both monoclonal antibody and vaccine approaches failed to neutralize and protect from infection with CoVs using the novel spike protein. On the basis of these findings, we synthetically re-derived an infectious full-length SHC014 recombinant virus and demonstrate robust viral replication both in vitro and in vivo. Our work suggests a potential risk of SARS-CoV re-emergence from viruses currently circulating in bat populations. –

1. Ge, X.Y. et al. *Isolation and characterization of a bat SARS-like coronavirus that uses the ACE2 receptor*. Nature 503, 535–538 (2013).

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GE Xing-Yi, WANG Ning, ZHANG Wei, HU Ben, LI Bei, ZHANG Yun-Zhi, ZHOU Ji-Hua, LUO Chu-Ming, YANG Xing-Lou, WU Li-Jun, WANG Bo, ZHANG Yun, LI Zong-Xiao, SHI Zheng-Li [石正麗]

©2016 [2 pdf]

Coexistence of multiple coronaviruses in several bat colonies in an abandoned mineshaft,

in: *Virologica Sinica* 31(1): 31-40, 4 figs. [Electronic supplementary material: 2p. Table S1.] <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12250-016-3713-9>>

[Abstract: Since the 2002–2003 severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) outbreak prompted a search for the natural reservoir of the SARS coronavirus, numerous alpha- and betacoronaviruses have been discovered in bats around the world. Bats are likely the natural reservoir of alpha- and betacoronaviruses, and due to the rich diversity and global distribution of bats, the number of bat coronaviruses will likely increase. We conducted a surveillance of coronaviruses in bats in an abandoned mineshaft in Mojiang County, Yunnan Province, China, from 2012–2013. Six bat species were frequently detected in the cave: *Rhinolophus sinicus*, *Rhinolophus affinis*, *Hipposideros pomona*, *Miniopterus schreibersii*, *Miniopterus fuliginosus*, and *Miniopterus fuscus*. By sequencing PCR products of the coronavirus RNA-dependent RNA polymerase gene (*RdRp*), we found a high frequency of infection by a diverse group of coronaviruses in different bat species in the mineshaft. Sequenced partial *RdRp* fragments had 80%–99% nucleic acid sequence identity with well-characterized *Alphacoronavirus* species, including BtCoV HKU2, BtCoV HKU8, and BtCoV1, and unassigned species BtCoV HKU7 and BtCoV HKU10. Additionally, the surveillance identified two unclassified betacoronaviruses, one new strain of SARS-like coronavirus, and one potentially new betacoronavirus species. Furthermore, coronavirus co-infection was detected in all six bat species, a phenomenon that fosters recombination and promotes the emergence of novel virus strains. Our findings highlight the importance of bats as natural reservoirs of coronaviruses and the potentially zoonotic source of viral pathogens.]

Figure 1. Sample collection site in Mojiang, Yunnan Province. The mineshaft where bat samples were collected is indicated with a red dot, three county towns (Mojiang, Zhenyuan, and Ning'er) near the mineshaft are labeled with green dots.

MENACHERY Vineet D. *et al.*

2016 *SARS-like WIV1-CoV poised for human emergence,*
in: PNAS 113: 3048-3053.

ANTHONY S.J., GILARDI K., MENACHERY Vineet D., GOLDSTEIN T., SSEBIDE B., MBABAZI R., NAVARRETE-MACIAS I., LIANG E., WELLS H., HICKS A., PETROSOV A., BYARUGABA D.K., DEBBINK K., DINNON K.H., SCOBAY T., RANDELL S.H., YOUNT B.L., CRANFIELD M., JOHNSON C.K., BARIC R.S., LIPKIN W.I., MAZET J.A.

2017 *Further evidence for bats as the evolutionary source of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus,*
in: mBio 8 (2017).
<<https://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00373-17>>

HU B., ZENG L.-P., YANG X.-L., GE X.-Y., ZHANG W., LI B., XIE J.-Z., SHEN X.-R., ZHANG Y.-Z., WANG N., LUO D.-S., ZHENG X.-S., WANG M.-N., DASZAK P., WANG L.-F., CUI J., SHI Zheng-Li [石正麗]

2017 *Discovery of a rich gene pool of bat SARS-related coronaviruses provides new insights into the origin of SARS coronavirus,*
in: PLoS Pathog. 13 (2017) e1006698.
<<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.ppat.1006698>>

WANG, N. *et al.*

2018 *Serological Evidence of Bat SARS-Related Coronavirus Infection in Humans, China,*
in: Virol Sin 33: 104-107.

LI Hongying, MENDELSON Emma, ZONG Chen, ZHANG Wei, HAGAN Emily, WANG Ning, LI Shiyue, YAN Hong, HUANG Huimin, ZHU Guangjian, ROSS Noam, CHMURA Aleksei, TERRY Philip, FIELDER Mark, MILLER Maureen, SHI Zhengli [石正麗], DASZAK Peter

°2019 [pdf] *Human-animal interactions and bat coronavirus spillover potential among rural residents in Southern China,*
in: Biosafety and Health 1(2): 84-90, 2 figs., 1 table, 60 refs.
<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bsheal.2019.10.004>>

[Highlights: • Scientific question.

What are the behavioral risks in human-animal interactions that could lead to the emergence of bat coronaviruses in human population.

• Evidence before this study.

Bat borne coronaviruses have caused several emerging infectious disease outbreaks of global significance, including SARS. Novel SARS-related coronaviruses have been discovered in bat populations in Southern China, some of which have the capacity to infect human cells. Human-animal interactions are thought to be critical for the emergence of bat coronaviruses, however the specific interactions linked to animal-to-human spillover remain unknown.

• New Findings.

This study found serological evidence for bat-borne coronavirus transmission to people. Direct contact with bats was not identified as a risk factor. However, self-reported severe acute respiratory infection (SARI) and/or influenza-like illness (ILI) was linked to human interaction with other wildlife and livestock, suggesting that there may be other zoonotic exposures leading to clinical illness in these populations.

• Significance of the study.

Findings from this study suggested that an integrated biological and behavioral surveillance in healthy community settings can help identify potential zoonotic disease spillover events or target surveillance to at-risk populations. This approach represents a potential early-warning system that could be used under non-outbreak conditions to identify potential zoonotic emerging diseases prior to largescale outbreaks.

Abstract: Human interaction with animals has been implicated as a primary risk factor for several high impact zoonoses, including many bat-origin viral diseases. However the animal-to-human spillover events that lead to emerging diseases are rarely observed or clinically exami-

ned, and the link between specific interactions and spillover risk is poorly understood. To investigate this phenomenon, we conducted biological-behavioral surveillance among rural residents in Yunnan, Guangxi, and Guangdong districts of Southern China, where we have identified a number of SARS-related coronaviruses in bats. Serum samples were tested for four bat-borne coronaviruses using newly developed enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA). Survey data were used to characterize associations between human-animal contact and bat coronavirus spillover risk. A total of 1,596 residents were enrolled in the study from 2015 to 2017. Nine participants (0.6%) tested positive for bat coronaviruses. 265 (17%) participants reported severe acute respiratory infections (SARI) and/or influenza-like illness (ILI) symptoms in the past year, which were associated with poultry, carnivore, rodent/shrew, or bat contact, with variability by family income and district of residence. This study provides serological evidence of bat coronavirus spillover in rural communities in Southern China. The low seroprevalence observed in this study suggests that **bat coronavirus spillover is a rare event**. Nonetheless, this study highlights associations between human-animal interaction and zoonotic spillover risk. These findings can be used to support targeted biological behavioral surveillance in high-risk geographic areas in order to reduce the risk of zoonotic disease emergence.

Keywords: Bat coronavirus; Human-animal interaction; Disease emergence; Southern China; Rural community.]

CUI J., LI F., SHI Zheng-Li [石正麗]

2019

Origin and evolution of pathogenic coronaviruses,
in: *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 17 (2019) 181-192.
<<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-018-0118-9>>

FAN Yi, ZHAO Kai, SHI Zheng-Li [石正麗] & ZHOU Peng

°2019 [pdf]

Bat Coronaviruses in China,
in: *Viruses* 11(3): 210. [14p., 2 figs., 1 table, 77 refs.]
<<https://doi.org/10.3390/v11030210>>
<<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6466186/>>

[Abstract: During the past two decades, three zoonotic coronaviruses have been identified as the cause of large-scale disease outbreaks—Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), and Swine Acute Diarrhea Syndrome (SADS). SARS and MERS emerged in 2003 and 2012, respectively, and caused a worldwide pandemic that claimed thousands of human lives, while SADS struck the swine industry in 2017. They have common characteristics, such as they are all highly pathogenic to humans or livestock, their agents originated from bats, and two of them originated in China. Thus, it is highly likely that future SARS- or MERS-like coronavirus outbreaks will originate from bats, and there is an increased probability that this will occur in China. Therefore, the investigation of bat coronaviruses becomes an urgent issue for the detection of early warning signs, which in turn minimizes the impact of such future outbreaks in China. The purpose of the review is to summarize the current knowledge on viral diversity, reservoir hosts, and the geographical distributions of bat coronaviruses in China, and eventually we aim to predict virus hotspots and their cross-species transmission potential. Keywords: coronavirus, bat, epidemiology, cross-species, zoonosis.]

Conclusions: This study explored the relationship among zoonotic risk and human behaviour, environment and policies in rural communities in southern China. It identifies key behavioural risk factors that can be targeted for development of tailored risk-mitigation strategies to reduce the threat of novel zoonoses.

Keywords: ethnographic, qualitative, rural communities, southern China, Zoonotic Risk, 2019-nCoV, coronavirus, SARS. Topic: animals, wild china zoonoses community.]

COVID-19 • SARS-CoV-2 • 2019-nCoV

xīnxíng guānzhhuàng bìngdú gǎnrǎn 新型冠状病毒感染 ‘new coronavirus infection’

fèiyán 肺炎 ‘pneumonia; lungenentzündung’

NCIP • novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV)-infected pneumonia, *xīnguān fèiyán* 新冠肺炎

COVID-19 “corona virus disease 2019”; German “Coronavirus-Krankheit 2019” (disease name)

SARS-CoV-2 (virus name)

Case reporting websites

- WHO <<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/situation-reports>>
Dashboard: Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) Situation
<<https://experience.arcgis.com/experience/685d0ace521648f8a5beee1b9125cd>>
- U.S. CDC <<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/index.html>>
- ECDC <<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/home>>
- China CDC (CCDC) <<http://www.chinacdc.cn/en/>>
- China CDC Tracking the Epidemic: <<http://weekly.chinacdc.cn/news/TrackingtheEpidemic.htm>>
[National Health Commission Updates]
- NHC 国家卫生健康委员会统计信息中心 <http://www.nhc.gov.cn/yjb/s3578/new_list.shtml>
- DXY [Dingxiang yuan] 丁香园
<<https://3g.dxy.cn/newh5/view/pneumonia?scene=2&clicktime=1579582238&enterid=1579582238&from=singlemessage&isappinstalled=0>>
DXY is a Chinese website that aggregates NHC and local CCDC situation reports in near real-time, providing more current regional case estimates than the national level reporting organizations are capable of, and is thus used for all the mainland China cases reported in our dashboard (confirmed, suspected, recovered, deaths).
- *the_wuhan_virus*, by thebaselab <<https://thewuhanvirus.com/>>
- National Health Commission of the People’s Republic of China (Chinese language)
<http://www.nhc.gov.cn/xcs/xxgzbd/gzbd_index.shtml>
- [tracking map] Wuhan Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Global Cases (by JHU CSSE)
As of Jan 25, 2020 12:00 am EST
<<https://gisanddata.maps.arcgis.com/apps/opsdashboard/index.html#/bda7594740fd40299423467b48e9ecf6>>
We are tracking the 2019-nCoV spread in real-time. Cases and locations can be viewed here; data available for download. Blog: <<https://systems.jhu.edu/research/public-health/ncov/>>
[JHU CSSE • Johns Hopkins University, Center for Systems Science and Engineering; cf. GARDNER 2020.]
- Timeline of the 2019–20 Wuhan coronavirus outbreak
<https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Timeline_of_the_2019%E2%80%9320_coronavirus_pandemic#/cite_note-Schirring16Jan2020-53>
- 2019–20 Wuhan coronavirus outbreak (with 281/648 references!)
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2019%E2%80%9320_Wuhan_coronavirus_outbreak>

- Recombinomics: Coronavirus (2019-nCoV)
<<http://recombinomics.co/forum/431-coronavirus-2019-ncov/>>
- Worldometer: COVID-19 Coronavirus Outbreak
<<https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>>
- Neues Coronavirus, Bundesamt für Gesundheit BAG, Switzerland
<<https://www.bag.admin.ch/bag/de/home/krankheiten/ausbrueche-epidemien-pandemien/aktuelle-ausbrueche-epidemien/novel-cov.html> - 520017891>
- National Institute of Infectious Diseases, Japan
<<https://www.niid.go.jp/niid/en/2019-ncov-e.html>>
- La Repubblica • Coronavirus, i contagi in Italia per regione • Coronavirus, i numeri in Italia per provincia <<https://lab.gedidigital.it/gedi-visual/2020/coronavirus-i-contagi-in-italia/>>
- Robert Koch Institut: SARS-CoV-2: Fallzahlen in Deutschland, China und weltweit.
<https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/InfAZ/N/Neuartiges_Coronavirus/Fallzahlen.html>
- National Institutes of Health: Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)
<<https://www.nih.gov/health-information/coronavirus>>
- Evidence Aid: Coronavirus (COVID-19) resources
<<https://www.evidenceaid.org/coronavirus-resources/>>
- Epidemic Data for COVID-19 (World)
<<https://www.wolframcloud.com/obj/examples/COVID19World>>
This interactive dashboard displays the latest information on the COVID-19 epidemic, patient symptoms and outcomes, and the genetic makeup of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. All visualizations and analyses are created in the Wolfram Language using curated data from the Wolfram Data Repository and other sources. Click the navigation buttons for more detail on each dataset.
- nCoV2019.live, Avi Schiffmann.
<<https://ncov2019.live/data>>
- Nextstrain. Real-time tracking of pathogen evolution. Novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV)
<<https://nextstrain.org/>>
Nextstrain is an open-source project to harness the scientific and public health potential of pathogen genome data. We provide a continually-updated view of publicly available data alongside powerful analytic and visualization tools for use by the community. Our goal is to aid epidemiological understanding and improve outbreak response. If you have any questions, or simply want to say hi, please give us a shout at hello@nextstrain.org.
 - *Genomic epidemiology of novel coronavirus (nCoV)* <<https://nextstrain.org/ncov>>
 - *Phylogeny of SARS-like betacoronaviruses including novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2.*
Built with github.com/blab/sars-like-cov. Maintained by Trevor BEDFORD.
<<https://nextstrain.org/groups/blab/sars-like-cov>>
 - *Genomic analysis of nCoV spread. Situation report 2020-01-30.*
<<https://nextstrain.org/narratives/ncov/sit-rep/en/2020-01-30>>

[Executive summary

Using 42 publicly shared novel coronavirus (nCoV) genomes, we examined genetic diversity to infer date of common ancestor and rate of spread. We find:

- the 42 sampled genomes are very similar, differing from the consensus by 0-7 mutations
- This lack of genetic diversity has a parsimonious explanation that the outbreak descends either from a single introduction into the human population or a small number of animal-to-human transmissions of very similar viruses.
- This event most likely occurred in November or early December 2019.
- There has been ongoing human-to-human spread since this point resulting in observed cases.
- Using estimates of total case count from Imperial College London of several thousand cases, we infer a reproductive number between 1.8 and 3.5 indicating rapid growth in the November 2019-January 2020 period.]

- Genomic epidemiology of SARS-CoV2.
<https://www.gisaid.org/epiflu-applications/next-sars-cov2-app/>

- Genomic epidemiology of novel coronavirus (hCoV-19).
 avatarBuilt with nextstrain/ncov using data from gisaid-logo.
 Showing 711 of 711 genomes sampled between Dec 2019 and Mar 2020.
 [radial, updated regularly] <https://nextstrain.org/ncov?!=radial>

Daily reports WHO • NHC PRC • Health Commission of Hubei Province

- WHO: Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) situation reports; 1 (21 January 2020) onwards
<<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/situation-reports/>>
- National Health Commission of the People's Republic of China (Chinese language)
<http://www.nhc.gov.cn/xcs/xxgzbd/gzbd_index.shtml>
- Hubeisheng weisheng jiankang weiyuanhui 湖北省卫生健康委员会 • Health Commission of Hubei Province
<<http://wjw.hubei.gov.cn/fbjd/tzgg/index.shtml>>

Bibliographies • Living Papers

- Living Paper: Coronavirus COVID-19. ★
The living paper on the new coronavirus disease (COVID-19) provides a structured compilation of scientific data about the virus, the disease and its control. Its objective is to help scientists identify the most relevant publications on COVID-19 in the mass of information that appears every day. It is also expected to foster a global understanding of disease control and stimulate transdisciplinary initiatives. / This living paper is updated on a weekly basis.
<https://rega.kuleuven.be/if/corona_covid-19>
- CWML COVID-19 Literature.
This collection of literature about COVID-19 is updated daily by Yale's Cushing/Whitney Medical Library staff to support the research missions of the Yale Schools of Medicine and Public Health.
<https://www.zotero.org/groups/2465841/cwml_covid-19_literature/>
- MCINTOSH Kenneth (author), HIRSCH Martin S. (section editor), BLOOM Allyson (deputy editor) 2020 *Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19)*.
UpToDate. Literature review current through: Feb 2020. This topic last updated: Mar 27, 2020. [151 refs.]
<https://www.uptodate.com/contents/coronavirus-disease-2019-covid-19?source=history_widget>

Syllabi • Teaching Tools

- #coronavirussyllabus | a crowdsourced cross-disciplinary resource.
*open access / contributors? see #coronavirussyllabus + click notification button on top right of the page
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1dTkJmhWQ8NcxhmjeLp6ybT1_YOPhFLx9hZ43j1S7DjE/edit>
- Teaching COVID-19: An Anthropology Syllabus Project.
<<http://teachinglearninganthro.com/teaching-covid-19-an-anthropology-syllabus-project/>>
- EISENBERG Merle, MCDUGALL Sara & MORREALE Laura (2020) *Middle Ages for Educators*.
April 2, 2020. doi:10.5281/zenodo.3738188. <<http://middleagesforeducators.com/>>
See Linked Resources: <<http://middleagesforeducators.com/linked-resources/>>
> Pandemics & Plague; > COVID-19 Era Open Access Publishing; > Adjacent Fields with Resources; > COVID-19 Era Special Online Presentations.

COVID-19 Research & Development

- *Database of publications on coronavirus disease (COVID-19).*

You can search the WHO database of publications on coronavirus disease (COVID-19). Articles are searchable by author, key word (title, author, journal), journal, or by general topic. To see the most recently added citations, select “Newest updates”. The database is updated daily, Monday through Friday.

<<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/global-research-on-novel-coronavirus-2019-ncov>>

- *Update on research activities for novel coronavirus.* WHO’s R&D Blueprint has been activated to accelerate diagnostics, vaccines and therapeutics for this outbreak.

<<https://www.who.int/blueprint/priority-diseases/key-action/novel-coronavirus/en/>>

- WHO: *International Clinical Trials Registry Platform.*

<<http://apps.who.int/trialsearch/AdvSearch.aspx?SearchTermStat=117&ReturnUrl=~/ListBy.aspx?TypeListing=0>>

- SNF: Sonderausschreibung für Forschung zu Coronaviren, 27.02.2020

Abteilung InterCo / Marc Zbinden und Timothy Ryan / E-Mail interco@snf.ch

<<http://www.snf.ch/de/fokusForschung/newsroom/Seiten/news-200227-sonderausschreibung-fuer-forschung-zu-coronaviren.aspx>>

Biomedical, epidemiological, genetic studies

Websites collecting scientific information

- Springer Nature, Coronavirus campaign
<<https://www.springernature.com/gp/researchers/campaigns/coronavirus>>
- Nature, Coronavirus latest
<<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-00154-w>>
- bioRxiv, Results for term “covid”
<https://www.biorxiv.org/search/covid%20jcode%3Amedrxiv%7C%7Cbiorxiv%20numresults%3A75%20sort%3Apublication-date%20direction%3Adescending%20format_result%3Astandard>
- F1000: The COVID-19 articles you need to read.
Our Faculty have evaluated the literature relevant to the recent COVID-19 outbreak, and handpicked the most relevant and important research to help tackle this global crisis. To assist in addressing this epidemic we have made all recommendations of articles relating to COVID-19 and the coronavirus family freely available to access on F1000Prime. <<https://f1000.com/prime/covid-19/>>
- SSRN’s Coronavirus and Infectious Disease Research
<<https://www.ssrn.com/index.cfm/en/coronavirus/>>
SSRN’s Coronavirus and Infectious Disease Research page provides a curated view into the early-stage research to help researchers, public health authorities, clinicians and the public understand, contain and manage this disease.
Emerging and rapidly evolving healthcare emergencies necessitate the quick dissemination of research. The growing role of early-stage research, often referred to as preprints, was acknowledged in the Ebola and Zika virus outbreaks as a way of “accelerating the dissemination of scientific findings to support responses to infectious disease outbreaks”. SSRN Elsevier’s world-leading platform devoted to the rapid worldwide dissemination of early-stage research, is committed to making coronavirus related research available immediately. Research on SSRN is free to download and upload. It is important to note that these papers have not benefited from the pivotal role of peer-review, which validates and improves the quality of final published journal articles.
Content is presented in the following categories:
 - COVID-19 Research - on the COVID-19 outbreak originating in Wuhan, Hubei province, China, and escalating in January 2020.
[rodo: March 8, 193 papers] <<https://www.ssrn.com/link/Coronavirus-Infectious-Disease-Research.html>>
 - Infectious Disease Research - on infectious diseases including coronavirus, SARS, MERS and ebola.
 - Interdisciplinary Coronavirus & Infectious Disease Related Research - related to public health, legal, economic, societal and fiscal implications.A few additional resources for staying up to date on COVID-19
 - The Johns Hopkins Coronavirus COVID-19 Global Cases site
 - The US CDC’s Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) web page
 - Healthmap animated view of the spread of COVID-19
- ChinaXiv: zhōngguó kēxuéyuàn kējì lùnwén yù fābù píngtái 中國科學院科技論文預發佈
<<http://chinaxiv.org/user/search.htm>>
- Elsevier: Novel Coronavirus Information Center
Elsevier’s free health and medical research on novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV), January 27, 2020 –
Expert guidance / Clinical information / 中文资源 (Chinese-language) / Research / Drug discovery /
Related resources & news
<<https://www.elsevier.com/connect/coronavirus-information-center>>
- JAMA Network: Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)
Check back here for updates on COVID-19 diagnosis and treatment
<<https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/pages/coronavirus-alert>>

- WorldCat: List of helpful e-resources
<https://www.worldcat.org/search?qt=worldcat_org_all&q=covid-19>
- Oxford University Press: Free Resources for Instructors and Students Affected by Covid-19
<<https://pages.oup.com/he/us/covidresourcepage>>
- (Questionnaire in French, Institut Pasteur) Self-test / s'auto-tester au coronavirus en répondant à quelques questions. <<https://maladiecoronavirus.fr/>>
- Science: Coronavirus: Research, Commentary, and News
<<https://www.sciencemag.org/coronavirus-research-commentary-and-news>>
- Centre d'enseignement et de recherche en action humanitaire de Genève (CERAH Genève): COVID-19 Scientific Resources
<<https://cerahgeneve.ch/resources/covid-19-free-online-scientific-resources/>>
- Moitessier Research Group COVID-19 Info Page
<<http://moitessier-group.mcgill.ca/covid.html>>
- Zenodo: Coronavirus Disease Research Community – COVID-19
<<https://zenodo.org/communities/covid-19/>>
- Academia.edu: Covid-19 (Coronavirus) INFECTIOUS DISEASE
<<https://www.academia.edu/coronavirus-covid-19/papers>>
- Figshare: COVID-19 open research data
<<https://covid19.figshare.com/>>

Virology • Phylogeny and Genome of SARS-like betacoronaviruses

ANDERSEN Kristian

*2020a

*Clock and TMRCa based on 27 genomes. (Novel 2019 coronavirus)
Estimates of the clock and TMRCa for 2019-nCoV based on 27 genomes.
January 25, 2020.*

<http://virological.org/t/clock-and-tmrca-based-on-27-genomes/347>

[Following up on the analyses provided by Andrew Rambaut this is a brief report estimating the evolutionary rate and timing of the epidemic (date of the most recent ancestor (MRCA)) based on 27 publicly shared n2019-nCoV genome sequences. Compared to earlier analyses where several parameters had to be fixed, there is now enough information content in the sequences to obtain reasonable estimates of the clock and TMRCa without fixing parameters. This work is for information purposes only and is not intended for publication. All the data used here is provided by the laboratories listed below through NCBI Genbank or GISAID.

Data: As of January 25, 2020, 28 full-length nCoV-2019 genomes and 1 partial genome are available on the GISAID 14 platform. The partial genome (EPI_ISL_402126) and one with too many sequencing errors (EPI_ISL_403928) were eliminated from these analyses. The final dataset contained 27 full-length nCoV-2019 genomes with 41 SNPs in total, 9 of them masked because of likely sequencing errors (leaving 32 SNPs in the dataset). Acknowledgements of the genome sequences used in this analysis are in the table at the end of this document.]

*2020b

nCoV-2019 codon usage and reservoir (not snakes v2).

Virological.org. January 24, 2020, last edited January 31, 2020.

<http://virological.org/t/ncov-2019-codon-usage-and-reservoir-not-snakes-v2/339>

[Critical assessment of Ji Wei *et al.* 2020:

“(…) In conclusion, the study by Ji *et al.* is flawed and **there is no evidence for snakes being the reservoir for nCoV-2019.** This does not mean that snakes couldn’t be the reservoir, however, there is currently no data to support this claim and I find that hypothesis unlikely given that nCoV-2019 is closely related to SARS-CoV-like viruses circulating in bats. At this stage, **we still do not know what the reservoir for nCoV-2019 is and how wide-spread it is** (although bats seem likely). Finally, the premise that one would be able to use a

single simple measure such as codon adaptation to identify reservoir hosts for novel viruses is incorrect. (...)” (emphasis by author)]

ANDERSEN Kristian G., RAMBAUT Andrew, LIPKIN W. Ian, HOLMES Edward C. & GARRY Robert F.
 ©2020 [pdf]

The proximal origin of SARS-CoV-2, (Correspondence)
 in: Nature Medicine (2020).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0820-9>

[Sections: Notable features of the SARS-CoV-2 genome / Theories of SARS-CoV-2 origins / Conclusions / References / Acknowledgements / Author information / Ethics declarations / Rights and permissions / About this article.]

Theories of SARS-CoV-2 origins

“It is improbable that SARS-CoV-2 emerged through laboratory manipulation of a related SARS-CoV-like coronavirus. As noted above, the RBD of SARS-CoV-2 is optimized for binding to human ACE2 with an efficient solution different from those previously predicted^{7,11}. Furthermore, if genetic manipulation had been performed, one of the several reverse-genetic systems available for betacoronaviruses would probably have been used¹⁹. However, the genetic data irrefutably show that SARS-CoV-2 is not derived from any previously used virus backbone²⁰. Instead, we propose two scenarios that can plausibly explain the origin of SARS-CoV-2: (i) natural selection in an animal host before zoonotic transfer; and (ii) natural selection in humans following zoonotic transfer. We also discuss whether selection during passage could have given rise to SARS-CoV-2.”

3. Selection during passage

“In theory, it is possible that SARS-CoV-2 acquired RBD mutations (Fig. 1a) during adaptation to passage in cell culture, as has been observed in studies of SARS-CoV¹¹. The finding of SARS-CoV-like coronaviruses from pangolins with nearly identical RBDs, however, provides a much stronger and more parsimonious explanation of how SARS-CoV-2 acquired these via recombination or mutation¹⁹.

The acquisition of both the polybasic cleavage site and predicted O-linked glycans also argues against culture-based scenarios. New polybasic cleavage sites have been observed only after prolonged passage of low-pathogenicity avian influenza virus in vitro or in vivo¹⁷. Furthermore, a hypothetical generation of SARS-CoV-2 by cell culture or animal passage would have required prior isolation of a progenitor virus with very high genetic similarity, which has not been described. Subsequent generation of a polybasic cleavage site would have then required repeated passage in cell culture or animals with ACE2 receptors similar to those of humans, but such work has also not previously been described. Finally, the generation of the predicted O-linked glycans is also unlikely to have occurred due to cell-culture passage, as such features suggest the involvement of an immune system¹⁸.”

Conclusions: “(...) The genomic features described here may explain in part the infectiousness and transmissibility of SARS-CoV-2 in humans. Although the evidence shows that SARS-CoV-2 is not a purposefully manipulated virus, it is currently impossible to prove or disprove the other theories of its origin described here. However, since we observed all notable SARS-CoV-2 features, including the optimized RBD and polybasic cleavage site, in related coronaviruses in nature, we do not believe that any type of laboratory-based scenario is plausible.”]

Fig. 1: Features of the spike protein in human SARS-CoV-2 and related coronaviruses.

a, Mutations in contact residues of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein. The spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 (red bar at top) was aligned against the most closely related SARS-CoV-like coronaviruses and SARS-CoV itself. Key residues in the spike protein that make contact to the ACE2 receptor are marked with blue boxes in both SARS-CoV-2 and related viruses, including SARS-CoV (Urbani strain). b, Acquisition of polybasic cleavage site and O-linked glycans. Both the polybasic cleavage site and the three adjacent predicted O-linked glycans are unique to SARS-CoV-2 and were not previously seen in lineage B betacoronaviruses. Sequences shown are from NCBI GenBank, accession codes MN908947, MN996532, AY278741, KY417146 and MK211376. The pangolin coronavirus sequences are a consensus generated from SRR10168377 and SRR10168378 (NCBI BioProject PRJNA573298)^{29,30}.

BEDFORD Tevor
2020

Phylogeny of SARS-like betacoronaviruses including novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2.

Built with github.com/blab/sars-like-cov.

Maintained by Trevor Bedford.

<https://nextstrain.org/groups/blab/sars-like-cov>

[This phylogeny shows evolution of SARS-like betacoronaviruses including samples from the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2 causing the COVID-19 epidemic in Hubei and in China. SARS-CoV-2 coronaviruses from the COVID-19 epidemic are colored in red, SARS-CoV-1 coronaviruses from the 2002-03 SARS outbreak are colored in yellow, while related SARS-like coronaviruses are colored in blue.

Full details on bioinformatic processing can be found here: <https://github.com/blab/sars-like-cov>

We gratefully acknowledge the Authors, Originating and Submitting laboratories of the genetic sequence and metadata made available through GISAID <https://gisaid.org/> on which this research is based.

The SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus genomes were generously shared by scientists at the Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center & School of Public Health, Fudan University (*WH-Human_1*), at the National Institute for Viral Disease Control and Prevention, China CDC, Beijing, China (*Wuhan/IVDC-HB-01/2019*, *Wuhan/IVDC-HB-05/2019*, *IVDC-HB-04/2020*) at the Institute of Pathogen Biology, Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences & Peking Union Medical College, Beijing, China (*Wuhan/IPBCAMS-WH-01/2019*), and at the Wuhan Institute of Virology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Wuhan, China (*Wuhan/WIV04/2019*, *bat/Yunnan/ RaTG13/2013*).

Related SARS-like bat virus was shared by Zhu et al at the Wuhan Institute of Virology, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Wuhan, China (*bat/Yunnan/RaTG13/2013*). Related SARS-like pangolin viruses were shared by Lam, Cao et al at the State Key Laboratory of Pathogen and Biosecurity, Beijing Institute of Microbiology and Epidemiology, Beijing, China and at the State Key Laboratory of Emerging Infectious Diseases and Centre of Influenza Research, University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong (*pangolin/Guangdong/P2S/2019*, *pangolin/Guangxi/P1E/2017*, *pangolin/Guangxi/P2V/2017*, *pangolin/Guangxi/P3B/2017*, *pangolin/Guangxi/P4L/2017*, *pangolin/Guangxi/P5E/2017*, *pangolin/Guangxi/P5L/2017*). Other related SARS-like pangolin viruses were shared by Shen, Xiao et al at the South China Agricultural University (*pangolin/Guangdong/1/2020*).]

BONI Maciej F., LEMEY Philippe, JIANG Xiaowei, LAM Tommy Tsan-Yuk, PERRY Blair, CASTOE Todd, RAMBAUT Andrew, ROBERTSON David L.

°2020 [pdf]

Evolutionary origins of the SARS-CoV-2 sarbecovirus lineage responsible for the COVID-19 pandemic,

in: bioRxiv, March 31, 2020. [25p., 5 figs., Supplementary Materials and Figures: 20p., figs. S1-S14, tables S1-S2.]

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.30.015008>

[Abstract: There are outstanding evolutionary questions on the recent emergence of coronavirus SARS-CoV-2/hCoV-19 in Hubei province that caused the COVID-19 pandemic, including (1) the relationship of the new virus to the SARS-related coronaviruses, (2) the role of bats as a reservoir species, (3) the potential role of other mammals in the emergence event, and (4) the role of recombination in viral emergence. Here, we address these questions and find that the sarbecoviruses – the viral subgenus responsible for the emergence of SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 – exhibit frequent recombination, but the SARS-CoV-2 lineage itself is not a recombinant of any viruses detected to date. In order to employ phylogenetic methods to date the divergence events between SARS-CoV-2 and the bat sarbecovirus reservoir, recombinant regions of a 68-genome sarbecovirus alignment were removed with three independent methods. Bayesian evolutionary rate and divergence date estimates were consistent for all three recombination-free alignments and robust to two different prior specifications based on HCoV-OC43 and MERS-CoV evolutionary rates. Divergence dates between SARS-CoV-2 and the bat sarbecovirus reservoir were estimated as 1948 (95% HPD: 1879-1999), 1969 (95% HPD: 1930-2000), and 1982 (95% HPD: 1948-2009). Despite intensified characterization of sarbecoviruses since SARS, the lineage giving rise to SARS-CoV-2 has been circulating unnoticed for decades in bats and been transmitted to other hosts such as pangolins. The occurrence of a third significant coronavirus emergence in 17 years together with the high prevalence and virus diversity in bats implies that these viruses are likely to cross species boundaries again.

In Brief: The Betacoronavirus SARS-CoV-2 is a member of the sarbecovirus subgenus which shows frequent recombination in its evolutionary history. We characterize the extent of this genetic exchange and identify non-recombining regions of the sarbecovirus genome using three independent methods to remove the effects of recombination. Using these non-recombining genome regions and prior information on coronavirus evolutionary rates, we obtain estimates from three approaches that the most likely divergence date of SARSCoV-2 from its most closely related available bat sequences ranges from 1948 to 1982.

Key Points: • RaTG13 is the closest available bat virus to SARS-CoV-2; a sub-lineage of these bat viruses is able to infect humans. Two sister lineages of the RaTG13/SARS-CoV-2 lineage infect Malayan pangolins.

• The sarbecoviruses show a pattern of deep recombination events, indicating that there are high levels of co-infection in horseshoe bats and that the viral pool can generate novel allele combinations and substantial genetic diversity; the sarbecoviruses are efficient ‘explorers’ of phenotype space.

• The SARS-CoV-2 lineage is not a recent recombinant, at least not involving any of the bat or pangolin viruses sampled to date.

• Non-recombinant regions of the sarbecoviruses can be identified, allowing for phylogenetic inference and dating to be performed. We constructed three such regions using different methods.

• We estimate that RaTG13 and SARS-CoV-2 diverged 40 to 70 years ago. There is a diverse unsampled reservoir of generalist viruses established in horseshoe bats.

• While an intermediate host responsible for the zoonotic event cannot be ruled out, the relevant evolution for spillover to humans very likely occurred in horseshoe bats.

Supplementary Section 3: SARS-CoV-2 synonymous codon usage patterns are not consistent with snake genome (contra Ji Wei et al. 2020); Fig. S4.]

Figure 1. Top: Breakpoints identified by 3SEQ shown by the percentage of sequences (out of 68) that support a particular breakpoint position. Note that breakpoints can be shared between sequences if they are descendants of the same recombination events. The pink, green, and orange bars show breakpoint-free regions (BFRs), with Region A (nt 13291-19628) showing two trimmed segments to yield Region A' (nt 13291-14932, 15405-17162, 18009-19628). Region B spans nucleotides 3625-9150, and region C spans 9261-11795. Concatenated region A'BC is non-recombining region 1 (NRR1). Open reading frames are shown above the breakpoint plot, with the variable loop region indicated in the S protein. Center: Similarity plot between SARSCoV-2 and several selected sequences including RaTG13 (black), SARS 2002-2003 (pink), and two pangolin sequences (orange). Shaded region corresponds to the S protein. Bottom: Maximum likelihood phylogenetic trees rooted on a 2007 virus sampled in Kenya (BtKy72; root truncated from images), shown for five breakpoint-free regions of the sarbecovirus alignment. Nucleotide positions for phylogenetic inference are 147-695, 962-1686 (first tree), 3625-9150 (second tree, also BFR B), 9261-11795 (third tree, also BFR C), 12443-19638 (fourth tree), and 23631-24633, 24795-25847, 27702-28843, 29574-30650 (fifth tree). Relevant bootstrap values are shown on branches, and gray-shaded regions show sequences that exhibit phylogenetic incongruence along the genome. SC China corresponds to provinces in southcentral China, specifically Yunnan, Guizhou, and Guangxi provinces. NE China corresponds to provinces in northeast China: Jilin, Shaanxi, Shanxi, Hebei, and Henan provinces.

Figure 2. Maximum likelihood trees of the sarbecoviruses using the two longest breakpoint-free regions (BFRs), rooted on the Kenya/Bulgaria lineage. Region **A** has been shortened to **A'** (5017nt) based on potential recombination signals within the region. Region **B** is 5525nt long. Sequences are color-coded by province according to the map. Five example sequences with incongruent phylogenetic positions in the two trees are indicated by dashed lines.

Figure 3. Phylogenetic relationships among SARS-CoV-2 and closely related sequences for sub-regions of the S protein. SARS-CoV-2 and RaTG13 are the most closely related (their most recent common ancestor node denoted by a green circle), except in the 220nt variable loop region of the C-terminal domain (bar graphs at bottom). In the variable loop region, RaTG13 diverges considerably with the tMRCA now outside that of SARS-CoV-2 and Pangolin Guangdong 2019 ancestor, suggesting that RaTG13 has acquired this region from a more divergent and undetected bat lineage. The genetic distances between SARS-CoV-2 and RaTG13 (bottom panel) demonstrate their relationship is consistent across all regions except for the variable loop. The genetic distances between SARS-CoV-2 and Pangolin Guangdong 2019 are consistent across all regions except the NTD.

CAO Yanan, LI Lin, FENG Zhimin, WAN Shengqing, HUANG Peide, SUN Xiaohui, WEN Fang, HUANG Xuanlin, NING Guang & WANG Weiqing
2020

Comparative genetic analysis of the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV/SARS-CoV-2) receptor ACE2 in different populations, (Correspondence)
in: Cell Discovery 6, article number 11 (2020).
<<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41421-020-0147-1>>

Fig. 1: The coding-region variants and eQTL variants for ACE2 in East Asian and other populations.
a Schematics of 32 coding variants in ACE2 identified in the ChinaMAP and 1KGP databases. Yellow stars indicate the nonsense variants; dots indicate the missense variants. The number of samples with hotspot variants was marked.
b The distribution of hotspot missense mutations of ACE2 in different populations. The colors indicate different populations.
c The distribution and the allele frequencies of representative eQTL variants for ACE2 in different populations. Pie charts depict the allele frequencies of an intron variant of ACE2 (rs4646127) in the world. Orange color denotes the frequency of alteration allele, and blue color denotes the reference allele. The allele frequencies of 15 eQTLs for ACE2 gene are shown in tables. The color gradient from blue to red indicates the increasing of allele frequencies. The allele frequencies of INDEL variant rs200781818 were annotated by the gnomAD database. EAS, East Asian; EUR, European; AFR, African; SAS, South Asian; AMR, Ad Mixed American.

CHAN Jasper Fuk-Woo, KOK Kin-Hang, ZHU Zheng, CHU Hin, TO Kelvin Kai-Wang, YUAN Shuofeng & YUEN Kwok-Yung

©2020 [2 pdf]

Genomic characterization of the 2019 novel human-pathogenic coronavirus isolated from a patient with atypical pneumonia after visiting Wuhan,
in: Emerging Microbes & Infections 9(1): 221-236, 7 figs., 2 tables,
supplementary appendix: 8p., figs. S1-S2, table S1.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/22221751.2020.1719902>

[Abstract: A mysterious outbreak of atypical pneumonia in late 2019 was traced to a seafood wholesale market in Wuhan of China. Within a few weeks, a novel coronavirus tentatively named as 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) was announced by the World Health Organization. We performed bioinformatics analysis on a virus genome from a patient with 2019-nCoV infection and compared it with other related coronavirus genomes. Overall, the genome

of 2019-nCoV has 89% nucleotide identity with bat SARS-like-CoVZXC21 and 82% with that of human SARS-CoV. The phylogenetic trees of their orf1a/b, Spike, Envelope, Membrane and Nucleoprotein also clustered closely with those of the bat, civet and human SARS coronaviruses. However, the external subdomain of Spike's receptor binding domain of 2019-nCoV shares only 40% amino acid identity with other SARS-related coronaviruses. Remarkably, its orf3b encodes a completely novel short protein. Furthermore, its new orf8 likely encodes a secreted protein with an alpha-helix, following with a beta-sheet(s) containing six strands. Learning from the roles of civet in SARS and camel in MERS, hunting for the animal source of 2019-nCoV and its more ancestral virus would be important for understanding the origin and evolution of this novel lineage B *betacoronavirus*. These findings provide the basis for starting further studies on the pathogenesis, and optimizing the design of diagnostic, antiviral and vaccination strategies for this emerging infection. Keywords: Coronavirus, Wuhan, SARS, emerging, genome, respiratory, virus, bioinformatics.]

CHÉN Jiāyuán 陳嘉源, SHĪ Jīnsōng 施勁松, QIŪ Dòng'ān 丘棟安, LIÚ Chàng 劉暢, Lǐ Xīn 李鑫, ZHÀO Qiáng 趙強, RUǎN Jíshòu 阮吉壽, GĀO Shān 高山

2019

2019 *xīnxíng guānzhàng bìngdú jīyīnzǔ de shēngwù xìnxī xué fēnxī* 2019 新型冠狀病毒基因組的生物信息學分析 – *Bioinformatics analysis of the 2019 novel coronavirus genome*,

in: shengwuxinxue 生物信息學 • Chinese Journal of Bioinformatics 1-10. (2020-01-21). Online First Publishing Date: 2020-01-21 09:34:23.

[Abstract: In 2019, a human coronavirus has caused the pneumonia outbreak in Wuhan (a city of China). This virus was predicted as a new coronavirus, named the 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV), as it caused clinical symptoms different from Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) during the 2003 outbreak. Currently, most of the researchers simply use the complete genome or specific structural gene sequences to investigate coronavirus (e.g. phylogenetic analysis) without considering the functions of the products from coronavirus genes. To overcome this shortcoming, we proposed the joint analysis of the molecular function and phylogeny, and applied it in our previous study of genomes of Betacoronavirus subgroup B (BB coronavirus). In that study, we identified a 22-bp complemented palindrome from a highly conserved Coding Sequence (CDS). Both the 22-bp complemented palindrome (named Nankai complemented palindrome) and the CDS (named Nankai CDS), evolutionary conserved in BB coronavirus genomes, were identified as genomic features associated to the molecular functions of BB coronavirus. In the present study, we used these two genomic features to trace the origin of 2019-nCoV (GenBank:MN908947) and conduct a preliminary study of the mechanisms in the cross-species infection and host adaptation of BB coronavirus. Our analytical results show that 2019-nCoV with large differences from the SARS coronavirus, may originate from BB coronavirus in Chinese horseshoe bats (*Rhinolophus sinicus*). The most important finding is that the alternative translation of Nankai CDS can produce more than 17 putative proteins, which may be responsible for the host adaptation. The genotyping of 13 viruses using the 17 putative proteins revealed the high mutation rate and diversity of BB coronavirus. Our study, for the first time, aimed to explain the reason for the high host adaptability of the multi-host BB coronavirus at the molecular level using large amounts of genomic data. The findings in the present study laid foundations for the rapid detection, genotyping, vaccine development and drug design of, but not limited to BB coronavirus.

Keywords: Coronavirus 冠狀病毒; SARS; Alternative translation 可變翻譯; 2019-nCoV; Cross-species infection 跨物種傳播.

2019年12月,中國武漢報導了冠狀病毒引起的肺炎,其臨床症狀與2003年爆發的嚴重急性呼吸綜合徵(Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome,SARS)不同,因此推斷該病毒可能是冠狀病毒的一個新變種。不同於簡單使用全基因組序列的其它研究,我們於2018年在國際上首次提出分子功能與進化分析相結合的研究思想,並應用於Beta冠狀病毒B亞群(BB冠狀病毒)基因組的研究。在這一思想指導下,本研究使用BB冠狀病毒基因組中的一個互補回文序列(命名為Nankai complemented palindrome)與其所在的編碼區(命名為Nankai CDS)對新發佈的2019新型冠狀病毒基因組(GenBank:MN908947)進行分析以期準確溯源,並對BB冠狀病毒的跨物種傳播和宿主適應性進行初步研究。溯源分析的結果支持2019新型冠狀病毒源自中華菊頭蝠,但與SARS冠狀病毒差異較大,這一結果與兩者臨床症狀差異一致。本研究的最重要發現是BB冠狀病毒存在大量的可變翻譯,從分子水平揭示了BB冠狀病毒變異快、多樣性高的特點。從BB冠狀病毒可變翻譯中獲取的信息可應用於(但不限於)其快速檢測、基因分型、疫苗開發以及藥物設計。另外,我們推斷BB冠狀病毒可能通過可變翻譯以適應不同宿主。基於大量基因組數據的實證分析,本研究在國際上首次從分子水平嘗試解釋BB冠狀病毒變異快、宿主多且具有較強宿主適應性的原因。]

The spike glycoprotein of the new coronavirus 2019-nCoV contains a furin-like cleavage site absent in CoV of the same clade,

in: Antiviral Research 76, 104742. [5p., 2 figs., 1 table; Appendix A.

Supplementary data: XML file (282B) ([link defunct](#))

<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.antiviral.2020.104742>>

Highlights: • The genomic sequence of 2019-nCoV indicates that the virus clusters with beta-coronaviruses of lineage b.

• 2019-nCoV S-protein sequence has a specific furin-like cleavage site absent in lineage b CoV including SARS-CoV sequences.

• The furin-like cleavage site in the S-protein of 2019-nCoV may have implications for the viral life cycle and pathogenicity.

• Campaigns to develop anti-2019-nCoV therapeutics should include the evaluation of furin inhibitors.

Abstract: In 2019, a new coronavirus (2019-nCoV) infecting Humans has emerged in Wuhan, China. Its genome has been sequenced and the genomic information promptly released. Despite a high similarity with the genome sequence of SARS-CoV and SARS-like CoVs, we identified a peculiar furin-like cleavage site in the Spike protein of the 2019-nCoV, lacking in the other SARS-like CoVs. In this article, we discuss the possible functional consequences of this cleavage site in the viral cycle, pathogenicity and its potential implication in the development of antivirals.

Keywords: 2019-nCoV; SARS-CoV; Spike protein; Maturation protease; Furin; Antivirals.]

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the human 2019-nCoV S-protein with a focus on the putative maturation sites. The domains were previously characterized in SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV: Signal peptide (SP), N-terminal domain (NTD), receptor-binding domain (RBD), fusion peptide (FP), internal fusion peptide (IFP), heptad repeat 1/2 (HR1/2), and the transmembrane domain (TM). The SP, S1↓S2 and S2' cleavage sites are indicated by arrows. The sequence of different CoV S1/S2 and S2' cleavage sites were aligned using Multalin webserver (<http://multalin.toulouse.inra.fr/multalin/>) with manual adjustments and the figure prepared using ESPript 3 (<http://esprict.ibcp.fr/ESPript/ESPript/>) presenting the secondary structure of SARS-CoV S-protein at the bottom of the alignment (PDB 5X58) (Yuan et al., 2017). Insertion of furin like cleavage site is surrounded by a black frame. Red asterisks indicate the presence of a canonical furin-like cleavage motif at the S1/S2 site. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

FOLEY Brian Thomas
2020 [png]

Phylogenies of the Receptor-Binding Domain.
February 2020; Project: 2019-nCoV natural history.
<<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339390797>>

GORBALENYA Alexander E., BAKER Susan C., BARIC Ralph S., DE GROOT Raoul J., DROSTEN Christian, GULYAEVA Anastasia A., HAAGMANS Bart L., LAUBER Chris, LEONTOVICH Andrey M, NEUMAN Benjamin W., PENZAR Dmitry, PERLMAN Stanley, POON Leo L.M., SAMBORSKIY Dmitry, SIDOROV Igor A., SOLA Isabel, ZIEBUHR John
°2020 [pdf]

Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus – The species and its viruses, a statement of the Coronavirus Study Group,
in: bioRxiv 2020.02.07.937862.
<<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.07.937862>>

[Abstract: The present outbreak of lower respiratory tract infections, including respiratory distress syndrome, is the third spillover, in only two decades, of an animal coronavirus to humans resulting in a major epidemic. Here, the Coronavirus Study Group (CSG) of the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses, which is responsible for developing the official classification of viruses and taxa naming (taxonomy) of the Coronaviridae family, assessed the novelty of the human pathogen tentatively named 2019-nCoV. Based on phylogeny, taxonomy and established practice, the CSG formally recognizes this virus as a sister to severe acute respiratory syndrome coronaviruses (SARS-CoVs) of the species *Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus* and designates it as severe acute respiratory syndrome corona-

virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). To facilitate communication, the CSG further proposes to use the following naming convention for individual isolates: SARS-CoV-2/Isolate/Host/Date/Location. The spectrum of clinical manifestations associated with SARS-CoV-2 infections in humans remains to be determined. The independent zoonotic transmission of SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 highlights the need for studying the entire (virus) species to complement research focused on individual pathogenic viruses of immediate significance. This research will improve our understanding of virus-host interactions in an ever-changing environment and enhance our preparedness for future outbreaks.]

Ji Wei, WANG Wei, ZHAO Xiaofang, ZAI Junjie, LI Xingguang

°2020 [pdf]

Cross-species transmission of the newly identified coronavirus 2019-nCoV,
in: *Journal of Medical Virology* 92(4): 433-440, 4 figs., 1 table.

[jmv25682-sup-0001-SuppTableS1.xlsx] <<https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.25682>>

[Abstract: The current outbreak of viral pneumonia in the city of Wuhan, China, was caused by a novel coronavirus designated 2019-nCoV by the World Health Organization, as determined by sequencing the viral RNA genome. Many initial patients were exposed to wildlife animals at the Huanan seafood wholesale market, where poultry, snake, bats, and other farm animals were also sold. To investigate possible virus reservoir, we have carried out comprehensive sequence analysis and comparison in conjunction with relative synonymous codon usage (RSCU) bias among different animal species based on the 2019-nCoV sequence. Results obtained from our analyses suggest that the 2019-nCoV may appear to be a recombinant virus between the bat coronavirus and an origin-unknown coronavirus. The recombination may [have] occurred within the viral spike glycoprotein, which recognizes a cell surface receptor. Additionally, our findings suggest that 2019-nCoV has most similar genetic information with bat coronavirus [recte: coronavirus] and most similar codon usage bias with snake. Taken together, our results suggest that homologous recombination may occur and contribute to the 2019-nCoV cross-species transmission.

Research Highlights: • Taken together, our results suggest that homologous recombination may occur and contribute to the 2019-nCoV cross-species transmission.]

Critique:

- ANDERSEN Kristian 2020.
- ROBERTSON David L. 2020.
- BONI Maciej F. *et al.* 2020, esp. Supplementary Section 3, found no evidence for Ji Wei *et al.* 2020's hypothesis for snakes as intermediate hosts of SARS-CoV-2.

LI Hua, WU Canrong, YANG Yueying, LIU Yang, ZHANG Peng, WANG Yali, WANG Qiqi, XU Yang, LI Mingxue, ZHENG Mengzhu, CHEN Lixia

°2020 [pdf]

Furin, a potential therapeutic target for COVID-19,
in: *ChinaXiv*, 2020-02-23.

[34p., 8 figs., 4 tables, 28+3 refs., supplementary information: figs. S1-S5.]

<<http://chinaxiv.org/abs/202002.00062>>

[Abstract: A novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) infectious disease has broken out in Wuhan, Hubei Province since December 2019, and spread rapidly from Wuhan to other areas, which has been listed as an international concerning public health emergency. We compared the Spike proteins from four sources, SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV and Bat-CoVRaTG13, and found that the SARS-CoV-2 virus sequence had redundant PRRA sequences. Through a series of analyses, we propose the reason why SARS-CoV-2 is more infectious than other coronaviruses. And through structure based virtual ligand screening, we found potential furin inhibitors, which might be used in the treatment of new coronary pneumonia.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2; Spike proteins; Furin; Inhibitors; Virtual screening. –

Table 2. *Potential furin inhibitors from ZINC drug database.*

Table 3. *Potential furin inhibitors from in-house natural product database.*]

Figure 1. Evolutionary relationships of taxa. The evolutionary history was inferred using the Neighbor-Joining method. The bootstrap consensus tree inferred from 500 replicates is taken to represent the evolutionary history of the taxa analyzed. Branches corresponding to partitions reproduced in less than 50% bootstrap replicates are collapsed. The evolutionary distances were computed using the Poisson correction method and in the units of the number of amino acid substitutions per site. The analysis involved 155 amino acid sequences. All positions containing gaps and missing data were eliminated. There are a total of 711 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA7. Those painted in red mean containing cleavage site in sequences and those painted in yellow mean no cleavage site in sequences.

LIU Chuang, YANG Yang, GAO Yuanzhu, SHEN Chenguang, JU Bin, LIU Congcong, TANG Xian, WEI Jinli, MA Xiaomin, LIU Weilong, XU Shuman, LIU Yingxia, YUAN Jing, WU Jing, LIU Zheng, ZHANG Zheng, WANG Peiyi, LIU Lei

©2020 [pdf]

Viral Architecture of SARS-CoV-2 with Post-Fusion Spike Revealed by Cryo-EM,

in: bioRxiv Posted March 05, 2020. [3 figs., Figure S1, Table S1.]

<<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.02.972927>>

[Abstract: Since December 2019, the outbreak of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) spread from Wuhan, China to the world, it has caused more than 87,000 diagnosed cases and more than 3,000 deaths globally. To fight against COVID-19, we carried out research for the near native SARS-CoV-2 and report here our preliminary results obtained. The pathogen of the COVID-19, the native SARS-CoV-2, was isolated, amplified and purified in a BSL-3 laboratory. The whole viral architecture of SARS-CoV-2 was examined by transmission electron microscopy (both negative staining and cryo-EM). We observed that the virion particles are roughly spherical or moderately pleiomorphic. Spikes have nail-like shape towards outside with a long body embedded in the envelope. The morphology of virion observed in our result indicates that the S protein of SARS-CoV-2 is in post-fusion state, with S1 disassociated. This state revealed by cryo-EM [Cryogenic electron microscopy] first time could provide an important information for the identification and relevant clinical research of this new coronavirus.3q

Figure 2. Negative stain EM results of SARS-CoV-2. (A). Image of negative stained SARS-CoV-2. Nail-like spikes can be clearly seen. (B). Enlarged view of virion boxed in (A). (C) Zoom-in view of a spike boxed in (B). The shape is depicted by red dot line. Length, the diameter of stem and spike's head are 23nm, 4nm and 7nm, respectively. (D). Three-dimensional surface of post-fusion state S2 protein (EMDB code: 9597) [15]. (E). Projection of post-fusion state S2 protein [15].]

Figure 3. Cryo-EM results of SARS-CoV-2. (A) and (B). Cryo-EM images of SARSCoV-2. (C). Zoom-in view of the virion showed in (A). Envelope and nucleocapsid are indicated by green and blue respectively, remarkable spikes are indicated by red triangles. (D). Zoom-in views of the two virions showed in (B), remarkable spikes are indicated by red triangles. (E). Zoom-in view of the spike indicated by yellow triangle in (C). The shape is depicted by yellow dot lines. (F). Zoom-in view of the spike indicated by yellow triangle in (D). The shape is depicted by yellow dot lines.

LIU Shan-Lu & SAIF Linda
2020

Emerging Viruses without Borders: The Wuhan Coronavirus, (Editorial)
in: *Viruses* 2020, 12(2), no. 130. (Special Issue Pathogenesis of Human
and Animal Coronaviruses) <<https://doi.org/10.3390/v12020130>>

[Abstract The recently emerged coronavirus in Wuhan, China has claimed at least six lives as of January 22 and infected hundreds if not thousands of individuals. The situation has drawn international attention, including from the virology community. We applaud the rapid release to the public of the genome sequence of the new virus by Chinese virologists, but we also believe that increased transparency on disease reporting and data sharing with international colleagues are crucial for curbing the spread of this newly emerging virus to other parts of the world.]

LU Roujian, ZHAO Xiang, LI Juan, Niu Peihua, YANG Bo, WU Honglong, WANG Wenling, SONG Hao, HUANG Baoying, ZHU Na, BI Yuhai, MA Xuejun, ZHAN Faxian, WANG Liang, HU Tao, ZHOU Hong, HU Zhenhong, ZHOU Weimin, ZHAO Li, CHEN Jing, MENG Yao, WANG Ji, LIN Yang, YUAN Jianying, XIE Zhihao, MA Jinmin, LIU William J., WANG Dayan, XU Wenbo, HOLMES Edward C., GAO George F., WU Guizhen, CHEN Weijun, SHI Weifeng, TAN Wenjie
©2020 [pdf]

Genomic characterisation and epidemiology of 2019 novel coronavirus: implications for virus origins and receptor binding,

in: *The Lancet*, January 30, 2020. [10p.; 5 figs.; 1 table.]

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30251-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30251-8)

[Summary: Background: In late December, 2019, patients presenting with viral pneumonia due to an unidentified microbial agent were reported in Wuhan, China. A novel coronavirus was subsequently identified as the causative pathogen, provisionally named 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). As of Jan 26, 2020, more than 2000 cases of 2019-nCoV infection have been confirmed, most of which involved people living in or visiting Wuhan, and human-to-human transmission has been confirmed.

Methods: We did next-generation sequencing of samples from bronchoalveolar lavage fluid and cultured isolates from nine inpatients, eight of whom had visited the Huanan seafood market in Wuhan. Complete and partial 2019-nCoV genome sequences were obtained from these individuals. Viral contigs were connected using Sanger sequencing to obtain the full-length genomes, with the terminal regions determined by rapid amplification of cDNA ends. Phylogenetic analysis of these 2019-nCoV genomes and those of other coronaviruses was used to determine the evolutionary history of the virus and help infer its likely origin. Homology modelling was done to explore the likely receptor-binding properties of the virus.

Findings: The ten genome sequences of 2019-nCoV obtained from the nine patients were extremely similar, exhibiting more than 99.98% sequence identity. Notably, 2019-nCoV was closely related (with 88% identity) to two bat-derived severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS)-like coronaviruses, bat-SL-CoVZC45 and bat-SL-CoVZXC21, collected in 2018 in Zhoushan, eastern China, but were more distant from SARS-CoV (about 79%) and MERS-CoV (about 50%). Phylogenetic analysis revealed that 2019-nCoV fell within the subgenus Sarbecovirus of the genus Betacoronavirus, with a relatively long branch length to its closest relatives bat-SL-CoVZC45 and bat-SL-CoVZXC21, and was genetically distinct from SARS-CoV. Notably, homology modelling revealed that 2019-nCoV had a similar receptor-binding domain structure to that of SARS-CoV, despite amino acid variation at some key residues.

Interpretation: 2019-nCoV is sufficiently divergent from SARS-CoV to be considered a new human-infecting betacoronavirus. ~~Although our phylogenetic analysis suggests that bats might be the original host of this virus, an animal sold at the seafood market in Wuhan might represent an intermediate host facilitating the emergence of the virus in humans.~~ Importantly, structural analysis suggests that 2019-nCoV might be able to bind to the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 receptor in humans. The future evolution, adaptation, and spread of this virus warrant urgent investigation.

Funding: National Key Research and Development Program of China, National Major Project for Control and Prevention of Infectious Disease in China, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Shandong First Medical University. –

• Research in context: Evidence before this study: The causal agent of an outbreak of severe pneumonia in Wuhan, China, is a novel coronavirus, provisionally named 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). The first cases were reported in December, 2019.

Added value of this study: We have described the genomic characteristics of 2019-nCoV and similarities and differences to other coronaviruses, including the virus that caused the severe acute respiratory syndrome epidemic of 2002–03. Genome sequences of 2019-nCoV sampled from nine patients who were among the early cases of this severe infection are almost genetically identical, which suggests very recent emergence of this virus in humans and that the outbreak was detected relatively rapidly. 2019-nCoV is most closely related to other betacoronaviruses of bat origin, indicating that these animals are the likely reservoir hosts for this emerging viral pathogen.

Implications of all the available evidence: By documenting the presence of 2019-nCoV in a sample of patients, our study extends previous evidence that this virus has led to the novel pneumonia that has caused severe disease in Wuhan and other geographical localities. Currently available data suggest that 2019-nCoV infected the human population from a bat reservoir, although it remains unclear if a currently unknown animal species acted as an intermediate host between bats and humans.]

Figure 3 Phylogenetic analysis of full-length genomes of 2019-nCoV and representative viruses of the genus Betacoronavirus

2019-nCoV=2019 novel coronavirus. MERS-CoV=Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus. SARS-CoV=severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus.

<https://marlin-prod.literatumonline.com/cms/attachment/2a04241c-fd41-44b6-bb67-336e53f2e4f5/gr3.jpg>

Figure 5 Phylogenetic analysis and homology modelling of the receptor-binding domain of the 2019-nCoV, SARS-CoV, and MERS-CoV

(A) Phylogenetic analysis of the receptor-binding domain from various betacoronaviruses. The star highlights 2019-nCoV and the question marks means that the receptor used by the viruses remains unknown. Structural comparison of the receptor-binding domain of SARS-CoV (B), 2019-nCoV (C), and MERS-CoV (D) binding to their own receptors. Core subdomains are magenta, and the external subdomains of SARS-CoV, 2019-nCoV, and MERS CoV are orange, dark blue, and green, respectively. Variable residues between SARS-CoV and 2019-nCoV in the receptor-binding site are highlighted as sticks. CoV= coronavirus. 2019-nCoV=2019 novel coronavirus. SARS-CoV=severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus. MERS= Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus.

<https://marlin-prod.literatumonline.com/cms/attachment/54253add-72fa-4650-9520-1b6457bec4eb/gr5.jpg>

PARASKEVIS Dimitrios, KOSTAKI Evangelia G., MAGIORKINIS Gkikas, PANAYIOTAKOPOULOS George, TSIODRAS Sotirios

*2020a

Full-genome evolutionary analysis of the novel corona virus (2019-nCoV) rejects the hypothesis of emergence as a result of a recent recombination event,
in: bioRxiv, January 27, 2020.

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.01.26.920249>

[Abstract. Background: A novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) associated with human to human transmission and severe human infection has been recently reported from the city of Wuhan in China. Our objectives were to characterize the genetic relationships of the 2019-nCoV and to search for putative recombination within the subgenus of sarbecovirus.

Methods: Putative recombination was investigated by RDP4 and Simplot v3.5.1 and discordant phylogenetic clustering in individual genomic fragments was confirmed by phylogenetic analysis using maximum likelihood and Bayesian methods.

Results: Our analysis suggests that the 2019-nCoV although closely related to BatCoV RaTG13 sequence throughout the genome (sequence similarity 96.3%), shows discordant clustering with the Bat-SARS-like coronavirus sequences. Specifically, in the 5'-part spanning the first 11,498

nucleotides and the last 3'-part spanning 24,341-30,696 positions, 2019-nCoV and RaTG13 formed a single cluster with Bat-SARS-like coronavirus sequences, whereas in the middle region spanning the 3'-end of ORF1a, the ORF1b and almost half of the spike regions, 2019-nCoV and RaTG13 grouped in a separate distant lineage within the sarbecovirus branch.

Conclusions: The levels of genetic similarity between the 2019-nCoV and RaTG13 suggest that the latter does not provide the exact variant that caused the outbreak in humans, but the hypothesis that 2019-nCoV has originated from bats is very likely. We show evidence that the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) is not-mosaic consisting in almost half of its genome of a distinct lineage within the betacoronavirus. These genomic features and their potential association with virus characteristics and virulence in humans need further attention.]

*2020b [pdf]

Full-genome evolutionary analysis of the novel corona virus (2019-nCoV) rejects the hypothesis of emergence as a result of a recent recombination event,

in: *Infection, Genetics and Evolution* 79, April 2020, 104212.

[4p.; 2 figs.] <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcegid.2020.104212>>

[Highlights: • Full-genomic sequence analysis of the novel corona virus (2019-nCoV).

- Phylogenetic and recombination analysis within the subgenus of sarbecovirus.
- Evidence that the 2019-nCoV shows discordant clustering with the Bat_SARS-like coronavirus sequences.
- Evidence that the hypothesis of emergence of 2019-nCoV as a result of a recent recombination event is rejected.

Abstract: Background: A novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) associated with human to human transmission and severe human infection has been recently reported from the city of Wuhan in China. Our objectives were to characterize the genetic relationships of the 2019-nCoV and to search for putative recombination within the subgenus of sarbecovirus.

Methods: Putative recombination was investigated by RDP4 and Simplot v3.5.1 and discordant phylogenetic clustering in individual genomic fragments was confirmed by phylogenetic analysis using maximum likelihood and Bayesian methods.

Results: Our analysis suggests that the 2019-nCoV although closely related to BatCoV RaTG13 sequence throughout the genome (sequence similarity 96.3%), shows discordant clustering with the Bat_SARS-like coronavirus sequences. Specifically, in the 5'-part spanning the first 11,498 nucleotides and the last 3'-part spanning 24,341–30,696 positions, 2019-nCoV and RaTG13 formed a single cluster with Bat_SARS-like coronavirus sequences, whereas in the middle region spanning the 3'-end of ORF1a, the ORF1b and almost half of the spike regions, 2019-nCoV and RaTG13 grouped in a separate distant lineage within the sarbecovirus branch.

Conclusions: The levels of genetic similarity between the 2019-nCoV and RaTG13 suggest that the latter does not provide the exact variant that caused the outbreak in humans, but the hypothesis that 2019-nCoV has originated from bats is very likely. We show evidence that the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) is not-mosaic consisting in almost half of its genome of a distinct lineage within the betacoronavirus. These genomic features and their potential association with virus characteristics and virulence in humans need further attention.

Keywords: Novel coronavirus; Genomic sequence analysis; Phylogenetic analysis; Recombination; Origin; Molecular epidemiology. –

Conclusions: “(...) Our study rejects the hypothesis of emergence as a result of a recent recombination event. Notably, the new coronavirus provides a new lineage for almost half of its genome, with no close genetic relationships to other viruses within the subgenus of sarbecovirus. This genomic part comprises half of the spike region encoding a multifunctional protein responsible also for virus entry into host cells (Babcock et al., 2004; Li et al., 2005b). The unique genetic features of 2019-nCoV and their potential association with virus characteristics and virulence in humans remain to be elucidated.”]

Fig. 1. A. Genomic organization of the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) according to the positions in the edited alignment. B. Simplot of 2019-nCoV (NC_045512_Wuhan_Hu-1) against sequences within the subgenus sarbecovirus. Different colours correspond to the nucleotide similarity between the 2019-nCoV and different groups. The regions with discordant phylogenetic clustering of the 2019-nCoV with Bats_SARS-like sequences are shown in different colours. C. Maximum likelihood (ML) phylogenetic trees inferred in different genomic regions as indicated by the Simplot analysis. The genomic regions are shown in numbers at the top or at the left of the trees. The 2019-nCoV sequence is shown in red and stars indicate important nodes received 100% bootstrap and 1 posterior probability support. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Neighbor joining distance tree of the BLAST search results of the 2019-nCoV (NC_045512_Wuhan_Hu_1) sequence in the genomic region 10,901–22,830 of the alignment.

ROBERTSON David L.

2020

nCoV's relationship to bat coronaviruses & recombination signals (no snakes) – no evidence the 2019-nCoV lineage is recombinant.

Virological.org. <<http://virological.org/t/331>>

[Critical assessment of Ji Wei *et al.* 2020.

“With Xiaowei Jiang at XJTU we’ve carried out a preliminary evolutionary analysis to characterise the evolutionary origins of the Wuhan virus, nCoV. Focus of our analysis is on the Wuhan-Hu-1 virus (accession no. MN908947, released on GenBank by Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center and School of Public Health, Fudan University, Shanghai, China) as all nCoV cluster together so will share the same evolutionary ancestry. It’s clear from phylogenetic analysis the new human virus is most closely related to bat coronaviruses in the Betacoronaviruses genera. (...)]

TAN Wenjie, ZHAO Xiang, MA Xuejun, WANG Wenling, NIU Peihua, XU Wenbo, GAO George F., WU Guizhen

©2020 [pdf]

A Novel Coronavirus Genome Identified in a Cluster of Pneumonia Cases – Wuhan, China 2019–2020,

in: China CDC Weekly, 2020, 2(4): 61-62.
<http://weekly.chinacdc.cn/en/article/id/a3907201-f64f-4154-a19e-4253b453d10c>

FIGURE 1. Phylogenetic relationships between the genomes of the new types of *Betacoronavirus* and other *Orthocoronavirinae* genomes. The viruses in the subfamily *Orthocoronavirinae* were classified into four genera (prototype or Refseq strains shown): *Alphacoronavirus* (purple), *Betacoronavirus* (orange), *Gammacoronavirus* (green), and *Deltacoronavirus* (blue). Classic subgroup clusters for the *Betacoronavirus* were labelled 2a–2d. The tree was based on complete genomes shown above using the maximum likelihood method under the GTR + I + Γ model of nucleotide substitution as implemented in PhyML. The new types of *Betacoronavirus*, labelled with red stars, were placed into the lineage of *Betacoronavirus* 2b, which contain the following: avian infectious bronchitis virus (AIBV), Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), mouse hepatitis virus (MHV), porcine enteric diarrhea virus (PEDV), severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV), SARS-related coronavirus (SARSr-CoV), and Human coronavirus (HCoV).

<http://weekly.chinacdc.cn/fileCCDCW/journal/article/ccdcw/2020/4/PIC/Wuhan-1.jpg>

TANG Xiaolu, WU Changcheng, LI Xiang, SONG Yuhe, YAO Xinmin, WU Xinkai, DUAN Yuange, ZHANG Hong, WANG Yirong, QIAN Zhaohui, CUI Jie, LU Jian
 °2020 [pdf]

On the origin and continuing evolution of SARS-CoV-2,
 in: National Science Review, nwa036, accepted ms.

[24p., 7 figs., 2 tables; Supplementary data: nwa036_Supplemental_File - xlsx file]
<https://doi.org/10.1093/nsr/nwa036>

[Abstract: The SARS-CoV-2 epidemic started in late December 2019 in Wuhan, China, and has since impacted a large portion of China and raised major global concern. Herein, we investigated the extent of molecular divergence between SARS-CoV-2 and other related coronaviruses. Although we found only 4% variability in genomic nucleotides between SARS-CoV-2 and a bat SARS-related coronavirus (SARSr-CoV; RaTG13), the difference at neutral sites was 17%, suggesting the divergence between the two viruses is much larger than previously estimated. Our results suggest that the development of new variations in functional sites in the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the spike seen in SARS-CoV-2 and viruses from pangolin SARSr-CoVs are likely caused by mutations and natural selection besides recombination. Population genetic analyses of 103 SARS-CoV-2 genomes indicated that these viruses evolved into two major types (designated L and S), that are well defined by two different SNPs that show nearly complete linkage across the viral strains sequenced to date. Although the L type (~70%) is more prevalent than the S type (~30%), the S type was found to be the ancestral version. Whereas the L type was more prevalent in the early stages of the outbreak in Wuhan, the frequency of the L type decreased after early January 2020. Human intervention may have placed more severe selective pressure on the L type, which might be more aggressive and spread more quickly. On the other hand, the S type, which is evolutionarily older and less aggressive, might have increased in relative frequency due to relatively weaker selective pressure. These findings strongly support an urgent need for further immediate, comprehensive studies that combine genomic

already mutated at least once, in: CNBC Published Wed, Mar 4 2020 7:35 AM EST, Updated Wed, Mar 4 2020 8:53 AM EST.

<https://www.cnbc.com/2020/03/04/coronavirus-chinese-scientists-identify-two-types-covid-19.html>

[Key Points: • The more aggressive type of virus was found to be prevalent in the early stages of the outbreak in Wuhan — the Chinese city where COVID-19 was first detected late last year. • But the frequency of this type of virus has since decreased from early January, the scientists said. • Researchers cautioned that data examined in the study was still “very limited.”]

public peer review:

• BEDFORD Trevor, twitter @trvr, March 7, 2020: There is continued interest in “L” vs “S” strains of #SARSCoV2 proposed in the manuscript

<https://academic.oup.com/nsr/advance-article/doi/10.1093/nsr/nwaa036/5775463>.

Please consider this thread to be a public peer review of this work. 1/8

We've recorded 145 different single amino acid mutations among sequenced viruses in the #COVID19 pandemic. This manuscript focuses on a particular change from leucine (“L”) to serine (“S”) at site 84 in the ORF-8 gene of #SARSCoV2. 2/8

This mutation appears to have happened very early on in the outbreak while the virus was still in Wuhan, China. Viruses with “L” and viruses with “S” have spread from Wuhan to the rest of the world. Visible at https://nextstrain.org/ncov?c=gt-ORF8_84&r=country. 3/8

Generally, the expectation among virologists is that a random single amino acid change will have little impact on virus behavior. My “null” model would be that this mutation just happened to occur on an early branch on the tree and any “impact” is due solely to epidemiology. 4/8

We had a similar story with Ebola virus in West Africa where a possibly impactful mutation occurred, but distinguishing between virological and epidemiological effects was hugely difficult. <https://bedford.io/papers/bedford-ebola-gp82-adaptation/> 5/8

Any differences in apparent severity between these two genetic variants are most likely due to sampling of market-associated severe cases in Wuhan and missing the bulk of mild cases in this setting. 6/8

That said, we will continue to monitor spread of these two variants to look to see how frequencies behave over time and to look for possible differences in clinical outcomes, though at this point we don't see one variant outcompeting the other. 7/8

Frequencies (coloured by Genotype at ORF8 pos 84)

In summary, I don't think the strong conclusions of the manuscript are warranted. We will monitor these two genetic variants, but I see no reason to conclude they have important functional significance at this point. 8/8

THAO Tran Thi Nhu, LABROUSSAA Fabien, EBERT Nadine, V'KOVSKI Philip, STALDER Hanspeter, PORTMANN Jasmine, KELLY Jenna, STEINER Silvio, HOLWERDA Melle, KRATZEL Annika, GULTOM Mitra, LALOLI Laura, HÜSSER Linda, WIDER Manon, PFAENDER Stephanie, HIRT Dagny, CIPPÀ Valentina, CRESPO-POMAR Silvia, SCHRÖDER Simon, MUTH Doreen, NIEMEYER Daniela, MÜLLER Marcel A., DROSTEN Christian, DIJKMAN Ronald, JORES Joerg, THIEL Volker

°2020 [pdf]

Rapid reconstruction of SARS-CoV-2 using a synthetic genomics platform,

in: bioRxiv, February 21, 2020. [29p., 2 figs., table 1, 22 refs., extended data figs. 1-2.] <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.21.959817>

[Abstract: Reverse genetics has been an indispensable tool revolutionising our insights into viral pathogenesis and vaccine development. Large RNA virus genomes, such as from Coronaviruses, are cumbersome to clone and to manipulate in *E. coli* hosts due to size and occasional instability¹⁻³. Therefore, an alternative rapid and robust reverse genetics platform for RNA viruses would benefit the research community. Here we show the full functionality of a yeast-based synthetic genomics platform for the genetic reconstruction of diverse RNA viruses, including

members of the *Coronaviridae*, *Flaviviridae* and *Paramyxoviridae* families. Viral subgenomic fragments were generated using viral isolates, cloned viral DNA, clinical samples, or synthetic DNA, and reassembled in one step in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* using transformation associated recombination (TAR) cloning to maintain the genome as a yeast artificial chromosome (YAC). T7-RNA polymerase has been used to generate infectious RNA, which was then used to rescue viable virus. Based on this platform we have been able to engineer and resurrect chemically-synthesized clones of the recent epidemic SARS-CoV-2⁴ in only a week after receipt of the synthetic DNA fragments. The technical advance we describe here allows to rapidly responding to emerging viruses as it enables the generation and functional characterization of evolving RNA virus variants – in real-time – during an outbreak.]

WRAPP Daniel, WANG Nianshuang, CORBETT Kizzmekia S., GOLDSMITH Jory A., HSIEH Ching-Lin, ABIONA Olubukola, GRAHAM Barney S., MCLELLAN Jason S.

°2020 [2 pdf, 2 mov]

Cryo-EM structure of the 2019-nCoV spike in the prefusion conformation,

in: Science 19 Feb 2020: eabb2507. DOI: 10.1126/science.abb2507

<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/early/2020/02/19/science.abb2507/tab-pdf>>

Supplementary Materials

<https://science.sciencemag.org/highwire/filestream/739683/field_highwire_adjunct_files/0/abb2507-Wrapp-SM.pdf>

Materials and Methods: Figs. S1 to S8; Table S1; Captions for Movies S1 and S2; References; Images, Video, and Other Media.

Movie S1: CryoSPARC 3D variability analysis side-view. 2019-nCoV S trimer viewed from the side, along the viral membrane.

<https://science.sciencemag.org/highwire/filestream/739683/field_highwire_adjunct_files/1/abb2507s1.mov>

Movie S2: CryoSPARC 3D variability analysis top-view. 2019-nCoV S trimer viewed from the top, toward the viral membrane.

<https://science.sciencemag.org/highwire/filestream/739683/field_highwire_adjunct_files/2/abb2507s2.mov>

[Abstract: The outbreak of a novel betacoronavirus (2019-nCoV) represents a pandemic threat that has been declared a public health emergency of international concern. The CoV spike (S) glycoprotein is a key target for vaccines, therapeutic antibodies, and diagnostics. To facilitate medical countermeasure (MCM) development, we determined a 3.5 Å-resolution cryo-EM structure of the 2019-nCoV S trimer in the prefusion conformation. The predominant state of the trimer has one of the three receptor-binding domains (RBDs) rotated up in a receptor-accessible conformation. We also show biophysical and structural evidence that the 2019-nCoV S binds ACE2 with higher affinity than SARS-CoV S. Additionally, we tested several published SARS-CoV RBD-specific monoclonal antibodies and found that they do not have appreciable binding to 2019-nCoV S, suggesting antibody cross-reactivity may be limited between the two RBDs. The structure of 2019-nCoV S should enable rapid development and evaluation of MCMs to address the ongoing public health crisis.]

XU Jiabao, ZHAO Shizhe, TENG Tieshan, ABDALLA Abualgasim Elgaili, ZHU Wan, XIE Longxiang, WANG Yunlong & GUO Xiangqian

°2020 [pdf, docx, tif]

Systematic Comparison of Two Animal-to-Human Transmitted Human Coronaviruses: SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV,

in: Viruses 12(2): no. 244. (Special Issue Pathogenesis of Human and Animal Coronaviruses) [17p., 4 figs., 3 tables, 109 refs.; supplementary material: Table S1. The genomic information of latest SARS-CoV-2 strains. Figure S1.]

<<https://doi.org/10.3390/v12020244>>

[Abstract: After the outbreak of the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in the world in 2003, human coronaviruses (HCoVs) have been reported as pathogens that cause severe symptoms in respiratory tract infections. Recently, a new emerged HCoV isolated from the respiratory epithelium of unexplained pneumonia patients in the Wuhan seafood market caused a major disease outbreak and has been named the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). This virus causes acute lung symptoms, leading to a condition that has been named as “coronavirus disease 2019” (COVID-19). The emergence of SARS-CoV-2 and of SARS-CoV caused widespread fear and concern and has threatened global health security. There are some similarities and differences in the epidemiology and clinical features between these two viruses and diseases that are caused by these viruses. The goal of this work is to systematically review and compare between SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 in the context of their virus incubation, originations, diagnosis and treatment methods, genomic and proteomic

sequences, and pathogenic mechanisms. Keywords: coronaviruses; SARS-CoV-2; SARS-CoV; genomic comparison; proteomic comparison; pathogenic mechanism; clinical manifestations.]

Table 1. Comparison of SARS and COVID-19.

Items	SARS	COVID-19
First occurrence	Nov. 16th, 2002 in Foshan, Guangdong	Dec. 07th, 2019 in Wuhan, Hubei
Pathogen	SARS-CoV	SARS-CoV-2
Intermediate host	<i>Paguma larvata</i>	Pangolin, Mink (Possible)
Definitive host	<i>Rhinolophus sinicus</i>	<i>Rhinolophus affinis</i> (Possible)
Virus type	RNA virus	RNA virus
Species pathogen	β -coronavirus	β -coronavirus
Total DNA sequence length of pathogen	29,751	29,903
Latency	1–4 days on average	3–7 days on average
Susceptible people	Young adults	People who have not been exposed to SARS-CoV-2
Male–female patient ratio	1:1.25	2.70:1
Mortality	9.60%	2.10%
Clinical symptoms	Fever, cough, myalgia, dyspnea, and diarrhea	Fever, fatigue, and dry cough
Propagation mode	Droplets or close contacts	Droplets or close contacts
Major regional distribution	Beijing, Guangdong, Shanxi in China	Hubei, especially Wuhan in China
Diagnostic methods	RT-PCR, rRT-PCR, RT-LAMP, rRT-LAMP, Coronavirus detection kit	RT-PCR, rRT-PCR, RT-LAMP, rRT-LAMP, Coronavirus detection kit
Treatment	Glucocorticoid and interferon	Lopinavir/ritonavir (in testing)

Figure 1. Timeline of SARS (a) and COVID-19 (b) epidemic development.

YAN Renhong, ZHANG Yuanyuan, LI Yaning, XIA Lu, GUO Yingying, ZHOU Qiang
 ©2020 [2 pdf] *Structural basis for the recognition of the SARS-CoV-2 by full-length human ACE2,*

in: Science 04 Mar 2020: eabb2762.

[10p.; 5 figs. Supplementary material, 25p.: Materials/Methods, Supplementary Text, Tables, Figures, and/or References: Download Supplement / Materials and Methods: Figs. S1 to S9 / Table S1 / Caption for Movie S1 / References / MDAR Reproducibility Checklist / Images, Video, and Other Media / Movie S1: The struc-

tural morph between the closed and open conformation of the ACE2-Ba0AT1 complex.] DOI: 10.1126/science.abb2762.

<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/early/2020/03/03/science.abb2762>>

[Abstract: Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) is the cellular receptor for SARS coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and the new coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) that is causing the serious epidemic COVID-19. Here we present cryo-EM structures of full-length human ACE2, in the presence of a neutral amino acid transporter B⁰AT1, with or without the receptor binding domain (RBD) of the surface spike glycoprotein (S protein) of SARS-CoV-2, both at an overall resolution of 2.9 Å, with a local resolution of 3.5 Å at the ACE2-RBD interface. The ACE2-B⁰AT1 complex is assembled as a dimer of heterodimers, with the Collectrin-like domain (CLD) of ACE2 mediating homo-dimerization. The RBD is recognized by the extracellular peptidase domain (PD) of ACE2 mainly through polar residues. These findings provide important insights to the molecular basis for coronavirus recognition and infection.]

ZHANG Liangsheng, YANG Jian-Rong, ZHANG Zhenguo, LIN Zhenguo

©2020 [4 pdf, txt]

Genomic variations of SARS-CoV-2 suggest multiple outbreak sources of transmission,

in: medRxiv, March 05, 2020. [9p., 3 figs.; supplementary figs. 1-4.]

<<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.25.20027953>>

[Abstract: We examined 169 genomes of SARS-CoV-2 and found that they can be classified into two major genotypes, Type I and Type II. Type I can be further divided into Type IA and IB. Our phylogenetic analysis showed that the Type IA resembles the ancestral SARS-CoV-2 most. Type II was likely evolved from Type I and predominant in the infections. Our results suggest that Type II SARS-CoV-2 was the source of the outbreak in the Wuhan Huanan market and it was likely originated from a super-spreader. The outbreak caused by the Type I virus should have occurred somewhere else, because the patients had no direct link to the market. Furthermore, by analyzing three genomic sites that distinguish Type I and Type II strains, we found that synonymous changes at two of the three sites confer higher protein translational efficiencies in Type II strains than in Type I strains, which might explain why Type II strains are predominant, implying that Type II is more contagious (transmissible) than Type I. These findings could be valuable for the current epidemic prevention and control. –

“In summary, our results illustrate the presence of two major genotypes of SARS-CoV-2, suggesting of at least two, possibly three, major outbreak sources (Figure 3). The outbreak in the Huanan market may not be the initiation transmission of SARS-CoV-2 to human, and thus the location of initial transmission to humans remain to be determined. As most samples detected belong to Type II, it indicates that Type II is more transmissible. We identified three genomic variants that separate the two types of SARS-CoV-2. Our data suggest that two variants are linked to improved translation efficiency in Type II. The impacts of these genomic variants could be further evaluated by comparing the symptoms of patients infected by each type of viruses. Particularly, some asymptomatic carriers have been recently found [11]. It is worth examining whether these asymptomatic cases are enriched in Type I. With more sequencing data of SARS-CoV-2, we expect a more complete understanding of transmission history.”]

Fig 1

a: this column shows the number of tRNA genes in human genome with anticodons matching the considered codons. tAI is a measure of codon's translational efficiency¹⁰, the higher the more efficient.

ZHOU Peng, YANG Xing-Lou, WANG Xian-Guang, HU Ben, ZHANG Lei, ZHANG Wei, SI Hao-Rui, ZHU Yan, LI Bei, HUANG Chao-Lin, CHEN Hui-Dong, CHEN Jing, LUO Yun, GUO Hua, JIANG Ren-Di, LIU Mei-Qin, CHEN Ying, SHEN Xu-Rui, WANG Xi, ZHENG Xiao-Shuang, ZHAO Kai, CHEN Quan-Jiao [陳全姣], DENG Fei, LIU Lin-Lin, YAN Bing, ZHAN Fa-Xian, WANG Yan-Yi [王延軼], XIAO Geng-Fu & SHI Zheng-Li [石正麗]

*2020

Discovery of a novel coronavirus associated with the recent pneumonia outbreak in humans and its potential bat origin.

bioRxiv. 2020;10.1101/2020.01.22.914952.

<<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2020/01/23/2020.01.22.914952>>

*o2020 [pdf]

A pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin,

in: Nature, 03 February 2020 (open access). Accelerated Article

Preview. [23p.; 3 figs., Extended data: 7 figs., 4 tables.]

in: Nature 579: 270-273. <<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2012-7>>

[Abstract: Since the SARS outbreak 18 years ago, a large number of severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronaviruses (SARSr-CoV) have been discovered in their natural reservoir host, bats¹⁻⁴. Previous studies indicated that some of those bat SARSr-CoVs have the potential to infect humans⁵⁻⁷. Here we report the identification and characterization of a novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) which caused an epidemic of acute respiratory syndrome in humans in Wuhan, China. The epidemic, which started from 12 December 2019, has caused 2,050 laboratory-confirmed infections with 56 fatal cases by 26 January 2020. Full-length genome sequences were obtained from five patients at the early stage of the outbreak. They are almost identical to each other and share 79.5% sequence identity to SARS-CoV. Furthermore, it was found that 2019-nCoV is 96% identical at the whole-genome level to a bat coronavirus. The pairwise protein sequence analysis of seven conserved non-structural proteins show that this virus belongs to the species SARSr-CoV. The 2019-nCoV virus was then isolated from the bronchoalveolar lavage fluid of a critically ill patient, which can be neutralized by sera from several patients. Importantly, we have confirmed that this novel CoV uses the same cell entry receptor, ACE2, as SARS-CoV. –

• HORVAT Branka F1000Prime: This manuscript provides the first detailed report of a novel coronavirus which caused an epidemic of acute respiratory syndrome in humans in Wuhan,

China. The authors found that the new coronavirus belongs to the species of SARS-CoV and is 96% identical at the whole-genome level to a bat coronavirus, suggesting thus its probable bat origin. In addition, they isolated the virus from one critically ill patient and confirmed that the new virus uses the same cell receptor, ACE2, as the known SARS-CoV.
 Disclosures: Branka Horvat has a joint grant with ZL Shi.]

Fig. 1 | Genome characterization of 2019-nCoV. **a**, Metagenomics analysis of next-generation sequencing of BALF from patient ICU06. **b**, Genomic organization of 2019-nCoV WIV04. M, membrane. **c**, Similarity plot based on the full-length genome sequence of 2019-nCoV WIV04. Full-length genome sequences of SARS-CoV BJ01, bat SARSr-CoV WIV1, bat coronavirus RaTG13 and ZC45 were used as reference sequences. **d**, Phylogenetic tree based on

nucleotide sequences of complete genomes of coronaviruses. MHV, murine hepatitis virus; PEDV, porcine epidemic diarrhoea virus; TGEV, porcine transmissible gastroenteritis virus. The scale bars represent 0.1 substitutions per nucleotide position. Descriptions of the settings and software that was used are included in the Methods.

ZHU Na, ZHANG Dingyu, WANG Wenling, LI Xingwang, YANG Bo, SONG Jingdong, ZHAO Xiang, HUANG Baoying, SHI Weifeng, LU Roujian, NIU Peihua, ZHAN Faxian, MA Xuejun, WANG Dayan, XU Wenbo, WU Guizhen, GAO George F. & TAN Wenjie for the CHINA NOVEL CORONAVIRUS INVESTIGATING AND RESEARCH TEAM
 2020

A novel coronavirus from patients with pneumonia in China, 2019,
 in: New England Journal of Medicine January 24, 2020. [4 figs.]
<https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2001017>

[Summary: In December 2019, a cluster of patients with pneumonia of unknown cause was linked to a seafood wholesale market in Wuhan, China. A previously unknown betacoronavirus was discovered through the use of unbiased sequencing in samples from patients with pneumonia. Human airway epithelial cells were used to isolate a novel coronavirus, named 2019-nCoV, which formed a clade within the subgenus sarbecovirus, Orthocoronavirinae subfamily. Different from both MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV, 2019-nCoV is the seventh member of the family of coronaviruses that infect humans. Enhanced surveillance and further investigation are ongoing. (Funded by the National Key Research and Development Program of China and the National Major Project for Control and Prevention of Infectious Disease in China.)]

Figure 3. Visualization of 2019-nCoV with Transmission Electron Microscopy. Negative-stained 2019-nCoV particles are shown in Panel A, and 2019-nCoV particles in the human airway epithelial cell ultrathin sections are shown in Panel B. Arrowheads indicate extracellular virus particles, arrows indicate inclusion bodies formed by virus components, and triangles indicate cilia.

VAN DOREMALEN Neeltje, BUSHMAKER Trenton, MORRIS Dylan H., HOLBROOK Myndi G., GAMBLE Amandine, WILLIAMSON Brandi N., TAMIN Azaibi, HARCOURT Jennifer L., THORNBURG Natalie J., GERBER Susan I., LLOYD-SMITH James O., DE WIT Emmie, MUNSTER Vincent J.

2020

Aerosol and Surface Stability of SARS-CoV-2 as Compared with SARS-CoV-1,
(Correspondence)

in: *The New England Journal of Medicine*, March 17, 2020.

[3p., 1 fig.; supplementary appendix: 10p. figs. S1-S5, 1 suppl. table.]

<<https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMc2004973>>

AHMAD Tauseef, KHAN Muhammad, HAROON, MUSA Taha Hussein, NASIR Saima, HUI Jin, BONILLA-ALDANA D. Katterine, RODRIGUEZ-MORALES Alfonso J.

°2020

COVID-19: Zoonotic aspects, (Letter to the Editor)

in: *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, In Press, Corrected Proof

<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmaid.2020.101607>>

[Keywords: 2019-New coronavirus; Outbreak; Transmission; China. 1 fig.]

Fig. 1. Potential transmission cycles of SARS-CoV2 (formerly 2019nCoV).

ARAB-MAZAR Zahra, SAH Ranjit, RABAAN Ali A., DHAMA Kuldeep, RODRIGUEZ-MORALES Alfonso J.

°2020 [pdf]

Mapping the incidence of the COVID-19 hotspot in Iran – Implications for Travellers,

in: *Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 14 March 2020, 101630.

In Press, Corrected Proof. [3p., 1 fig.]

<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmaid.2020.101630>>

[“Dear Editor / After the first two months of the epidemics of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) in the world [1,2], caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2), multiple epidemiological assessments in countries from Asia, Pacific, Europe, and North America have been published [3,4]. Nevertheless, there are countries, with a rapid increase and a high number of cases, with a lack of studies. This is the case of Iran in the Middle East. For these reasons, we have developed epidemiological maps of cases but also of incidence rates using official populations, by provinces, for COVID-19 in Iran using geographical information systems (GIS).

Surveillance cases data from February 19 to March 9, 2020, officially reported by the Iranian health authorities were used to estimate the cumulated incidence rates using reference population data on SARS-CoV-2 confirmed infections (cases/100,000 pop) and to develop the maps by provinces, using the GIS software Kosmo® 3.1. (...”]

ARAÚJO Miguel B., NAIMI Babak
2020

Spread of SARS-CoV-2 Coronavirus likely to be constrained by climate,
in: medRxiv, March 16, 2020.

<<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.12.20034728>>

[Abstract: As new cases of SARS CoV-2 (aka 2019-nCoV) Coronavirus are confirmed throughout the world and millions of people are being put into quarantine, hit the developing world, such as sub-Saharan Africa, potentially leading to a global human calamity. It is still early days, but using existing data we develop a large ensemble of ecological niche models that project monthly variation in climate suitability of SARS-CoV-2 Coronavirus throughout a typical climatological year. The current spread suggests a degree of climate determination with Coronavirus displaying preference for cool and dry conditions. The predecessor SARS-CoV was linked to similar climate conditions. Should the spread of SARS CoV-2 continue to follow current trends, a worst-case scenario of synchronous global pandemic is improbable. More probable is the emergence of asynchronous seasonal global outbreaks much like other respiratory diseases. People in temperate warm and cold climates are more vulnerable. Those in arid climates follow next in vulnerability, while the disease will likely marginally affect the tropics. Our projections minimize uncertainties related with spread of SARS CoV-2, providing critical information for anticipating the adequate social, economic and political responses.]

BANNISTER-TYRRELL Melanie, MEYER Anne, FAVERJON Celine, CAMERON Angus
2020

Preliminary evidence that higher temperatures are associated with lower incidence

of COVID-19, for cases reported globally up to 29th February 2020,
in: medRxiv, March 20, 2020.

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.18.20036731>

[Abstract: Seasonal variation in COVID-19 incidence could impact the trajectory of the pandemic. Using global line-list data on COVID-19 cases reported until 29th February 2020 and global gridded temperature data, and after adjusting for surveillance capacity and time since first imported case, higher average temperature was strongly associated with lower COVID-19 incidence for temperatures of 1°C and higher. However, temperature explained a relatively modest amount of the total variation in COVID-19 incidence. These preliminary findings support stringent containment efforts in Europe and elsewhere.]

BI Qifang, WU Yongsheng, MEI Shujiang, YE Chenfei, ZOU Xuan, ZHANG Zhen, LIU Xiaojian, WEI Lan, TRUELOVE Shaun A., ZHANG Tong, GAO Wei, CHENG Cong, TANG Xiujuan, WU Xiaoliang, WU Yu, SUN Binbin, HUANG Suli, SUN Yu, ZHANG Juncen, MA Ting, LESSLER Justin, FENG Teijian
°2020 [pdf]

Epidemiology and Transmission of COVID-19 in Shenzhen China: Analysis of 391 cases and 1,286 of their close contacts,

in: medRxiv, Posted March 04, 2020. [21p., 3 tables, 3 figs., 20 refs.;

supplementary material: tables S1-S4, figs. S1-S2, texts S1-S2.]

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.03.20028423>

[Abstract: Background: Rapid spread of SARS-CoV-2 in Wuhan prompted heightened surveillance in Shenzhen and elsewhere in China. The resulting data provide a rare opportunity to measure key metrics of disease course, transmission, and the impact of control. Methods: The Shenzhen CDC identified 391 SARS-CoV-2 cases from January 14 to February 12, 2020 and 1286 close contacts. We compare cases identified through symptomatic surveillance and contact tracing, and estimate the time from symptom onset to confirmation, isolation, and hospitalization. We estimate metrics of disease transmission and analyze factors influencing transmission risk. Findings: Cases were older than the general population (mean age 45) and balanced between males (187) and females (204). Ninety-one percent had mild or moderate clinical severity at initial assessment. Three have died, 225 have recovered (median time to recovery is 32 days). Cases were isolated on average 4.6 days after developing symptoms; contact tracing reduced this by 1.9 days. Household contacts and those travelling with a case were at higher risk of infection (ORs 6 and 7) than other close contacts. The household secondary attack rate was 15%, and children were as likely to be infected as adults. The observed reproductive number was 0.4, with a mean serial interval of 6.3 days. Interpretation: Our data on cases as well as their infected and uninfected close contacts provide key insights into SARS-CoV-2 epidemiology. This work shows that heightened surveillance and isolation, particularly contact tracing, reduces the time cases are infectious in the community, thereby reducing R. Its overall impact, however, is uncertain and highly dependent on the number of asymptomatic cases. We further show that children are at similar risk of infection as the general population, though less likely to have severe symptoms; hence should be considered in analyses of transmission and control.

8: "Discussion / This analysis of early SARS-CoV-2 cases and their close contacts in Shenzhen China, provides insights into the natural history, transmission and control of this disease. The values estimated provide the evidentiary foundation for predicting the impact of this virus, evaluating control measures, and guiding the global response. Analysis of how cases are detected, and use of data on individuals exposed but not infected, allow us to show that infection rates in young children are no lower than the population average (even if rates of clinical disease are). We are able to directly estimate critical transmission parameters, and show that, at least among observed contacts, transmission rates are low. Estimates of the distribution of time between symptom onset and case isolation by surveillance type reveal that heightened surveillance combined with case isolation could plausibly account for these low rates of transmission. These results paint a positive picture of the impact of heightened surveillance and isolation in Shenzhen. However, uncertainty in the number of asymptomatic cases missed by surveillance and their ability to transmit must temper any hopes of stopping the COVID-19 epidemic by this means. / This work further supports the picture of COVID-19 as a disease with a fairly short incubation period (mean 4-6 days) but a long clinical course ^{2,7,19}, with patients taking many weeks to die or recover. It should be noted, however, that we estimate a higher proportion of cases taking 14 days or more to develop symptoms (9%) than previous studies ^{6,7,27}]

CHAN Jasper Fuk-Woo, YUAN Shuofeng, KOK Kin-Hang, TO Kelvin Kai-Wang, CHU Hin, YANG Jin, XING Fanfan, LIU Jiuling, YIP Cyril Chik-Yan, POON Rosana Wing-Shan, TSOI Hoi-Wah, LO Simon Kam-Fai, CHAN Kwok-Hung, POON Vincent Kwok-Man, CHAN Wan-Mui,

IP Jonathan Daniel, CAI Jian-Piao, CHENG Vincent Chi-Chung, CHEN Honglin, HUI Christopher Kim-Ming, YUEN Kwok-Yung

°2020 [2 pdf]

A familial cluster of pneumonia associated with the 2019 novel coronavirus indicating person-to-person transmission: a study of a family cluster,
in: *The Lancet*, January 24, 2020. [10p.; 4 figs.; 2 tables; supplementary appendix: 8p.] <[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30154-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30154-9)> (PMID: 31986261)

[Summary: Background: An ongoing outbreak of pneumonia associated with a novel coronavirus was reported in Wuhan city, Hubei province, China. Affected patients were geographically linked with a local wet market as a potential source. No data on person-to-person or nosocomial transmission have been published to date.

Methods: In this study, we report the epidemiological, clinical, laboratory, radiological, and microbiological findings of five patients in a family cluster who presented with unexplained pneumonia after returning to Shenzhen, Guangdong province, China, after a visit to Wuhan, and an additional family member who did not travel to Wuhan. Phylogenetic analysis of genetic sequences from these patients were done.

Findings: From Jan 10, 2020, we enrolled a family of six patients who travelled to Wuhan from Shenzhen between Dec 29, 2019 and Jan 4, 2020. Of six family members who travelled to Wuhan, five were identified as infected with the novel coronavirus. Additionally, one family member, who did not travel to Wuhan, became infected with the virus after several days of contact with four of the family members. None of the family members had contacts with Wuhan markets or animals, although two had visited a Wuhan hospital. Five family members (aged 36–66 years) presented with fever, upper or lower respiratory tract symptoms, or diarrhoea, or a combination of these 3–6 days after exposure. They presented to our hospital (The University of Hong Kong-Shenzhen Hospital, Shenzhen) 6–10 days after symptom onset. They and one asymptomatic child (aged 10 years) had radiological ground-glass lung opacities. Older patients (aged >60 years) had more systemic symptoms, extensive radiological ground-glass lung changes, lymphopenia, thrombocytopenia, and increased C-reactive protein and lactate dehydrogenase levels. The nasopharyngeal or throat swabs of these six patients were negative for known respiratory microbes by point-of-care multiplex RT-PCR, but five patients (four adults and the child) were RT-PCR positive for genes encoding the internal RNA-dependent RNA polymerase and surface Spike protein of this novel coronavirus, which were confirmed by Sanger sequencing. Phylogenetic analysis of these five patients' RT-PCR amplicons and two full genomes by next-generation sequencing showed that this is a novel coronavirus, which is closest to the bat severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS)-related coronaviruses found in Chinese horseshoe bats.

Interpretation: Our findings are consistent with person-to-person transmission of this novel coronavirus in hospital and family settings, and the reports of infected travellers in other geographical regions.

Funding: The Shaw Foundation Hong Kong, Michael Seak-Kan Tong, Respiratory Viral Research Foundation Limited, Hui Ming, Hui Hoy and Chow Sin Lan Charity Fund Limited, Marina Man-Wai Lee, the Hong Kong Hainan Commercial Association South China Microbiology Research Fund, Sanming Project of Medicine (Shenzhen), and High Level-Hospital Program (Guangdong Health Commission).]

CHEN Biqing, LIANG Hao, YUAN Xiaomin, HU Yingying, XU Miao, ZHAO Yating, ZHANG Binfen, TIAN Fang, ZHU Xuejun

2020

Roles of meteorological conditions in COVID-19 transmission on a worldwide scale,

in: medRxiv, March 20, 2020.

<<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.16.20037168>>

[Abstract: The novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2/2019-nCoV) identified in Wuhan, China, in December 2019 has caused great damage to public health and economy worldwide with over 140,000 infected cases up to date. Previous research has suggested an involvement of meteorological conditions in the spread of droplet-mediated viral diseases, such as influenza. However, as for the recent novel coronavirus, few studies have discussed systematically about the role of daily weather in the epidemic transmission of the virus. Here, we examine the relationships of meteorological variables with the severity of the outbreak on a worldwide scale. The confirmed case counts, which indicates the severity of COVID-19 spread, and four meteorological variables, i.e., air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, and visibility, were collected daily between January 20 and March 11 (52 days) for 430 cities and districts all over China, 21 cities/provinces in Italy, 21 cities/provinces in Japan, and 51 other countries around the world. Four different time delays of weather (on the day, 3 days ago, 7 days ago, and 14 days ago) as to the epidemic situation were taken for modeling and we finally chose the weather two weeks ago to model

against the daily epidemic situation as its correlated with the outbreak best. Taken Chinese cities as a discovery dataset, it was suggested that temperature, wind speed, and relative humidity combined together could best predict the epidemic situation. The meteorological model could well predict the outbreak around the world with a high correlation ($r^2 > 0.6$) with the real data. Using this model, we further predicted the possible epidemic situation in the future 12 days in several high-latitude cities with potential outbreak. This model could provide more information for government's future decisions on COVID-19 outbreak control.]

CHINAZZI Matteo, DAVIS Jessica T., AJELLI Marco, GIOANNINI Corrado, LITVINOVA Maria, MERLER Stefano, PASTORE Y PIONTTI Ana, MU Kunpeng, ROSSI Luca, SUN Kaiyuan, VIBOUD Cécile, XIONG Xinyue, YU Hongjie, HALLORAN M. Elizabeth, LONGINI Ira M. Jr., VESPIGNANI Alessandro

2020

The effect of travel restrictions on the spread of the 2019 novel coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak,

in: Science 06 Mar 2020: eaba9757. DOI: 10.1126/science.aba9757.

<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/early/2020/03/05/science.aba9757>>

[Abstract: Motivated by the rapid spread of COVID-19 in Mainland China, we use a global metapopulation disease transmission model to project the impact of travel limitations on the national and international spread of the epidemic. The model is calibrated based on internationally reported cases, and shows that at the start of the travel ban from Wuhan on 23 January 2020, most Chinese cities had already received many infected travelers. The travel quarantine of Wuhan delayed the overall epidemic progression by only 3 to 5 days in Mainland China, but has a more marked effect at the international scale, where case importations were reduced by nearly 80% until mid February. Modeling results also indicate that sustained 90% travel restrictions to and from Mainland China only modestly affect the epidemic trajectory unless combined with a 50% or higher reduction of transmission in the community.]

GARDNER Lauren

°2020 [pdf]

Mapping the Wuhan Coronavirus (2019-nCoV).

JHU CSSE, January 23, 2020.

<<https://systems.jhu.edu/research/public-health/ncov/>>

GIS Dashboard In response to this ongoing public health emergency, we developed an [online dashboard](#) (static snapshot shown below) to visualize and track the reported cases on a daily timescale; the complete set of data is downloadable as a google sheet. The case data visualized is collected from various sources, including [WHO](#), [U.S. CDC](#), [ECDC](#) [China CDC \(CCDC\)](#), [NHC](#) and [DXY](#). DXY is a Chinese website that aggregates NHC and local CCDC situation reports in near real-time, providing more current regional case estimates than the national level reporting organizations are capable of, and is thus used for all the mainland China cases reported in our dashboard (confirmed, suspected, recovered, deaths). U.S. cases (confirmed, suspected, recovered, deaths) are taken from the U.S. CDC, and all other country (suspected and confirmed) case data is taken from the corresponding regional health departments. The dashboard is intended to provide the public with an understanding of the outbreak situation as it unfolds, with transparent data sources.

GRALINSKI Lisa E. & MENACHERY Vineet D.

2020

Return of the Coronavirus: 2019-nCoV, (Commentary)

in: Viruses 2020, 12(2), no. 135. (Special Issue Pathogenesis of Human and Animal Coronaviruses) <<https://doi.org/10.3390/v12020135>>

[Abstract: The emergence of a novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) has awakened the echoes of SARS-CoV from nearly two decades ago. Yet, with technological advances and important lessons gained from previous outbreaks, perhaps the world is better equipped to deal with the most recent emergent group 2B coronavirus.]

IMAI Natsuko, DORIGATTI Ilaria, CORI Anne, RILEY Steven, FERGUSON Neil M.

2020

Report 1: Estimating the potential total number of novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) cases in Wuhan City, China.

London: Imperial College, 17 January 2020.

<<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/medicine/sph/ide/gida-fellowships/2019-nCoV-outbreak-report-17-01-2020.pdf>>

[Summary Report 1: Many aspects of the novel Wuhan coronavirus outbreak are highly uncertain. However, the detection of three cases outside China (two in Thailand, one in Japan) is

worrying. We calculate, based on flight and population data, that there is only a 1 in 574 chance that a person infected in Wuhan would travel overseas before they sought medical care. This implies there might have been over 1700 (3 x 574) cases in Wuhan so far. There are many unknowns, meaning the uncertainty range around this estimate goes from 190 cases to over 4000. But the magnitude of these numbers suggests that substantial human to human transmission cannot be ruled out. Heightened surveillance, prompt information sharing and enhanced preparedness are recommended.]

IMAI Natsuko, DORIGATTI Ilaria, CORI Anne, DONNELLY Christl, RILEY Steven, FERGUSON Neil M.
2020

Report 2: Estimating the potential total number of novel Coronavirus cases in Wuhan City, China.

London: Imperial College, 22 January 2020.

<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/medicine/sph/ide/gida-fellowships/2019-nCoV-outbreak-report-22-01-2020.pdf>

[Summary Report 2: On January 16th we released estimates of the scale of the nCoV-19 outbreak in China based on an analysis of the number of cases detected outside mainland China. Since then, cumulative confirmed cases reported by the Chinese authorities have increased 10-fold, to 440 by January 22nd. The number of detected outside China with symptom onset by 18th January had increased to 7 in the same time. Here we report updated estimates of the scale of the epidemic in Wuhan, based on an analysis of flight and population data from that city. Our estimate of the number of cases in Wuhan with symptoms onset by January 18th is now 4,000. The uncertainty range is 1,000-9,700, reflecting the many continuing unknowns involved in deriving these estimates. Our central estimate of 4,000 is more than double our past estimates, a result of the increase of the number of cases detected outside mainland China from 3 to 7. Our estimates should not be interpreted as implying the outbreak has suddenly doubled in size in the period 12th January to 18th January – delays in confirming and reporting exported cases and incomplete information about dates of symptom onset together with the still very small numbers of exported cases mean we are unable to estimate the epidemic growth rate at the current time.

Our analysis suggests that the 2019-nCoV outbreak has caused substantially more cases of moderate or severe respiratory illness in Wuhan than have currently been detected. However, recent rapid increases in officially reported confirmed case numbers in China suggest that case detection and reporting has been substantially enhanced in recent days. With further refinements and expansion of surveillance (for instance, to primary care providers) it is to be hoped that the differences between our estimates and official case numbers will lessen further. Given the increasing evidence for human-to-human transmission, enhancing rapid case detection will be essential if the outbreak is to be controlled.]

IMAI Natsuko, CORI Anne, DORIGATTI Ilaria, BAGUELIN Marc, DONNELLY Christl A., RILEY Steven, FERGUSON Neil M.
2020

Report 3: Transmissibility of 2019-nCoV.

London: Imperial College, 25 January 2020.

<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/media/imperial-college/medicine/sph/ide/gida-fellowships/Imperial-2019-nCoV-transmissibility.pdf>

[Note: This is an extended version of an analysis previously shared with WHO, governments and academic networks between 22/1/20-24/1/20.

Summary Report 3: Self-sustaining human-to-human transmission of the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) is the only plausible explanation of the scale of the outbreak in Wuhan. We estimate that, on average, each case infected 2.6 (uncertainty range: 1.5-3.5) other people up to 18th January 2020, based on an analysis combining our past estimates of the size of the outbreak in Wuhan with computational modelling of potential epidemic trajectories. This implies that control measures need to block well over 60% of transmission to be effective in controlling the outbreak. It is likely, based on the experience of SARS and MERS-CoV, that the number of secondary cases caused by a case of 2019-nCoV is highly variable – with many cases causing no secondary infections, and a few causing many. Whether transmission is continuing at the same rate currently depends on the effectiveness of current control measures implemented in China and the extent to which the populations of affected areas have adopted risk-reducing behaviours. In the absence of antiviral drugs or vaccines, control relies upon the prompt detection and isolation of symptomatic cases. It is unclear at the current time whether this outbreak can be contained within China; uncertainties include the severity spectrum of the disease caused by this virus and whether cases with relatively mild symptoms are able to transmit the virus efficiently. Identification and testing of potential cases need to be as extensive as is permitted by healthcare and diagnostic testing capacity – including the identification, testing and isolation of

suspected cases with only mild to moderate disease (e.g. influenza-like illness), when logistically feasible.]

KUCHARSKI Adam, RUSSELL Tim, DIAMOND Charlie, LIU Yang, CMMID nCoV WORKING GROUP, EDMUNDS John, FUNK Sebastian, EGGO Rosalind
2020

Analysis and projections of transmission dynamics of nCoV in Wuhan.
CMMID, 12 February, 2020.

https://cmmid.github.io/ncov/wuhan_early_dynamics/index.html

[Note: this is preliminary analysis and has not yet been peer-reviewed.]

Aim: To understand how human-to-human transmission varied in Wuhan during the early stages of the 2019-2020 nCoV outbreak and project forward based on current trends.

Methods summary

- To estimate the early dynamics of transmission in Wuhan, we fitted a mathematical model to multiple available datasets on international exported cases from Wuhan and cases in Wuhan. Fitting to multiple data sources rather than a single dataset (or data point) is particularly useful for estimates in real-time, because some datasets may be unreliable.
- Transmission was a random process in the model, and could vary over time – this means the model can uncover fluctuations in transmission during the early stages of the outbreak. Our group previously used a similar analysis to understand the dynamics of Ebola in Liberia.
- We assumed that the chance of cases being exported from Wuhan to other countries depended on the number of cases in Wuhan, the number of outbound travellers (accounting for travel restrictions after 23rd January), and the relative connectivity of different countries. We considered the 30 countries outside China most at risk of exported cases in the analysis. The model accounts for delays in symptom onset and reporting (see methods below).

Key results

- We estimated that the median effective basic reproduction number, R_t , had likely been fluctuating between 1.5-4.5 prior to travel restrictions being introduced on 23rd Jan (Figure 1E). (The effective reproduction number is the average number of secondary cases generated by a typical infectious individual at a given point in time).
- If R_t continues to vary as it has in Wuhan, we projected that the outbreak would peak in mid-to-late-February (Figure 1C-D). There is substantial uncertainty about what the exact height and timing of the peak might be - currently the model predicts the peak as a result of susceptibility declining to the point where transmission cannot be sustained. As we get more data in the coming days, we will be able to refine these projections.
- Based on the median reproduction number observed during January before travel restrictions were introduced, we estimated that a single introduction of 2019-nCoV with SARS-like or MERS-like individual-level variation in transmission would have a 20–30% probability of causing a large outbreak, assuming Wuhan-like transmission. Assuming SARS-like individual variation in transmission, we estimated that once more than three infections have been independently introduced into a new location with Wuhan-like transmission, there is an over 50% chance that an outbreak will occur. We have made an online tool so that users can explore different scenarios further.

Figure 1: Dynamics of transmission in Wuhan, fitted up to 28 January 2020. Red line marks travel restrictions starting on 23 January 2020. A) Onset dates of confirmed cases in Wuhan (triangles) and China (diamonds). Blue lines and shaded regions: median of simulated trajectories, 50% and 95% credible intervals of model estimate. B) Reported cases by date of onset (black) and estimated internationally exported cases from Wuhan by date of onset (blue line). C) Estimated prevalence of asymptomatic or pre-symptomatic infections over time in Wuhan, as proportion of population. Black dots show estimated prevalence based on evacuation flights, with 95% binomial CI shown by lines. D) Cumulative confirmed cases by date in Wuhan (points) and estimated cumulative cases (blue line). E) Estimated daily reproduction number (R) over time. F) International exportation events by date of confirmation of case, and expected number of exports in the fitted model G) Expected international exportation events by individual country and observed exports. Datasets that were fitted to shown as solid points; non-fitted data shown as circles. Grey box shows period of projection.]

LI Qun, GUAN Xuhua, WU Peng, WANG Xiaoye, ZHOU Lei, TONG Yeqing, REN Ruiqi, LEUNG Kathy S.M., LAU Eric H.Y., WONG Jessica Y., XING Xuesen, XIANG Nijuan, WU Yang, LI Chao, CHEN Qi, LI Dan, LIU Tian, ZHAO Jing, LIU Man, TU Wenxiao, CHEN Chuding, JIN Lianmei, YANG Rui, WANG Qi, ZHOU Suhua, WANG Rui, LIU Hui, LUO Yinbo, LIU Yuan, SHAO Ge, LI Huan, TAO Zhongfa, YANG Yang, DENG Zhiqiang, LIU Boxi, MA Zhitao, ZHANG Yanping, SHI Guoqing, LAM Tommy Tsan-Yuk, WU Joseph T., GAO George F., COWLING Benjamin J., YANG Bo, LEUNG Gabriel M. & FENG Zijian

°2020 [pdf]

Early Transmission Dynamics in Wuhan, China, of Novel Coronavirus–Infected Pneumonia,

in: *The New England Journal of Medicine* January 29, 2020.

[3 figs., 1 table.] <<https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2001316>>

[Abstract: Background: The initial cases of novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV)–infected pneumonia (NCIP) occurred in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China, in December 2019 and January 2020. We analyzed data on the first 425 confirmed cases in Wuhan to determine the epidemiologic characteristics of NCIP.

Methods: We collected information on demographic characteristics, exposure history, and illness timelines of laboratory-confirmed cases of NCIP that had been reported by January 22, 2020. We described characteristics of the cases and estimated the key epidemiologic time-delay distributions. In the early period of exponential growth, we estimated the epidemic doubling time and the basic reproductive number.

Results: Among the first 425 patients with confirmed NCIP, the median age was 59 years and 56% were male. The majority of cases (55%) with onset before January 1, 2020, were linked to the Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market, as compared with 8.6% of the subsequent cases. The mean incubation period was 5.2 days (95% confidence interval [CI], 4.1 to 7.0), with the 95th percentile of the distribution at 12.5 days. In its early stages, the epidemic doubled in size every 7.4 days. With a mean serial interval of 7.5 days (95% CI, 5.3 to 19), the basic reproductive number was estimated to be 2.2 (95% CI, 1.4 to 3.9).

Conclusions: On the basis of this information, there is evidence that human-to-human transmission has occurred among close contacts since the middle of December 2019. Considerable efforts to reduce transmission will be required to control outbreaks if similar dynamics apply elsewhere. Measures to prevent or reduce transmission should be implemented in populations at risk. (Funded by the Ministry of Science and Technology of China and others.)]

LI Ruiyun, PEI Sen, CHEN Bin, SONG Yimeng, ZHANG Tao, YANG Wan, SHAMAN Jeffrey 2020

Substantial undocumented infection facilitates the rapid dissemination of novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV2),

in: *Science* 16 Mar 2020: eabb3221. DOI: 10.1126/science.abb3221.

[Supplementary Materials: Materials and Methods; Figs. S1 to S26; Tables S1 to S3; References (20–37); MDAR Reproducibility Checklist; Data S1.]

<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/early/2020/03/24/science.abb3221>>

[Abstract: Estimation of the prevalence and contagiousness of undocumented novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV2) infections is critical for understanding the overall prevalence and pandemic potential of this disease. Here we use observations of reported infection within China, in conjunction with mobility data, a networked dynamic metapopulation model and Bayesian inference, to infer critical epidemiological characteristics associated with SARS-CoV2, including the fraction of undocumented infections and their contagiousness. We estimate 86% of all infections were undocumented (95% CI: [82%–90%]) prior to 23 January 2020 travel restrictions. Per person, the transmission rate of undocumented infections was 55% of documented infec-

tions ([46%–62%]), yet, due to their greater numbers, undocumented infections were the infection source for 79% of documented cases. These findings explain the rapid geographic spread of SARS-CoV2 and indicate containment of this virus will be particularly challenging.]

MAIER Benjamin F., BROCKMANN Dirk

2020

Effective containment explains subexponential growth in recent confirmed COVID-19 cases in China,

in: Science 08 April 2020: eabb4557. DOI: 10.1126/science.abb4557.

<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/early/2020/04/07/science.abb4557>>

[Abstract: The recent outbreak of COVID-19 in Mainland China was characterized by a distinctive subexponential increase of confirmed cases during the early phase of the epidemic, contrasting an initial exponential growth expected for an unconstrained outbreak. We show that this effect can be explained as a direct consequence of containment policies that effectively deplete the susceptible population. To this end, we introduce a parsimonious model that captures both, quarantine of symptomatic infected individuals as well as population-wide isolation practices in response to containment policies or behavioral changes and show that the model captures the observed growth behavior accurately. The insights provided here may aid the careful implementation of containment strategies for ongoing secondary outbreaks of COVID-19 or similar future outbreaks of other emergent infectious diseases.]

THE NOVEL CORONAVIRUS PNEUMONIA EMERGENCY RESPONSE EPIDEMIOLOGY TEAM

°2020 [pdf]

Vital Surveillances: The Epidemiological Characteristics of an Outbreak of 2019 Novel Coronavirus Diseases (COVID-19) — China, 2020,

in: China CDC Weekly 2(8): 113-122, 4 figs., 2 tables.

<<http://weekly.chinacdc.cn/en/article/id/e53946e2-c6c4-41e9-9a9b-fea8db1a8f51>>

[Abstract: Background: An outbreak of 2019 novel coronavirus diseases (COVID-19) in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China has spread quickly nationwide. Here, we report results of a descriptive, exploratory analysis of all cases diagnosed as of February 11, 2020.

Methods: All COVID-19 cases reported through February 11, 2020 were extracted from China's Infectious Disease Information System. Analyses included the following: 1) summary of patient characteristics; 2) examination of age distributions and sex ratios; 3) calculation of case fatality and mortality rates; 4) geo-temporal analysis of viral spread; 5) epidemiological curve construction; and 6) subgroup analysis.

Results: A total of 72,314 patient records—44,672 (61.8%) confirmed cases, 16,186 (22.4%) suspected cases, 10,567 (14.6%) clinically diagnosed cases (Hubei Province only), and 889 asymptomatic cases (1.2%)—contributed data for the analysis. Among confirmed cases, most were aged 30–79 years (86.6%), diagnosed in Hubei (74.7%), and considered mild (80.9%). A total of 1,023 deaths occurred among confirmed cases for an overall case fatality rate of 2.3%. The COVID-19 spread outward from Hubei Province sometime after December 2019, and by February 11, 2020, 1,386 counties across all 31 provinces were affected. The epidemic curve of onset of symptoms peaked around January 23–26, then began to decline leading up to February 11. A total of 1,716 health workers have become infected and 5 have died (0.3%).

Conclusions: COVID-19 epidemic has spread very quickly taking only 30 days to expand from Hubei to the rest of Mainland China. With many people returning from a long holiday, China needs to prepare for the possible rebound of the epidemic.]

summary:

• WU Zunyou, MCGOOGAN Jennifer M. 2020.

PETROSILLO Nicola, VICECONTE Giulio, ERGONUL Onder, IPPOLITO Giuseppe, PETERSEN Eskild

°2020

COVID-19, SARS and MERS: are they closely related? (Narrative Review)

in: Clinical Microbiology and Infection, 28 March 2020, In Press, Journal Pre-proof. [23p., 2 tables, 52 refs.]

<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2020.03.026>>

[Abstract: Background: The 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) is a new human coronavirus which is spreading with epidemic features in China and other Asian countries with cases reported worldwide. This novel Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) is associated with a respiratory illness that may cause severe pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). Although related to the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), COVID-19 shows some peculiar pathogenetic, epidemiological and clinical features which have not been completely understood to date.

Objectives: We provide a review of the differences in terms of pathogenesis, epidemiology and clinical features between COVID-19, SARS and MERS.

Sources: The most recent literature in English language regarding COVID-19 has been reviewed and extracted data have been compared with the current scientific evidence about SARS and MERS epidemics.

Content: COVID-19 seems not to be very different from SARS regarding its clinical features. However, it has a fatality rate of 2.3%, lower than SARS (9.5%) and much lower than MERS (34.4%). It cannot be excluded that because of the COVID-19 less severe clinical picture it can spread in the community more easily than MERS and SARS. The actual basic reproductive number (R0) of COVID-19 (2-2.5) is still controversial. It is probably slightly higher than the R0 of SARS (1.7-1.9) and higher than MERS (<1). The gastrointestinal route of transmission of SARS-CoV-2, which has been also assumed for SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV, cannot be ruled out and needs to be further investigated.

Implications: There is still much more to know about COVID-19, especially as concerns mortality and capacity of spreading on a pandemic level. Nonetheless, all of the lessons we learned in the past from SARS and MERS epidemics are the best cultural weapons to face this new global threat. Keywords: Coronavirus; COVID-19; Emerging infections; MERS; SARS.]

RIOU Julien, ALTHAUS Christian L.

°2020 [pdf]

Pattern of early human-to-human transmission of Wuhan 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV), December 2019 to January 2020,

in: *Euro Surveillance* 2020; 25(4). [5p.; 3 figs., 1 table.]

<<https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.4.2000058>>

[Abstract: Since December 2019, China has been experiencing a large outbreak of a novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) which can cause respiratory disease and severe pneumonia. We estimated the basic reproduction number R0 of 2019-nCoV to be around 2.2 (90% high density interval: 1.4–3.8), indicating the potential for sustained human-to-human transmission. Transmission characteristics appear to be of similar magnitude to severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and pandemic influenza, indicating a risk of global spread.]

press release:

• *Coronavirus: Berner Forscher berechnen die Ausbreitung.* Universität Bern.

<https://www.unibe.ch/aktuell/medien/media_relations/medienmitteilungen/2020/medienmitteilungen_2020/coronavirus_berner_forscher_berechnen_die_ausbreitung/index_ger.html>

ROBERT KOCH INSTITUT (RKI)

°2020 [pdf]

SARS-CoV-2 Steckbrief zur Coronavirus-Krankheit-2019 (COVID-19).

Stand: 03.04.2020.

<https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/InfAZ/N/Neuartiges_Coronavirus/Steckbrief.html>

ROTHER Camilla *et al.*

2020

Transmission of 2019-nCoV Infection from an Asymptomatic Contact in Germany, (Letter)

in: *The New England Journal of Medicine* January 30, 2020.

<<https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMc2001468>>

[Correction mentioned in KUPFERSCHMIDT 2020.]

ROVETTA Alessandro

°2020 [pdf]

Mathematical-statistical modeling of COVID-19 on the restricted population.

February 29, 2020.

<<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339566420>>

[With this article, we intend to find the best model to represent COVID-19 behavior on a restricted scale. The aim is to verify the goodness of the descriptive model and observe the limits of deterministic predictions on a real complex system.]

SAJADI Mohammad M., HABIBZADEH Parham, VINTZILEOS Augustin, SHOKOUHI Shervin
MIRALLES-WILHELM Fernando & AMOROSO Anthony

2020

Temperature, Humidity and Latitude Analysis to Predict Potential Spread and Seasonality for COVID-19 (March 5, 2020).

in: SSRN-id3550308. [18p., 5 figs., 1 table; supplementary fig. 1, tables 1-2.]

<<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3550308>>

<<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3550308>>

[Abstract: Background: A significant number of infectious diseases display seasonal patterns in their incidence, including human coronaviruses. Betacoronaviruses such as MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV are not thought to be seasonal.

Methods: We examined climate data from cities with significant community spread of COVID-19 using ERA-5 reanalysis, and compared to areas that are either not affected, or do not have significant community spread.

Findings: To date, Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by SARS-CoV-2, has established significant community spread in cities and regions along a narrow east west distribution roughly along the 30-50°N corridor at consistently similar weather patterns consisting of average temperatures of 5-11°C, combined with low specific (3-6 g/kg) and absolute humidity (4-7 g/m³). There has been a lack of significant community establishment in expected locations that are based only on population proximity and extensive population interaction through travel.

Interpretation: The distribution of significant community outbreaks along restricted latitude, temperature, and humidity are consistent with the behavior of a seasonal respiratory virus. Additionally, we have proposed a simplified model that shows a zone at increased risk for COVID-19 spread. Using weather modeling, it may be possible to predict the regions most likely to be at higher risk of significant community spread of COVID-19 in the upcoming weeks, allowing for concentration of public health efforts on surveillance and containment.

Keywords: COVID-19; SARS-CoV-2; novel coronavirus; coronavirus; temperature; latitude; seasonality.]

SHIM Eunha, TARIQ Amna, CHOI Wongyeong, LEE Yiseul, CHOWELL Gerardo

©2020 [pdf]

Transmission potential and severity of COVID-19 in South Korea,

in: *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 93: 339-344, 3 figs.,

3 tables. <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.03.031>>

[Highlights:

- COVID-19 caused 6284 cases and 42 deaths in South Korea as of March 6, 2020.
- The mean reproduction number R_t of COVID-19 in Korea was estimated at 1.5.
- The crude case fatality rate is higher among males and increases with age.
- Sustained disease transmission of COVID-19 in the region is suggested.
- Our estimates support the implementation of social distancing measures in Korea.

Abstract: Objectives: Since the first case of 2019 novel coronavirus (COVID-19) identified on Jan 20, 2020, in South Korea, the number of cases rapidly increased, resulting in 6284 cases including 42 deaths as of Mar 6, 2020. To examine the growth rate of the outbreak, we present the first study to report the reproduction number of COVID-19 in South Korea.

Methods: The daily confirmed cases of COVID-19 in South Korea were extracted from publicly available sources. By using the empirical reporting delay distribution and simulating the generalized growth model, we estimated the effective reproduction number based on the discretized probability distribution of the generation interval.

Results: We identified four major clusters and estimated the reproduction number at 1.5 (95% CI: 1.4–1.6). In addition, the intrinsic growth rate was estimated at 0.6 (95% CI: 0.6, 0.7), and the scaling of growth parameter was estimated at 0.8 (95% CI: 0.7, 0.8), indicating sub-exponential growth dynamics of COVID-19. The crude case fatality rate is higher among males (1.1%) compared to females (0.4%) and increases with older age.

Conclusions: Our results indicate an early sustained transmission of COVID-19 in South Korea and support the implementation of social distancing measures to rapidly control the outbreak.

Keywords: Coronavirus; COVID-19; Korea; Reproduction number.]

TIAN Huaiyu, LIU Yonghong, LI Yidan, WU Chieh-Hsi, CHEN Bin, KRAEMER Moritz U.G., LI Bingying, CAI Jun, XU Bo, YANG Qiqi, WANG Ben, YANG Peng, CUI Yujun, SONG Yimeng, ZHENG Pai, WANG Quanyi, BJORNSTAD Ottar N., YANG Ruifu, GRENFELL Bryan T., PYBUS Oliver G., DYE Christopher

©2020 [pdf]

An investigation of transmission control measures during the first 50 days of the COVID-19 epidemic in China,

in: *Science* 31 Mar 2020: eabb6105. [8p., 4 figs., 3 tables, 18 refs.;

supplementary materials: 24p., Materials and Methods; Figs S1 to S7; Tables S1 to S4; References (19-28).] DOI: 10.1126/science.abb6105.

<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/early/2020/03/30/science.abb6105>>

[Abstract: Responding to an outbreak of a novel coronavirus (agent of COVID-19) in December 2019, China banned travel to and from Wuhan city on 23 January and implemented a national emergency response. We investigated the spread and control of COVID-19 using a unique data set including case reports, human movement and public health interventions. The Wuhan shutdown was associated with the delayed arrival of COVID-19 in other cities by 2.91 days (95%CI: 2.54-3.29). Cities that implemented control measures pre-emptively reported

fewer cases, on average, in the first week of their outbreaks (13.0; 7.1-18.8) compared with cities that started control later (20.6; 14.5-26.8). Suspending intra-city public transport, closing entertainment venues and banning public gatherings were associated with reductions in case incidence. The national emergency response appears to have delayed the growth and limited the size of the COVID-19 epidemic in China, averting hundreds of thousands of cases by 19 February (day 50).]

WANG C. Jason, NG Chun Y., BROOK Robert H.,

°2020 [pdf]

Response to COVID-19 in Taiwan *Big Data Analytics, New Technology, and Proactive Testing*,

in: JAMA, March 3, 2020.

<<http://jamanetwork.com/article.aspx?doi=10.1001/jama.2020.3151>>

[Taiwan's Outcomes so Far (as of February 24) / Interim Outcomes / The CECC has communicated to the public in a clear and compassionate manner. Based on a poll of 1079 randomly selected people conducted by the Taiwan Public Opinion Foundation on February 17 and 18, the minister of health and welfare received approval ratings of more than 80% for his handling of the crisis, and the president and the premier received an overall approval rating of close to 70%. As of February 24, Taiwan has 30 cases of COVID-19. These cases represent the 10th-highest case number among countries affected thus far, but far fewer than the initial models predicting that Taiwan would have the second-highest importation risk.

Challenges / First, real-time public communications were mostly in Mandarin Chinese and sign language. Other than the Taiwan CDC website, there was not enough communication in different languages to non-Taiwanese citizens traveling or residing in Taiwan. Second, while its attention was focused on air travel, Taiwan permitted the docking of the Diamond Princess cruise ship and allowed passengers to disembark in Keelung, near New Taipei City, on January 31, before the ship left for Japan. The ship was subsequently found to have numerous confirmed infections onboard. This created a temporary public panic with concern about community spread. The government published the 50 locations where the cruise ship travelers may have visited and asked citizens who may have been in contact with the tour group to conduct symptom monitoring and self-quarantine if necessary. None were confirmed to have COVID-19 after 14 days had passed. Third, whether the intensive nature of these policies can be maintained until the end of the epidemic and continue to be well received by the public is unclear.

Conclusions / Taiwan's government learned from its 2003 SARS experience and established a public health response mechanism for enabling rapid actions for the next crisis. Well-trained and experienced teams of officials were quick to recognize the crisis and activated emergency management structures to address the emerging outbreak.

In a crisis, governments often make difficult decisions under uncertainty and time constraints. These decisions must be both culturally appropriate and sensitive to the population. Through early recognition of the crisis, daily briefings to the public, and simple health messaging, the government was able to reassure the public by delivering timely, accurate, and transparent information regarding the evolving epidemic. Taiwan is an example of how a society can respond quickly to a crisis and protect the interests of its citizens.]

press:

• FRIEBE 2020.

WANG Wenjun, WANG Yikai, ZHANG Xin, LI Yaping, JIA Xiaoli, DANG Shuangshuo

°2020 [pdf]

WeChat, a Chinese social media, may early detect the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak in 2019,

in: medRxiv, February 26, 2020, supplementary material.

<<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.24.20026682>>

[Abstract: We plotted daily data on the frequencies of keywords related to severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) from WeChat, a Chinese social media. Using 'Feidian', Chinese abbreviation for SARS, may detect the SARS-CoV-2 outbreak in 2019 two weeks earlier. WeChat offered a new approach to early detect disease outbreaks.]

WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION (WHO)

*2020a

Pneumonia of unknown cause – China.

Geneva: WHO.

<<https://www.who.int/csr/don/05-january-2020-pneumonia-of-unknown-cause-china/en/>>

*2020b

Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) situation report 9.

Geneva: WHO.

https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/situation-reports/20200129-sitrep-9-ncov-v2.pdf?sfvrsn=e2c8915_2

*^o2020c [pdf]

Report of the WHO-China Joint Mission on Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19).

Geneva: WHO. [40p., 6 figs., 1 table.]

<https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/who-china-joint-mission-on-covid-19-final-report.pdf>

[19-20: “2. **China’s uncompromising and rigorous use of non-pharmaceutical measures to contain transmission of the COVID-19 virus in multiple settings provides vital lessons for the global response. This rather unique and unprecedented public health response in China reversed the escalating cases in both Hubei, where there has been widespread community transmission, and in the importation provinces, where family clusters appear to have driven the outbreak.**

Although the timing of the outbreak in China has been relatively similar across the country, transmission chains were established in a wide diversity of settings, from megacities in the north and south of the country, to remote communities. However, the rapid adaptation and tailoring of China’s strategy demonstrated that containment can be adapted and successfully operationalized in a wide range of settings. China’s experience strongly supports the efficacy and effectiveness of anchoring COVID-19 readiness and rapid response plans in a thorough assessment of local risks and of utilizing a differentiated risk-based containment strategy to manage the outbreak in areas with no cases vs. sporadic cases vs. clusters of cases vs. community-level transmission. Such a strategy is essential for ensuring a sustainable approach while minimizing the socio-economic impact.

3. **Much of the global community is not yet ready, in mindset and materially, to implement the measures that have been employed to contain COVID-19 in China. These are the only measures that are currently proven to interrupt or minimize transmission chains in humans. Fundamental to these measures is extremely proactive surveillance to immediately detect cases, very rapid diagnosis and immediate case isolation, rigorous tracking and quarantine of close contacts, and an exceptionally high degree of population understanding and acceptance of these measures.**

Achieving the high quality of implementation needed to be successful with such measures requires an unusual and unprecedented speed of decision-making by top leaders, operational thoroughness by public health systems, and engagement of society. Given the damage that can be caused by uncontrolled, community-level transmission of this virus, such an approach is warranted to save lives and to gain the weeks and months needed for the testing of therapeutics and vaccine development. Furthermore, as the majority of new cases outside of China are currently occurring in high and middleincome countries, a rigorous commitment to slowing transmission in such settings with non-pharmaceutical measures is vital to achieving a second line of defense to protect low income countries that have weaker health systems and coping capacities. The time that can be gained through the full application of these measures – even if just days or weeks – can be invaluable in ultimately reducing COVID-19 illness and deaths. This is apparent in the huge increase in knowledge, approaches and even tools that has taken place in just the 7 weeks since this virus was discovered through the rapid scientific work that has been done in China.” –

• Members of WHO-China Joint Mission:

Bruce AYLWARD Team Lead WHO-China Joint Mission on COVID-19, Senior Advisor to the Director-General, World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland

Wannian LIANG Team Lead WHO-China Joint Mission on COVID-19, Head of Expert Panel, National Health Commission

Xiaoping DONG Director and Researcher, Center for Global Public Health, Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention

Tim ECKMANNS Head of Unit, Healthcare-associated Infections, Surveillance of Antibiotic Resistance and Consumption, Robert Koch Institute, Berlin, Germany

Dale FISHER Professor of Medicine, Yong Loo Lin School of Medicine, National University of Singapore, Singapore, Singapore

Chikwe IHEKWEAZU Director General, Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, Abuja, Nigeria

Clifford LANE Clinical Director, National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, US National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, United States

Jong-Koo LEE Professor of Family Medicine, Seoul National University College of Medicine, Seoul, Republic of Korea

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 Natalia PSHENICHNAYA Head of International Department and Consultant, Center of Infectious Diseases, National Medical Research Center of Phthisiopulmonology and Infectious Diseases, Moscow, Russia
 Aleksandr SEMENOV Deputy Director, Saint Petersburg Pasteur Institute, Saint Petersburg, Russia
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 Maria VAN KERKHOVE Head of Unit, Emerging Diseases & Zoonoses, Global Infectious Hazard Preparedness, World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland
 Bin WANG Deputy Team Leader, Deputy Director General, Disease Prevention and Control Bureau, National Health Commission
 Guangfa WANG Director, Department of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine, Peking University First Hospital
 Fan WU Vice Dean, Shanghai Medical College, Fudan University
 Zhongze WU Director, Compliance and Enforcement Division, Department of Wildlife Conservation, National Forestry and Grassland Administration
 Zunyou WU Chief Epidemiologist, Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention
 Jun XING Head of Unit, Country Capacity for International Health Regulations, Health Security Preparedness, World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland
 Kwok-Yung YUEN Chair Professor and Co-Director of State Key Laboratory of Emerging Infectious Diseases, Department of Microbiology, The University of Hong Kong
 Weigong ZHOU Medical Officer, Influenza Division, National Center for Immunization and Respiratory Diseases, US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, United States
 Yong ZHANG Assistant Director and Researcher, National Institute for Viral Disease Control and prevention, Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention.
 Lei ZHOU Chief and Researcher, Branch for Emerging Infectious Disease, Public Health Emergency Center, Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention.]

WU Joseph T., LEUNG Kathy, LEUNG Gabriel M.

©2020 [pdf]

Nowcasting and forecasting the potential domestic and international spread of the 2019-nCoV outbreak originating in Wuhan, China: a modelling study, in: *The Lancet* January 31, 2020, online first. [9p., 4 figs., 2 tables; supplementary appendix 6p., tables S1-S2, definition of *chunyun*, mobility data.]
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30260-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30260-9)

[Summary: Background: Since Dec 31, 2019, the Chinese city of Wuhan has reported an outbreak of atypical pneumonia caused by the 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). Cases have been exported to other Chinese cities, as well as internationally, threatening to trigger a global outbreak. Here, we provide an estimate of the size of the epidemic in Wuhan on the basis of the number of cases exported from Wuhan to cities outside mainland China and forecast the extent of the domestic and global public health risks of epidemics, accounting for social and non-pharmaceutical prevention interventions.

Methods: We used data from Dec 31, 2019, to Jan 28, 2020, on the number of cases exported from Wuhan internationally (known days of symptom onset from Dec 25, 2019, to Jan 19, 2020) to infer the number of infections in Wuhan from Dec 1, 2019, to Jan 25, 2020. Cases exported domestically were then estimated. We forecasted the national and global spread of 2019-nCoV, accounting for the effect of the metropolitan-wide quarantine of Wuhan and surrounding cities, which began Jan 23–24, 2020. We used data on monthly flight bookings from the Official Aviation Guide and data on human mobility across more than 300 prefecture-level cities in mainland China from the Tencent database. Data on confirmed cases were obtained from the reports published by the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention. Serial interval estimates were based on previous studies of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV). A susceptible-exposed-infectious-recovered metapopulation model was used to simulate the epidemics across all major cities in China. The basic reproductive number was estimated using Markov Chain Monte Carlo methods and presented using the resulting posterior mean and 95% credible interval (CrI).

Findings: In our baseline scenario, we estimated that the basic reproductive number for 2019-nCoV was 2.68 (95% CrI 2.47–2.86) and that 75 815 individuals (95% CrI 37 304–130 330) have been infected in Wuhan as of Jan 25, 2020. The epidemic doubling time was 6.4 days (95% CrI 5.8–7.1). We estimated that in the baseline scenario, Chongqing, Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou, and Shenzhen had imported 461 (95% CrI 227–805), 113 (57–193), 98 (49–168), 111 (56–191), and 80 (40–139) infections from Wuhan, respectively. If the transmissibility of 2019-nCoV were similar everywhere domestically and over time, we inferred that epidemics

are already growing exponentially in multiple major cities of China with a lag time behind the Wuhan outbreak of about 1–2 weeks.

Interpretation: Given that 2019-nCoV is no longer contained within Wuhan, other major Chinese cities are probably sustaining localised outbreaks. Large cities overseas with close transport links to China could also become outbreak epicentres, unless substantial public health interventions at both the population and personal levels are implemented immediately. Independent self-sustaining outbreaks in major cities globally could become inevitable because of substantial exportation of presymptomatic cases and in the absence of large-scale public health interventions. Preparedness plans and mitigation interventions should be readied for quick deployment globally. Funding: Health and Medical Research Fund (Hong Kong, China).

Research in context: Evidence before this study: In central China, Wuhan is investigating an outbreak of atypical pneumonia caused by the zoonotic 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). Few data and details are currently available. Two other novel coronaviruses (CoVs) have emerged as major global epidemics in recent decades; in 2002, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) spread to 37 countries and caused more than 8000 cases and almost 800 deaths, and in 2012, Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) spread to 27 countries, causing 2494 cases and 858 deaths worldwide to date. These CoVs are both zoonotic and have low potential for sustained community transmission. However, larger clusters involving superspreading events were observed for SARS in 2003 and MERS in 2014–17. As of Jan 25, 2020, the scale and geographical extent of the 2019-nCoV outbreak both within and outside mainland China are highly uncertain. National and global spread of this disease is particularly concerning given that *chunyun*, a 40-day period with extremely high air and train traffic across China because of the lunar new year Spring Festival, began on Jan 10, 2020. We searched PubMed and preprint archives for articles published up to Jan 25, 2020, that contained information about the Wuhan outbreak using the terms “coronavirus”, “CoV”, “2019-nCoV”, “Wuhan”, “transmission”, “China”, “superspreading”, and “Chinese New Year”. We found six studies that reported the relative risks of case exportation from Wuhan to areas outside mainland China.

Added value of this study: In the absence of a robust and complete line list for characterising the epidemiology of this novel pathogen, we inferred the outbreak size of 2019-nCoV in Wuhan from the number of confirmed cases that have been exported to cities outside mainland China. We used this outbreak size estimate to project the number of cases that have been exported to other Chinese cities. We forecasted the spread of 2019-nCoV both within and outside of mainland China.

Implications of all the available evidence: Preparedness plans should be readied for quick deployment worldwide, especially in cities with close travel links with Wuhan and other major Chinese cities.]

WU Zunyou, MCGOOGAN Jennifer M.

°2020 [pdf]

Characteristics of and Important Lessons From the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Outbreak in China. Summary of a Report of 72 314 Cases From the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention, (Viewpoint)

in: JAMA, February 24, 2020. [4p., 2 figs.] doi:10.1001/jama.2020.2648.

<https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2762130>

[(intro) The Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention recently published the largest case series to date of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in mainland China (72 314 cases, updated through February 11, 2020).¹ This Viewpoint summarizes key findings from this report and discusses emerging understanding of and lessons from the COVID-19 epidemic.]

https://cdn.jamanetwork.com/ama/content_public/journal/jama/0/jvp200028f1.png

https://cdn.jamanetwork.com/ama/content_public/journal/jama/0/jvp200028f2.png

ZHAO Shi, MUSA Salihu S., LIN Qianying, RAN Jinjun, YANG Guangpu, WANG Weiming, LOU Yijun, YANG Lin, GAO Daozhou, HE Daihai & WANG Maggie H.
 °2020 [pdf]

Estimating the Unreported Number of Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Cases in China in the First Half of January 2020: A Data-Driven Modelling Analysis of the Early Outbreak,

in: *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 2020, 9, 388; [6p.; 1 fig.]

<https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm9020388>

[Abstract: Background: In December 2019, an outbreak of respiratory illness caused by a novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) emerged in Wuhan, China and has swiftly spread to other parts of China and a number of foreign countries. The 2019-nCoV cases might have been under-reported roughly from 1 to 15 January 2020, and thus we estimated the number of unreported

cases and the basic reproduction number, R_0 , of 2019-nCoV. Methods: We modelled the epidemic curve of 2019-nCoV cases, in mainland China from 1 December 2019 to 24 January 2020 through the exponential growth. The number of unreported cases was determined by the maximum likelihood estimation. We used the serial intervals (SI) of infection caused by two other well-known coronaviruses (CoV), Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) CoVs, as approximations of the unknown SI for 2019-nCoV to estimate R_0 . Results: We confirmed that the initial growth phase followed an exponential growth pattern. The under-reporting was likely to have resulted in 469 (95% CI: 403–540) unreported cases from 1 to 15 January 2020. The reporting rate after 17 January 2020 was likely to have increased 21-fold (95% CI: 18–25) in comparison to the situation from 1 to 17 January 2020 on average. We estimated the R_0 of 2019-nCoV at 2.56 (95% CI: 2.49–2.63). Conclusion: The under-reporting was likely to have occurred during the first half of January 2020 and should be considered in future investigation. Keywords: novel coronavirus; outbreak; modelling; underreporting; reproduction number; China.]

Clinical disease • pathology • pathophysiology

CHANG De, MO Guoxin, YUAN Xin, TAO Yi, PENG Xiaohua, WANG Fusheng, XIE Lixin, SHARMA Lokesh, DELA CRUZ Charles S., QIN Enqiang

2020

Time Kinetics of Viral Clearance and Resolution of Symptoms in Novel Coronavirus Infection,

in: American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine

2020; just accepted. <<http://dx.doi.org/10.1164/rccm.202003-0524LE>>

press:

• AMERICAN THORACIC SOCIETY 2020: *Some COVID-19 patients still have coronavirus after symptoms disappear*, in: ScienceDaily, 27 March 2020.

<<https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2020/03/200327091234.htm>>

CHAVEZ Summer, LONG Brit, KOYFMAN Alex, LIANG Stephen Y.

°2020 [pdf]

Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19): A primer for emergency physicians,

in: The American Journal of Emergency Medicine, 24 March 2020,

In Press, Corrected Proof. [10p., 5 figs., 4 tables, 94 refs.]

<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajem.2020.03.036>>

[Abstract: Introduction: Rapid worldwide spread of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) has resulted in a global pandemic.

Objective: This review article provides emergency physicians with an overview of the most current understanding of COVID-19 and recommendations on the evaluation and management of patients with suspected COVID-19.

Discussion: Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), the virus responsible for causing COVID-19, is primarily transmitted from person-to-person through close contact (approximately 6 ft) by respiratory droplets. Symptoms of COVID-19 are similar to other viral upper respiratory illnesses. Three major trajectories include mild disease with upper respiratory symptoms, non-severe pneumonia, and severe pneumonia complicated by acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). Emergency physicians should focus on identifying patients at risk, isolating suspected patients, and informing hospital infection prevention and public health authorities. Patients with suspected COVID-19 should be asked to wear a face-mask. Respiratory etiquette, hand washing, and personal protective equipment are recommended for all healthcare personnel caring for suspected cases. Disposition depends on patient symptoms, hemodynamic status, and patient ability to self-quarantine.

Conclusion: This narrative review provides clinicians with an updated approach to the evaluation and management of patients presenting to the emergency department with suspected COVID-19. – Keywords: Coronavirus Disease; COVID-19; Infectious disease; Pulmonary.]

Fig. 2. This electron microscope image depicts the spikes on the outer surface of the COVID-19 in addition to several protein particles. Eckert A, Higgins D, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. ID# 23313; 2020.

<<https://phil.cdc.gov/Details.aspx?pid=23313>>. Accessed February 18, 2020.

CHEN Nanshan, ZHOU Min, DONG Xuan, QU Jieming, GONG Fengyun, HAN Yang, QIU Yang, WANG Jingli, LIU Ying, WEI Yuan, XIA Jia'an, YU Ting, ZHANG Xinxin, ZHANG Li

°2020 [pdf]

Epidemiological and clinical characteristics of 99 cases of 2019 novel coronavirus

pneumonia in Wuhan, China: a descriptive study,

in: *The Lancet*, January 29, 2020. [7p.; 1 fig.; 3 tables.]

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30211-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30211-7)

[Summary: Background: In December, 2019, a pneumonia associated with the 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) emerged in Wuhan, China. We aimed to further clarify the epidemiological and clinical characteristics of 2019-nCoV pneumonia.

Methods: In this retrospective, single-centre study, we included all confirmed cases of 2019-nCoV in Wuhan Jinyintan Hospital from Jan 1 to Jan 20, 2020. Cases were confirmed by real-time RT-PCR and were analysed for epidemiological, demographic, clinical, and radiological features and laboratory data. Outcomes were followed up until Jan 25, 2020.

Findings: Of the 99 patients with 2019-nCoV pneumonia, 49 (49%) had a history of exposure to the Huanan seafood market. The average age of the patients was 55.5 years (SD 13.1), including 67 men and 32 women. 2019-nCoV was detected in all patients by real-time RT-PCR. 50 (51%) patients had chronic diseases. Patients had clinical manifestations of fever (82 [83%] patients), cough (81 [82%] patients), shortness of breath (31 [31%] patients), muscle ache (11 [11%] patients), confusion (nine [9%] patients), headache (eight [8%] patients), sore throat (five [5%] patients), rhinorrhoea (four [4%] patients), chest pain (two [2%] patients), diarrhoea (two [2%] patients), and nausea and vomiting (one [1%] patient). According to imaging examination, 74 (75%) patients showed bilateral pneumonia, 14 (14%) patients showed multiple mottling and ground-glass opacity, and one (1%) patient had pneumothorax. 17 (17%) patients developed acute respiratory distress syndrome and, among them, 11 (11%) patients worsened in a short period of time and died of multiple organ failure.

Interpretation: The 2019-nCoV infection was of clustering onset, is more likely to affect older males with comorbidities, and can result in severe and even fatal respiratory diseases such as acute respiratory distress syndrome. In general, characteristics of patients who died were in line with the MuLBSTA score, an early warning model for predicting mortality in viral pneumonia. Further investigation is needed to explore the applicability of the MuLBSTA score in predicting the risk of mortality in 2019-nCoV infection.]

CORMAN V., BLEICKER T., BRÜNINK S, *et al.*

2020

Diagnostic detection of Wuhan coronavirus 2019 by real-time RT-PCR.

Geneva: World Health Organization, January 13, 2020.

<https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/wuhan-virus-assay-v1991527e5122341d99287a1b17c111902.pdf>

GUAN Wei-jie, NI Zheng-yi, HU Yu, LIANG Wen-hua, OU Chun-quan, HE Jian-xing, LIU Lei, SHAN Hong, LEI Chun-liang, HUI David SC, DU Bin, LI Lan-juan, ZENG Guang, YUEN Kowk-Yung, CHEN Ru-chong, TANG Chun-li, WANG Tao, CHEN Ping-yan, XIANG Jie, LI Shi-yue, WANG Jin-lin, LIANG Zi-jing, PENG Yi-xiang, WEI Li, LIU Yong, HU Ya-hua, PENG Peng, WANG Jian-ming, LIU Ji-yang, CHEN Zhong, LI Gang, ZHENG Zhi-jian, QIU Shao-qin, LUO Jie, YE Chang-jiang, ZHU Shao-yong, ZHONG Nan-shan

°2020 [pdf]

Clinical characteristics of 2019 novel coronavirus infection in China,

in: medRxiv 2020.02.06.20020974.

[30p., 2 figs., 3 tables; Supplementary text; Figure E1; Figure E2; patient number in individual hospital; ICMJE forms from all authors.]

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.06.20020974>

This article is a preprint and has not been peer-reviewed [what does this mean?]. It reports new medical research that has yet to be evaluated and so should not be used to guide clinical practice.

[Abstract: Background: Since December 2019, acute respiratory disease (ARD) due to 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) emerged in Wuhan city and rapidly spread throughout China. We sought to delineate the clinical characteristics of these cases. Methods: We extracted the data on 1,099 patients with laboratory-confirmed 2019-nCoV ARD from 552 hospitals in 31 provinces/provincial municipalities through January 29th, 2020. Results: The median age was 47.0 years, and 41.90% were females. Only 1.18% of patients had a direct contact with wildlife, whereas 31.30% had been to Wuhan and 71.80% had contacted with people from Wuhan. Fever (87.9%) and cough (67.7%) were the most common symptoms. Diarrhea is uncommon. The median incubation period was 3.0 days (range, 0 to 24.0 days). On admission, ground-glass opacity was the typical radiological finding on chest computed tomography (50.00%). Significantly more severe cases were diagnosed by symptoms plus reverse-transcriptase polymerase-chain-reaction without abnormal radiological findings than non-severe cases (23.87% vs. 5.20%, P<0.001). Lymphopenia was observed in 82.1% of patients. 55 patients (5.00%) were

admitted to intensive care unit and 15 (1.36%) succumbed. Severe pneumonia was independently associated with either the admission to intensive care unit, mechanical ventilation, or death in multivariate competing-risk model (sub-distribution hazards ratio, 9.80; 95% confidence interval, 4.06 to 23.67). Conclusions: The 2019-nCoV epidemic spreads rapidly by human-to-human transmission. Normal radiologic findings are present among some patients with 2019-nCoV infection. The disease severity (including oxygen saturation, respiratory rate, blood leukocyte/lymphocyte count and chest X-ray/CT manifestations) predict poor clinical outcomes.]

HUANG Chaolin, WANG Yeming, LI Xingwang, REN Lili, ZHAO Jianping, HU Yi, ZHANG Li, FAN Guohui, XU Jiuyang, GU Xiaoying, CHENG Zhenshun, YU Ting, XIA Jiaan, WEI Yuan, WU Wenjuan, XIE Xuelei, YIN Wen, LI Hui, LIU Min, XIAO Yan, GAO Hong, GUO Li, XIE Jungang, WANG Guangfa, JIANG Rongmeng, GAO Zhancheng, JIN Qi, WANG Jianwei, CAO Bin

°2020 [pdf]

Clinical features of patients infected with 2019 novel coronavirus in Wuhan, China,

in: *The Lancet*, January 24, 2020.

<[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30183-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30183-5)>

[Summary: Background: A recent cluster of pneumonia cases in Wuhan, China, was caused by a novel betacoronavirus, the 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). We report the epidemiological, clinical, laboratory, and radiological characteristics and treatment and clinical outcomes of these patients.

Methods: All patients with suspected 2019-nCoV were admitted to a designated hospital in Wuhan. We prospectively collected and analysed data on patients with laboratory-confirmed 2019-nCoV infection by real-time RT-PCR and next-generation sequencing. Data were obtained with standardised data collection forms shared by the International Severe Acute Respiratory and Emerging Infection Consortium from electronic medical records. Researchers also directly communicated with patients or their families to ascertain epidemiological and symptom data. Outcomes were also compared between patients who had been admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) and those who had not.

Findings: By Jan 2, 2020, 41 admitted hospital patients had been identified as having laboratory-confirmed 2019-nCoV infection. Most of the infected patients were men (30 [73%] of 41); less than half had underlying diseases (13 [32%]), including diabetes (eight [20%]), hypertension (six [15%]), and cardiovascular disease (six [15%]). Median age was 49.0 years (IQR 41.0–58.0). 27 (66%) of 41 patients had been exposed to Huanan seafood market. One family cluster was found. Common symptoms at onset of illness were fever (40 [98%] of 41 patients), cough (31 [76%]), and myalgia or fatigue (18 [44%]); less common symptoms were sputum production (11 [28%] of 39), headache (three [8%] of 38), haemoptysis (two [5%] of 39), and diarrhoea (one [3%] of 38). Dyspnoea developed in 22 (55%) of 40 patients (median time from illness onset to dyspnoea 8.0 days [IQR 5.0–13.0]). 26 (63%) of 41 patients had lymphopenia. All 41 patients had pneumonia with abnormal findings on chest CT. Complications included acute respiratory distress syndrome (12 [29%]), RNAemia (six [15%]), acute cardiac injury (five [12%]) and secondary infection (four [10%]). 13 (32%) patients were admitted to an ICU and six (15%) died. Compared with non-ICU patients, ICU patients had higher plasma levels of IL2, IL7, IL10, GSCF, IP10, MCP1, MIP1A, and TNF α .

Interpretation: The 2019-nCoV infection caused clusters of severe respiratory illness similar to severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus and was associated with ICU admission and high mortality. Major gaps in our knowledge of the origin, epidemiology, duration of human transmission, and clinical spectrum of disease need fulfilment by future studies.

Funding: Ministry of Science and Technology, Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences, National Natural Science Foundation of China, and Beijing Municipal Science and Technology Commission.]

Online Comments:

• HEYMANN David L. °2020 [pdf]: *Data sharing and outbreaks: best practice exemplified.*

January 24, 2020 [2p.] <[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30184-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30184-7)>

• WANG Chen, HORBY Peter W., HAYDEN Frederick G., GAO George F. °2020

[pdf]: *A novel coronavirus outbreak of global health concern.* January 24, 2020 [4p.]

<[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30185-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30185-9)>

Discussion:

COHEN Jon °2020 [pdf]: *Wuhan seafood market may not be source of novel virus spreading globally,* in: *Science* Jan. 26, 2020, 11:25 PM. doi:10.1126/science.abb0611.

<<https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/01/wuhan-seafood-market-may-not-be-source-novel-virus-spreading-globally>>

JOSEPH Andrew

°2020

Disease caused by the novel coronavirus officially has a name: Covid-19,
in: STAT February 11, 2020
<<https://www.statnews.com/2020/02/11/disease-caused-by-the-novel-coronavirus-has-name-covid-19/>>

LI Yan-chao, BAI Wan-Zhu, HASHIKAWA Tsutomu

°2020 [pdf]

The neuroinvasive potential of SARS-CoV2 may be at least partially responsible for the respiratory failure of COVID-19 patients,

in: Journal of Medical Virology, 27 February 2020: 1-4.

<<https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.25728>>

[Correction added on March 17, 2020 after first online publication: Manuscript has been revised with author's latest changes. 43 refs.]

[(neuroinvasive potential of SARS-CoV-2)]

Abstract: Following the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), another highly pathogenic coronavirus named SARS-CoV-2 (previously known as 2019-nCoV) emerged in December 2019 in Wuhan, China, and rapidly spreads around the world. This virus shares highly homological sequence with SARS-CoV, and causes acute, highly lethal pneumonia coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) with clinical symptoms similar to those reported for SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV. The most characteristic symptom of patients with COVID-19 is respiratory distress, and most of the patients admitted to the intensive care could not breathe spontaneously. Additionally, some patients with COVID-19 also showed neurologic signs, such as headache, nausea, and vomiting. Increasing evidence shows that coronaviruses are not always confined to the respiratory tract and that they may also invade the central nervous system inducing neurological diseases. The infection of SARS-CoV has been reported in the brains from both patients and experimental animals, where the brainstem was heavily infected. Furthermore, some coronaviruses have been demonstrated able to spread via a synapse-connected route to the medullary cardiorespiratory center from the mechanoreceptors and chemoreceptors in the lung and lower respiratory airways. Considering the high similarity between SARS-CoV and SARS-CoV2, it remains to make clear whether the potential invasion of SARS-CoV2 is partially responsible for the acute respiratory failure of patients with COVID-19. Awareness of this may have a guiding significance for the prevention and treatment of the SARS-CoV-2-induced respiratory failure.

Research Highlights

- SARS-CoV2 causes epidemic pneumonia characterized by acute respiratory distress.
- This novel coronavirus is similar to SARS-CoV in sequence, pathogenesis, and cellular entry.
- Some coronaviruses can invade brainstem via a synapse-connected route from the lung and airways.
- The potential invasion of SARS-CoV2 may be one reason for the acute respiratory failure. Awareness of this will have guiding significance for the prevention and treatment.

Keywords: cell susceptibility, coronavirus, dissemination, nervous system.]

LIU Jia, ZHENG Xin, TONG Qiaoxia, LI Wei, WANG Baoju, SUTTER Kathrin, TRILLING Mirko, LU Mengji, DITTMER Ulf, YANG Dongliang

°2020 [pdf]

Overlapping and discrete aspects of the pathology and pathogenesis of the emerging human pathogenic coronaviruses SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and 2019-nCoV,

in: Journal of Medical Virology, early view.

First published: 13 February 2020. <<https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.25709>>

[Abstract: First reported from Wuhan, The People's Republic of China, on 31 December 2019, the ongoing outbreak of a novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) causes great global concerns. Based on the advice of the International Health Regulations Emergency Committee and the fact that to date 24 other countries also reported cases, the WHO Director-General declared that the outbreak of 2019-nCoV constitutes a Public Health Emergency of International Concern on 30 January 2020. Together with the other two highly pathogenic coronaviruses, the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), 2019-nCoV and other yet to be identified coronaviruses pose a global threat to public health. In this mini-review, we provide a brief introduction to the pathology and pathogenesis of SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV and extrapolate this knowledge to the newly identified 2019-nCoV.

Highlights

- The pathology of SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV is introduced.
- The pathogenesis of SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV is introduced.
- The general features of 2019-nCoV and the disease caused by it are described.]

REN Li-Li, WANG Ye-Ming, WU Zhi-Qiang, XIANG Zi-Chun, GUO Li, XU Teng, JIANG Yong-Zhong, XIONG Yan, LI Yong-Jun, LI Xing-Wang, LI Hui, FAN Guo-Hui, GU Xiao-Ying, XIAO Yan, GAO Hong, XU Jiu-Yang, YANG Fan, WANG Xin-Ming, WU Chao, CHEN Lan, LIU Yi-Wei, LIU Bo, YANG Jian, WANG Xiao-Rui, DONG Jie, LI Li, HUANG Chao-Lin, ZHAO Jian-Ping, HU Yi, CHENG Zhen-Shun, LIU Lin-Lin, QIAN Zhao-Hui, QIN Chuan, JIN Qi, CAO Bin, WANG Jian-Wei; Section Editors: HAO Xiu-Yuan, WEI Pei-Fang

©2020 [pdf]

Identification of a novel coronavirus causing severe pneumonia in human: a descriptive study,

in: Chinese Medical Journal: February 11, 2020 Ahead of Print.

doi: 10.1097/CM9.0000000000000722. [10p., 4 figs., 2 tables.]

<https://journals.lww.com/cmj/Abstract/publishahead/Identification_of_a_novel_coronavirus_causing.99423.aspx>

[Abstract: Background: Human infections with zoonotic coronaviruses (CoVs), including severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS)-CoV and Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS)-CoV, have raised great public health concern globally. Here, we report a novel bat-origin CoV causing severe and fatal pneumonia in humans.

Methods: We collected clinical data and bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) specimens from five patients with severe pneumonia from Jin Yin-tan Hospital of Wuhan, Hubei province, China. Nucleic acids of the BAL were extracted and subjected to next-generation sequencing. Virus isolation was carried out, and maximum-likelihood phylogenetic trees were constructed.

Results: Five patients hospitalized from December 18 to December 29, 2019 presented with fever, cough, and dyspnea accompanied by complications of acute respiratory distress syndrome. Chest radiography revealed diffuse opacities and consolidation. One of these patients died. Sequence results revealed the presence of a previously unknown β -CoV strain in all five patients, with 99.8% to 99.9% nucleotide identities among the isolates. These isolates showed 79.0% nucleotide identity with the sequence of SARS-CoV (GenBank NC_004718) and 51.8% identity with the sequence of MERS-CoV (GenBank NC_019843). The virus is phylogenetically closest to a bat SARS-like CoV (SL-ZC45, GenBank MG772933) with 87.6% to 87.7% nucleotide identity, but is in a separate clade. Moreover, these viruses have a single intact open reading frame gene 8, as a further indicator of bat-origin CoVs. However, the amino acid sequence of the tentative receptor-binding domain resembles that of SARS-CoV, indicating that these viruses might use the same receptor.

Conclusion: A novel bat-borne CoV was identified that is associated with severe and fatal respiratory disease in humans.

Keywords: Bat-origin; Coronavirus; Zoonotic transmission; Pneumonia; Etiology; Next-generation sequencing.]

Figure 4: Computed tomographic chest radiographs of Patient 2, obtained on day 10 from illness onset at aortic arch (A) and pulmonary vein (B) scan demonstrating bilateral ground-glass opacity and consolidation, and Patient 5 on day 12 (C) and 13 (D) after illness onset demonstrating white lungs.

SALEHI Sana, ABEDI Aidin, BALAKRISHNAN Sudheer, GHOLAMREZANEZHAD Ali
©2020 [2 pdf]

Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): A Systematic Review of Imaging Findings in 919 Patients,

in: *AJR American Journal of Roentgenology*: 1-7, 2 figs., 2 tables;
supplemental Table S1: Characteristics and CT Findings From
30 Studies of Patients With COVID-19.

2020 Mar 14 [Online ahead of print] <<https://doi.org/10.2214/AJR.20.23034>>
<<https://www.ajronline.org/doi/full/10.2214/AJR.20.23034>>

[Abstract: Objective. Available information on CT features of the 2019 novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is scattered in different publications, and a cohesive literature review has yet to be compiled. Materials and Methods. This article includes a systematic literature search of PubMed, Embase (Elsevier), Google Scholar, and the World Health Organization database. Results. Known features of COVID-19 on initial CT include bilateral multilobar ground-glass opacification (GGO) with a peripheral or posterior distribution, mainly in the lower lobes and less frequently within the right middle lobe. Atypical initial imaging presentation of consolidative opacities superimposed on GGO may be found in a smaller number of cases, mainly in the elderly population. Septal thickening, bronchiectasis, pleural thickening, and subpleural involvement are some of the less common findings, mainly in the later stages of the disease. Pleural effusion, pericardial effusion, lymphadenopathy, cavitation, CT halo sign, and pneumothorax are uncommon but may be seen with disease progression. Follow-up CT in the intermediate stage of disease shows an increase in the number and size of GGOs and progressive transformation of GGO into multifocal consolidative opacities, septal thickening, and development of a crazy paving pattern, with the greatest severity of CT findings visible around day 10 after the symptom onset. Acute respiratory distress syndrome is the most common indication for transferring patients with COVID-19 to the ICU and the major cause of death in this patient population. Imaging patterns corresponding to clinical improvement usually occur after week 2 of the disease and include gradual resolution of consolidative opacities and decrease in the number of lesions and involved lobes. Conclusion. This systematic review of current literature on COVID-19 provides insight into the initial and follow-up CT characteristics of the disease. Keywords: 2019-nCoV; COVID-19; CT scan; coronavirus; influenza; outbreak; pneumonia; radiology; systematic review; viral.]

Fig. 1—79-year-old woman who presented with chest pain, cough, and fever for 3 days. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) had recently been diagnosed in two of her household members. Patient developed acute respiratory distress syndrome within subsequent few days and died 11 days after admission. (Courtesy of Song F, Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center, Shanghai, China)
A and B, CT image (**A**) and chest radiograph (**B**) show ground glass opacification (GGO) on day 1.
C and D, CT image (**C**) and chest radiograph (**D**) obtained on day 4 show GGO has progressed to airspace consolidation.

SCHWARTZ David A. & GRAHAM Ashley L.

°2020 [pdf]

Potential Maternal and Infant Outcomes from Coronavirus 2019-nCoV (SARS-CoV-2) Infecting Pregnant Women: Lessons from SARS, MERS, and Other Human Coronavirus Infections,

in: *Viruses* 2020, 12(2), 194. (Special Issue Pathogenesis of Human and Animal Coronaviruses) [16p., 1 fig., 80 refs.]

<https://doi.org/10.3390/v12020194>

[Abstract: In early December 2019 a cluster of cases of pneumonia of unknown cause was identified in Wuhan, a city of 11 million persons in the People's Republic of China. Further investigation revealed these cases to result from infection with a newly identified coronavirus, initially termed 2019-nCoV and subsequently SARS-CoV-2. The infection moved rapidly through China, spread to Thailand and Japan, extended into adjacent countries through infected persons travelling by air, eventually reaching multiple countries and continents. Similar to such other coronaviruses as those causing the Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), the new coronavirus was reported to spread via natural aerosols from human-to-human. In the early stages of this epidemic the case fatality rate is estimated to be approximately 2%, with the majority of deaths occurring in special populations. Unfortunately, there is limited experience with coronavirus infections during pregnancy, and it now appears certain that pregnant women have become infected during the present 2019-nCoV epidemic. In order to assess the potential of the Wuhan 2019-nCoV to cause maternal, fetal and neonatal morbidity and other poor obstetrical outcomes, this communication reviews the published data addressing the epidemiological and clinical effects of SARS, MERS, and other coronavirus infections on pregnant women and their infants. Recommendations are also made for the consideration of pregnant women in the design, clinical trials, and implementation of future 2019-nCoV vaccines.]

SUN Luna, SUN Zhuoer, WU Lili, ZHU Zhenwen, ZHANG Fan, SHANG Zhilei, JIA Yanpu, GU Jingwen, ZHOU Yaoguang, WANG Yan, LIU Nianqi, LIU Weizhi

°2020 [pdf]

Prevalence and Risk Factors of Acute Posttraumatic Stress Symptoms during

the COVID-19 Outbreak in Wuhan, China,

in: medRxiv, March 10, 2020. [17p., 1 fig., 3 tables.]

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.06.20032425>

[Abstract: Background: A novel coronavirus (SARA-CoV-2) emerged in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. Within a few weeks, the disease caused by SARA-CoV-2, which is named COVID-19, has escalated into an unprecedented ongoing outbreak with frightening speed, becoming a global health emergency. This study aimed to exam the prevalence and risk factors of acute posttraumatic stress symptoms (PTSS) in Chinese people shortly after the massive outbreak of COVID-19. Method: An online anonymous questionnaire survey was conducted in mainland China between 30 January and 3 February, 2020. The survey consisted of two self-administered questionnaires: one was designed to require personal information (gender, age, education background), current location, recent exposure history of Wuhan, the classification of population, and subjective sleep quality; the other was the PTSD Checklist for DSM-5 (PCL-5), which was to assess PTSS referring to the outbreak. Results: A total of 2091 Chinese participated in the current study. The prevalence of PTSS among the public in mainland China 1 month after the COVID-19 outbreak was 4.6%. Multiple linear regression analysis revealed that gender ($p < 0.001$), exposure history of Wuhan ($p = 0.047$), classification of population ($p < 0.001$), and subjective sleep quality ($p < 0.001$) could be regarded as predictor factors for PTSS. Conclusions: The results showed that some Chinese showed acute PTSS during the COVID-19 outbreak. Therefore, comprehensive psychological intervention needs further implementation. Furthermore, females, people who having recent exposure history of Wuhan, those at high risk of infection or with poor sleep quality deserve special attention.]

WANG Dawei, HU Bo, HU Chang, ZHU Fangfang, LIU Xing, ZHANG Jing, WANG Binbin, XIANG Hui, CHENG Zhenshun, XIONG Yong, ZHAO Yan, LI Yirong, WANG Xinghuan, PENG Zhiyong
©2020 [pdf]

Clinical Characteristics of 138 Hospitalized Patients With 2019 Novel Coronavirus-Infected Pneumonia in Wuhan, China,

in: JAMA. February 07, 2020. doi:10.1001/jama.2020.1585.

<https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2761044>

[Key Points: Question: What are the clinical characteristics of hospitalized patients with 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV)-infected pneumonia (NCIP) in Wuhan, China?

Findings: In this single-center case series involving 138 patients with NCIP, 26% of patients required admission to the intensive care unit and 4.3% died. Presumed human-to-human hospital-associated transmission of 2019-nCoV was suspected in 41% of patients.

Meaning: In this case series in Wuhan, China, NCIP was frequently associated with presumed hospital-related transmission, 26% of patients required intensive care unit treatment, and mortality was 4.3%.

Abstract: Importance In December 2019, novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV)-infected pneumonia (NCIP) occurred in Wuhan, China. The number of cases has increased rapidly but information on the clinical characteristics of affected patients is limited.

Objective: To describe the epidemiological and clinical characteristics of NCIP.

Design, Setting, and Participants: Retrospective, single-center case series of the 138 consecutive hospitalized patients with confirmed NCIP at Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University in Wuhan, China, from January 1 to January 28, 2020; final date of follow-up was February 3, 2020. Exposures Documented: NCIP.

Main Outcomes and Measures: Epidemiological, demographic, clinical, laboratory, radiological, and treatment data were collected and analyzed. Outcomes of critically ill patients and noncritically ill patients were compared. Presumed hospital-related transmission was suspected if a cluster of health professionals or hospitalized patients in the same wards became infected and a possible source of infection could be tracked.

Results: Of 138 hospitalized patients with NCIP, the median age was 56 years (interquartile range, 42-68; range, 22-92 years) and 75 (54.3%) were men. Hospital-associated transmission was suspected as the presumed mechanism of infection for affected health professionals (40 [29%]) and hospitalized patients (17 [12.3%]). Common symptoms included fever (136 [98.6%]), fatigue (96 [69.6%]), and dry cough (82 [59.4%]). Lymphopenia (lymphocyte count, $0.8 \times 10^9/L$ [interquartile range {IQR}, 0.6-1.1]) occurred in 97 patients (70.3%), prolonged prothrombin time (13.0 seconds [IQR, 12.3-13.7]) in 80 patients (58%), and elevated lactate dehydrogenase (261 U/L [IQR, 182-403]) in 55 patients (39.9%). Chest computed tomographic scans showed bilateral patchy shadows or ground glass opacity in the lungs of all patients. Most patients received antiviral therapy (oseltamivir, 124 [89.9%]), and many received antibacterial therapy (moxifloxacin, 89 [64.4%]; ceftriaxone, 34 [24.6%]; azithromycin, 25 [18.1%]) and glucocorticoid therapy (62 [44.9%]). Thirty-six patients (26.1%) were transferred to the intensive care unit (ICU) because of complications, including acute respiratory distress syndrome (22 [61.1%]), arrhythmia (16 [44.4%]), and shock (11 [30.6%]). The median time

from first symptom to dyspnea was 5.0 days, to hospital admission was 7.0 days, and to ARDS was 8.0 days. Patients treated in the ICU (n = 36), compared with patients not treated in the ICU (n = 102), were older (median age, 66 years vs 51 years), were more likely to have underlying comorbidities (26 [72.2%] vs 38 [37.3%]), and were more likely to have dyspnea (23 [63.9%] vs 20 [19.6%]), and anorexia (24 [66.7%] vs 31 [30.4%]). Of the 36 cases in the ICU, 4 (11.1%) received high-flow oxygen therapy, 15 (41.7%) received noninvasive ventilation, and 17 (47.2%) received invasive ventilation (4 were switched to extracorporeal membrane oxygenation). As of February 3, 47 patients (34.1%) were discharged and 6 died (overall mortality, 4.3%), but the remaining patients are still hospitalized. Among those discharged alive (n = 47), the median hospital stay was 10 days (IQR, 7.0-14.0).

Conclusions and Relevance: In this single-center case series of 138 hospitalized patients with confirmed NCIP in Wuhan, China, presumed hospital-related transmission of 2019-nCoV was suspected in 41% of patients, 26% of patients received ICU care, and mortality was 4.3%.]

WEI Min, YUAN Jingping, LIU Yu, FU Tao, YU Xue, ZHANG Zhi-Jiang,
 °2020 [pdf] *Novel Coronavirus Infection in Hospitalized Infants Under 1 Year of Age in China, (Letter)*

in: JAMA, February 14, 2020. [2p., 1 table.] doi:10.1001/jama.2020.2131.

<<https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2761659>>

[(intro) Since December 8, 2019, an epidemic of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) has spread rapidly.1 As of February 6, 2020, China reported 31 211 confirmed cases of COVID-19 and 637 fatalities.

Previous studies suggest that COVID-19 is more likely to infect older adult men, particularly those with chronic comorbidities.2-4 Few infections in children have been reported. We identified all infected infants in China [9 cases] and described demographic, epidemiologic, and clinical features.]

Table. Characteristics of 9 Hospitalized Infants Infected With Coronavirus Disease 2019

Characteristic	Patient								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Demographics									
Age	9 mo	11 mo	8 mo	10 mo	7 mo	1 mo 26 d	3 mo	3 mo 22 d	6 mo
Sex	Female	Female	Female	Male	Female	Female	Female	Female	Male
Symptoms at onset	Fever, peaking at 38.8 °C	Mild fever	None	NA	Fever	Runny nose; cough	Cough; sputum production	Fever	NA
Time between admission and diagnosis, d	1	1	3	3	1	1	1	1	2
Epidemiologic history									
No. of family members infected	2	1	5	1	2	2	2	1	1
Linkage to Wuhan	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	NA	No
Treatment									
Intensive unit care	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Mechanical ventilation	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Severe complications	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

Abbreviation: NA, not available.

ZOU Lirong, RUAN Feng, HUANG Mingxing, LIANG Lijun, HUANG Huitao, HONG Zhongsi, YU Jianxiang, KANG Min, SONG Yingchao, XIA Jinyu, GUO Qianfang, SONG Tie, HE Jianfeng, YEN Hui-Ling, PEIRIS Malik, WU Jie
 2020

SARS-CoV-2 Viral Load in Upper Respiratory Specimens of Infected Patients,
 in: New England Journal of Medicine, February 19, 2020.

[Supplementary Appendix.]

<<https://www.nejm.org/doi/10.1056/NEJMc2001737>>

[HARNER Davidson, F1000Prime Recommendation: The aim of this small study was to determine the viral load of SARS-CoV-2 in the upper respiratory tract of patients with COVID-19 in order to determine the relationship between time of onset of symptoms and detection of the virus in oral and nasopharyngeal samples, and to compare the relative yield from these two sites in the upper airway. SARS-CoV-2 viral load was higher soon after symptom onset, higher in patients with more severe symptoms, and became undetectable in nearly all patients by days 15-18 post-symptom onset. The cycle threshold values were generally lower in samples obtained from the nasopharynx relative to the oropharynx (cycle threshold values are inversely related

to viral load). Notably, there was one asymptomatic patient who had been exposed to a family with COVID-19 and who was found to have evidence of SARS-CoV-2 on days 7, 10, and 11 after contact with his infected friends.

This was a small study with just 18 patients so these results need confirmation with a larger cohort of patients in the future.

These preliminary results of the kinetics of SARS-CoV-2 detection in COVID-19 exposed patients provide some important insights into the timing of viral shedding in the upper respiratory tract, the duration of viral shedding and the potential for asymptomatic exposed individuals to shed the virus. In addition, these results suggest that nasopharyngeal samples may be more likely to have higher viral loads than oral mucosal samples. This has implications for patient testing and clinical studies of COVID-19.]

Treatment options • vaccines

ACN
2020

Cuban drug used to tackle COVID-19.

Radio Rebelde, 2020-03-13 11:06:57 / web@radiorebelde.icrt.cu

<<http://www.radiorebelde.cu/english/news/cuban-drug-used-to-tackle-covid-19-20200313/>>

[(full text) Developed in 1986 by a team of researchers from the Center for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology (CIGB), human recombinant Interferon Alfa 2B has benefited thousands of Cuban patients since its introduction into the national health system, and is one of the drugs currently used to combat the new coronavirus COVID-19.

Dr. Eulogio Pimentel, CIGB director general, told Granma newspaper that the product has shown its efficiency and safety in the therapy of viral diseases, such as Hepatitis B and C, Herpes zoster (also known as shingles), HIV-AIDS and Dengue.

It has the property of interfering with viral multiplication within cells and has also been used in the treatment of different types of carcinomas.

The choice of the Chinese medical authorities to use it against COVID-19 is due to the fact that this virus generally decreases the natural production of interferon in the human body and the Cuban drug is capable of supplying said deficiency, strengthening the immune system of patients afflicted by the contagious respiratory ailment that it causes, Pimentel said.

Based on a technology transfer made by CIGB to the Asian country, the Cuba-China joint venture ChangHeber was created in 2003, with headquarters in the city of Changchun. Ten years later a modern plant was inaugurated there, which currently manufactures biotechnological products created in the Caribbean island, including Interferon Alfa 2B. (ACN)]

AHMED Syed Faraz, QUADEER Ahmed A. & MCKAY Matthew R.

2020

Preliminary Identification of Potential Vaccine Targets for the COVID-19

Coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) Based on SARS-CoV Immunological Studies,

in: *Viruses* 2020, 12(3), no. 254. (Special Issue Pathogenesis of Human and Animal Coronaviruses) <<https://doi.org/10.3390/v12030254>>

[Abstract: The beginning of 2020 has seen the emergence of COVID-19 outbreak caused by a novel coronavirus, Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). There is an imminent need to better understand this new virus and to develop ways to control its spread. In this study, we sought to gain insights for vaccine design against SARS-CoV-2 by considering the high genetic similarity between SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV, which caused the outbreak in 2003, and leveraging existing immunological studies of SARS-CoV. By screening the experimentally-determined SARS-CoV-derived B cell and T cell epitopes in the immunogenic structural proteins of SARS-CoV, we identified a set of B cell and T cell epitopes derived from the spike (S) and nucleocapsid (N) proteins that map identically to SARS-CoV-2 proteins. As no mutation has been observed in these identified epitopes among the 120 available SARS-CoV-2 sequences (as of 21 February 2020), immune targeting of these epitopes may potentially offer protection against this novel virus. For the T cell epitopes, we performed a population coverage analysis of the associated MHC alleles and proposed a set of epitopes that is estimated to provide broad coverage globally, as well as in China. Our findings provide a screened set of epitopes that can help guide experimental efforts towards the development of vaccines against SARS-CoV-2.]

CAO Bin, WANG Yeming, WEN Danning, LIU Wen, WANG Jingli, FAN Guohui, RUAN Lianguo, SONG Bin, CAI Yanping, WEI Ming, LI Xingwang, XIA Jiaan, CHEN Nanshan, XIANG Jie, YU Ting, BAI Tao, XIE Xuelei, ZHANG Li, LI Caihong, YUAN Ye, CHEN Hua, LI Huadong, HUANG Hanping, TU Shengjing, GONG Fengyun, LIU Ying, WEI Yuan, DONG Chongya, ZHOU Fei, GU Xiaoying, XU Jiuyang, LIU Zhibo, ZHANG Yi, LI Hui, SHANG Lianhan, WANG Ke, LI Kunxia, ZHOU Xia, DONG Xuan, QU Zhaohui, LU Sixia, HU Xujuan, RUAN Shunan, LUO Shanshan, WU Jing, PENG Lu, CHENG Fang, PAN Lihong, ZOU Jun, JIA Chunmin, WANG Juan, LIU Xia, WANG Shuzhen, WU Xudong, GE Qin, HE Jing, ZHAN Haiyan, QIU Fang, GUO Li, HUANG Chaolin, JAKI Thomas, HAYDEN Frederick G., HORBY Peter W., ZHANG Dingyu, & WANG Chen

2020

A Trial of Lopinavir–Ritonavir in Adults Hospitalized with Severe Covid-19,

in: *The New England Journal of Medicine* March 18, 2020.

DOI: 10.1056/NEJMoa2001282.

<https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2001282>

[Abstract: Background: No therapeutics have yet been proven effective for the treatment of severe illness caused by SARS-CoV-2.

Methods: We conducted a randomized, controlled, open-label trial involving hospitalized adult patients with confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection, which causes the respiratory illness Covid-19, and an oxygen saturation (Sao2) of 94% or less while they were breathing ambient air or a ratio of the partial pressure of oxygen (Pao2) to the fraction of inspired oxygen (Fio2) of less than 300 mm Hg. Patients were randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to receive either lopinavir-ritonavir (400 mg and 100 mg, respectively) twice a day for 14 days, in addition to standard care, or standard care alone. The primary end point was the time to clinical improvement, defined as the time from randomization to either an improvement of two points on a seven-category ordinal scale or discharge from the hospital, whichever came first.

Results: A total of 199 patients with laboratory-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection underwent randomization; 99 were assigned to the lopinavir-ritonavir group, and 100 to the standard-care group. Treatment with lopinavir-ritonavir was not associated with a difference from standard care in the time to clinical improvement (hazard ratio for clinical improvement, 1.24; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.90 to 1.72). Mortality at 28 days was similar in the lopinavir-ritonavir group and the standard-care group (19.2% vs. 25.0%; difference, -5.8 percentage points; 95% CI, -17.3 to 5.7). The percentages of patients with detectable viral RNA at various time points were similar. In a modified intention-to-treat analysis, lopinavir-ritonavir led to a median time to clinical improvement that was shorter by 1 day than that observed with standard care (hazard ratio, 1.39; 95% CI, 1.00 to 1.91). Gastrointestinal adverse events were more common in the lopinavir-ritonavir group, but serious adverse events were more common in the standard-care group. Lopinavir-ritonavir treatment was stopped early in 13 patients (13.8%) because of adverse events.

Conclusions: In hospitalized adult patients with severe Covid-19, no benefit was observed with lopinavir-ritonavir treatment beyond standard care. Future trials in patients with severe illness may help to confirm or exclude the possibility of a treatment benefit. (Funded by Major Projects of National Science and Technology on New Drug Creation and Development and others; Chinese Clinical Trial Register number, ChiCTR2000029308. opens in new tab.)]

CHEN Jun 陳軍, LIU Danping 劉丹萍, LIU Li 劉莉, LIU Ping 劉萍, XU Qingnian 徐慶年, XIA Lu 夏露, LING Yun 凌雲, HUANG Dan 黃丹, SONG Shuli 宋樹麗, ZHANG Dandan 張丹丹, QIAN Zhiping 錢志平, LI Tao 李濤, SHEN Yinzhong 沈銀忠, LU Hongzhou 盧洪洲
°2020 [pdf]

Liúsuan qiǎng lǜkǔ zhìliáo pǔtōng xíng 2019 guānzhūàng bìngdú bìng (COVID-19) huànzhě chūbù yánjiū 硫酸羥氯喹治療普通型 2019 冠狀病毒病(COVID-19)患者初步研究 - A pilot study of hydroxychloroquine in treatment of patients with common coronavirus disease-19 (COVID-19),

in: Zhejiang daxue xuebao 浙江大學學報 (yixue ban 醫學版) • Journal of Zhejiang University (Medical Sciences)49(1): 0-0, 1 table. [6p.]

DOI: 10.3785/j.issn.1008-9292.2020.03.03

<http://www.zjujournals.com/med/10.3785/j.issn.1008-9292.2020.03.03>

<http://www.zjujournals.com/med/Y2020/V49/II/0>

[Abstract: Objective: To evaluate the efficacy and safety of hydroxychloroquine (HCQ) in the treatment of patients with common coronavirus disease-19 (COVID-19). Methods: We prospectively enrolled 30 treatment-naïve patients with confirmed COVID-19 after informed consent at Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center. The patients were randomized 1:1 to HCQ group and the control group. Patients in HCQ group were given HCQ 400 mg per day for 5 days plus conventional treatments, while those in the control group were given conventional treatment only. The primary endpoint was negative conversion rate of COVID-19 nucleic acid in respiratory pharyngeal swab on days 7 after randomization. This study has been approved by the ethics committee of Shanghai public health clinical center and registered online (NCT04261517). Results: One patient in HCQ group developed to severe during the treatment. On day 7, COVID-19 nucleic acid of throat swabs was negative in 13 (86.7%) cases in the HCQ group and 14 (93.3%) cases in the control group (P>0.05). The median duration from hospitalization to virus nucleic acid negative conversion was 4 (1-9) days in HCQ group, which is comparable to that in the control group [2 (1-4) days, (U=83.5, P>0.05)]. The median time for body temperature normalization in HCQ group was 1 (0-2) after hospitalization, which was also comparable to that in the control group 1 (0-3). Radiological progression was shown on CT images in 5 cases (33.3%) of the HCQ group and 7 cases (46.7%) of the control group, and all patients showed improvement in follow-up examination. Four cases (26.7%) of the HCQ group and 3 cases (20%) of the control group had transient diarrhea and abnormal liver function

($P > 0.05$). Conclusions: The prognosis of common COVID-19 patients is good. Larger sample size study are needed to investigate the effects of HCQ in the treatment of COVID-19. Subsequent research should determine better endpoint and fully consider the feasibility of experiments such as sample size. Keywords: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2; Coronavirus disease-19; Novel coronavirus, pneumonia; Hydroxychloroquine; Treatment outcome; Safety.]

critical reviews:

• TELLIER Philippe 2020a: *Hydroxychloroquine et Covid-19: un essai randomisé chinois négatif*, in: JIM Journal international de médecine, 26/03/2020. (& réactions)
<https://www.jim.fr/e-docs/hydroxychloroquine_et_covid_19_un_essai_randomise_chinois_negatif__182350/document_actu_med.phtml?reagir=1#article-reactions>

CHEN Zhaowei, HU Jijia, ZHANG Zongwei, JIANG Shan, HAN Shoumeng, YAN Dandan, ZHUANG Ruhong, HU Ben, ZHANG Zhan

2020

Efficacy of hydroxychloroquine in patients with COVID-19: results of a randomized clinical trial,

in: medRxiv, 31 March 2020.

<<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.22.20040758>>

[Abstract: Aims: Studies have indicated that chloroquine (CQ) shows antagonism against COVID-19 in vitro. However, evidence regarding its effects in patients is limited. This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of hydroxychloroquine (HCQ) in the treatment of patients with COVID-19. Main methods: From February 4 to February 28, 2020, 62 patients suffering from COVID-19 were diagnosed and admitted to Renmin Hospital of Wuhan University. All participants were randomized in a parallel-group trial, 31 patients were assigned to receive an additional 5-day HCQ (400 mg/d) treatment, Time to clinical recovery (TTCR), clinical characteristics, and radiological results were assessed at baseline and 5 days after treatment to evaluate the effect of HCQ. Key findings: For the 62 COVID-19 patients, 46.8% (29 of 62) were male and 53.2% (33 of 62) were female, the mean age was 44.7 (15.3) years. No difference in the age and sex distribution between the control group and the HCQ group. But for TTCR, the body temperature recovery time and the cough remission time were significantly shortened in the HCQ treatment group. Besides, a larger proportion of patients with improved pneumonia in the HCQ treatment group (80.6%, 25 of 32) compared with the control group (54.8%, 17 of 32). Notably, all 4 patients progressed to severe illness that occurred in the control group. However, there were 2 patients with mild adverse reactions in the HCQ treatment group. Significance: Among patients with COVID-19, the use of HCQ could significantly shorten TTCR and promote the absorption of pneumonia.]

critical reviews:

• TELLIER Philippe 2020b: *Hydroxychloroquine et Covid-19: nouvel essai randomisé chinois ... «positif»*, in: JIM Journal international de médecine, 31/03/2020.

<https://www.jim.fr/medecin/actualites/evenements/e-docs/hydroxychloroquine_et_covid_19_nouvel_essai_randomise_chinois_positif__182434/document_actu_med.phtml>

HUNT Joshua

2020

Japan Is Racing to Test a Drug to Treat Covid-19.

Based on a compound discovered in 1998, the antiviral favipiravir is already being used in Japan and Turkey. Its maker? A subsidiary of Fujifilm, (Backchannel)

in: Wired, 04.04.2020 07:00 AM.

<<https://www.wired.com/story/japan-is-racing-to-test-a-drug-to-treat-covid-19/>>

[JIN Ying-Hui *et al.* 2020:]

JIN Ying-Hui, CAI Lin, CHENG Zhen-Shun, CHENG Hong, DENG Tong, FAN Yi-Pin, FANG Cheng, HUANG Di, HUANG Lu-Qi, HUANG Qiao, HAN Yong, HU Bo, HU Fen, LI Bing-Hui, LI Yi-Rong, LIANG Ke, LIN Li-Kai, LUO Li-Sha, MA Jing, MA Lin-Lu, PENG Zhi-Yong, PAN Yun-Bao, PAN Zhen-Yu, REN Xue-Qun, SUN Hui-Min, WANG Ying, WANG Yun-Yun, WENG Hong, WEI Chao-Jie, WU Dong-Fang, XIA Jian, XIONG Yong, XU Hai-Bo, YAO Xiao-Mei, YUAN Yu-Feng, YE Tai-Sheng, ZHANG Xiao-Chun, ZHANG Ying-Wen, ZHANG Yin-Gao, ZHANG Hua-Min, ZHAO Yan, ZHAO Ming-Juan, ZI Hao, ZENG Xian-Tao, WANG Yong-Yan,

WANG Xing-Huan & for the ZHONGNAN HOSPITAL OF WUHAN UNIVERSITY NOVEL CORONAVIRUS MANAGEMENT AND RESEARCH TEAM, EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE CHAPTER OF CHINA INTERNATIONAL EXCHANGE AND PROMOTIVE ASSOCIATION FOR MEDICAL AND HEALTH CARE (CPAM)

°2020 [pdf]

A rapid advice guideline for the diagnosis and treatment of 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) infected pneumonia (standard version),

in: Military Medical Research volume 7, Article number: 4 (2020).

[23p., 10 figs. (CT imaging), 8 tables, 38 refs. Supplementary information: Additional file 1. A successful treatment case of the severe 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia patient. Additional file 2. Experience and lessons in hospital rescue for 2019-nCoV infections.] <<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40779-020-0233-6>>

[Abstract: In December 2019, a new type viral pneumonia cases occurred in Wuhan, Hubei Province; and then named “2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV)” by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 12 January 2020. For it is a never been experienced respiratory disease before and with infection ability widely and quickly, it attracted the world’s attention but without treatment and control manual. For the request from frontline clinicians and public health professionals of 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia management, an evidence-based guideline urgently needs to be developed. Therefore, we drafted this guideline according to the rapid advice guidelines methodology and general rules of WHO guideline development; we also added the first-hand management data of Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University. This guideline includes the guideline methodology, epidemiological characteristics, disease screening and population prevention, diagnosis, treatment and control (including traditional Chinese Medicine), nosocomial infection prevention and control, and disease nursing of the 2019-nCoV. Moreover, we also provide a whole process of a successful treatment case of the severe 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia and experience and lessons of hospital rescue for 2019-nCoV infections. This rapid advice guideline is suitable for the first frontline doctors and nurses, managers of hospitals and healthcare sections, community residents, public health persons, relevant researchers, and all person who are interested in the 2019-nCoV. –

14/23-16/23: **6.4 Traditional Chinese medicine treatment**

6.4.1 Guiding principles / 6.4.2 Prevention / 6.4.3 Treatment [12] / In medical observation period / Clinical treatment period / This period involving 7 stages (...)]

MCCARTY Mark F., DI NICOLANTONIO James J.

°2020 [pdf]

Nutraceuticals have potential for boosting the type 1 interferon response to RNA viruses including influenza and coronavirus,

in: Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases, 12 February 2020.

In Press, Corrected Proof. [3p., 1 table.]

<<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pcad.2020.02.007>>

[Outline: • NOX2-dependent oxidant production inhibits TLR7 signaling

- Antioxidants can also protect by quelling excessive lung inflammation
- Glucosamine administration may up-regulate MAVS activation
- Toward a practical nutraceutical strategy for coping with RNA virus infections. –

Table 1. Provisional daily dosage suggestions for nutraceuticals that might aid control of RNA viruses including influenza and coronavirus

Ferulic acid	500-1,000 mg
Lipoic acid	1,200-1,800 mg (in place of ferulic acid)
Spirulina	15 g (or 100 mg PCB)
N-Acetylcysteine	1,200–1,800 mg
Selenium	50-100 mcg
Glucosamine	3,000 mg or more
Zinc	30-50 mg
Yeast Beta-Glucan	250-500 mg
Elderberry	600–1,500 mg.]

SMITH Tim, BUSHEK Jennifer, PROSSER Tony

2020

COVID-19 Drug Therapy.

Elsevier. Clinical Drug Information | Clinical Solutions. [15p.]

<https://www.elsevier.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0007/988648/COVID-19-Drug-Therapy_Mar-2020.pdf>

[Highlights: • There are no specific therapies approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), the virus that causes coronavirus disease 2019 COVID-19. Several agents are being used under clinical trial

and compassionate use protocols based on in vitro activity (against SARS-CoV-2 or related viruses) and on limited clinical experience. Efficacy has not been established for any drug therapy.

- o Chloroquine – In vitro and limited clinical data suggest potential benefit.
- o Hydroxychloroquine – In vitro and limited clinical data suggest potential benefit.
- o Lopinavir; Ritonavir – Role in the treatment of COVID-19 is unclear. Preclinical data suggested potential benefit; however, more recent data has failed to confirm.
- o Remdesivir – Investigational and available only through expanded access and study protocols; several large clinical trials are underway.
- o Azithromycin – Used in some protocols based on theoretical mechanism and limited preliminary data as adjunct therapy.
- o Tocilizumab – Immunomodulating agent used in some protocols based on theoretical mechanism and limited preliminary data as adjunct therapy.
- o COVID-19 convalescent plasma – Investigational use is being studied.
 - Corticosteroid therapy is not recommended for viral pneumonia; however, use may be considered for patients with refractory shock or acute respiratory distress syndrome.
 - The FDA continues to investigate the use of NSAIDs in patients with COVID-19 symptoms. Concern for potential worsening of COVID-19 symptoms has been suggested, but confirmatory clinical data is lacking at this time.]

WU Canrong, LIU Yang, YANG Yueying, ZHANG Peng, ZHONG Wu, WANG Yali, WANG Qiqi, XU Yang, LI Mingxue, LI Xingzhou, ZHENG Mengzhu, CHEN Lixia, LI Hua
 ©2020 [pdf]

Analysis of therapeutic targets for SARS-CoV-2 and discovery of potential drugs by computational methods,

in: Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B, In Press, Journal Pre-proof

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsb.2020.02.008>

[Abstract: SARS-CoV-2 has caused tens of thousands of infections and more than one thousand deaths. There are currently no registered therapies for treating coronavirus infections. Because of time consuming process of new drug development, drug repositioning may be the only solution to the epidemic of sudden infectious diseases. We systematically analyzed all the proteins encoded by SARS-CoV-2 genes, compared them with proteins from other coronaviruses, predicted their structures, and built 19 structures that could be done by homology modeling. By performing target-based virtual ligand screening, a total of 21 targets (including two human targets) were screened against compound libraries including ZINC drug database and our own database of natural products. Structure and screening results of important targets such as 3-chymotrypsin-like protease (3CLpro), Spike, RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp), and papain like protease (PLpro) were discussed in detail. In addition, a database of 78 commonly used anti-viral drugs including those currently on the market and undergoing clinical trials for SARS-CoV-2 was constructed. Possible targets of these compounds and potential drugs acting on a certain target were predicted. This study will provide new lead compounds and targets for further in vitro and in vivo studies of SARS-CoV-2, new insights for those drugs currently ongoing clinical studies, and also possible new strategies for drug repositioning to treat SARS-CoV-2 infections.

Graphical abstract: Twenty structures including 19 SARS-CoV-2 targets and 1 human target were built by homology modeling. Library of ZINC drug database, natural products, 78 anti-viral drugs were screened against these targets plus human ACE2. This study provides drug repositioning candidates and targets for further in vitro and in vivo studies of SARS-CoV-2.

Keywords: SARS-CoV-2; Drug repurposing; Molecular docking; Remdesivir; Homology modeling.

Abbreviations: 3Clpro, 3-chymotrypsin-like protease; E, envelope; M, membrane protein; N, nucleocapsid protein; N, spon-structure protein; ORF, open reading frame; PDB, protein data bank; RdRp, RNA-dependence RNA polymerase; S, Spike; SUD, SARS unique domain; U, Bubiqutin-like domain.]

Retractions • Withdrawals

THE EDITORS OF THE LANCET GLOBAL HEALTH

2020

Retraction—Chinese medical staff request international medical assistance in fighting against COVID-19,

in: The Lancet Global Health, February 26, 2020.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(20\)30076-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30076-0)

[On Feb 26, 2020, we were informed by the authors of this Correspondence¹ that the account described therein was not a first-hand account, as the authors had claimed, and that they wished to withdraw the piece. We have therefore taken the decision to retract this Correspondence.

1. ZENG Yingchun, ZHEN Yan (2020) *Chinese medical staff request international medical assistance in fighting against COVID-19*, in: Lancet Glob Health. 2020; (published online Feb 24.)

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(20\)30065-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30065-6)]

PRADHAN Prashant, PANDEY Ashutosh Kumar, MISHRA Akhilesh, GUPTA Parul, TRIPATHI Praveen Kumar, MENON Manoj Balakrishnan, GOMES James, VIVEKANANDAN Perumal, KUNDU Bishwajit

2020

Uncanny similarity of unique inserts in the 2019-nCoV spike protein to HIV-1 gp120 and Gag, (Withdrawn)

in: bioRxiv, January 31, 2020. 126 comments.

<https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.01.30.927871>

[Abstract: We are currently witnessing a major epidemic caused by the 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). The evolution of 2019-nCoV remains elusive. We found 4 insertions in the spike glycoprotein (S) which are unique to the 2019-nCoV and are not present in other coronaviruses. Importantly, amino acid residues in all the 4 inserts have identity or similarity to those in the HIV-1 gp120 or HIV-1 Gag. Interestingly, despite the inserts being discontinuous on the primary amino acid sequence, 3D-modelling of the 2019-nCoV suggests that they converge to constitute the receptor binding site. The finding of 4 unique inserts in the 2019-nCoV, all of which have identity /similarity to amino acid residues in key structural proteins of HIV-1 is unlikely to be fortuitous in nature. This work provides yet unknown insights on 2019-nCoV and sheds light on the evolution and pathogenicity of this virus with important implications for diagnosis of this virus.]

• **Withdrawn:** Abstract: This paper has been withdrawn by its authors. They intend to revise it in response to comments received from the research community on their technical approach and their interpretation of the results. If you have any questions, please contact the corresponding author. <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.01.30.927871v2>

• Prashant PRADHAN •

This is a preliminary study. Considering the grave situation, it was shared in BioRxiv as soon as possible to have creative discussion on the fast evolution of SARS-like corona viruses. It was not our intention to feed into the conspiracy theories and no such claims are made here. While we appreciate the criticisms and comments provided by scientific colleagues at BioRxiv forum and elsewhere, the story has been differently interpreted and shared by social media and news platforms. We have positively received all criticisms and comments. To avoid further misinterpretation and confusions world-over, we have decided to withdraw the current version of the preprint and will get back with a revised version after reanalysis, addressing the comments and concerns. Thank you to all who contributed in this open-review process.

: Authors of the Manuscript.

autor's comment:

press:

• ORANSKY Ivan & MARCUS Adam 2020: *Quick retraction of a faulty coronavirus paper was a good moment for science*, in: STAT February 3, 2020.

<https://www.statnews.com/2020/02/03/retraction-faulty-coronavirus-paper-good-moment-for-science/>

SHARMA Manas, SCARR Simon & KELLAND Kate

2020

Speed Science. The risks of swiftly spreading coronavirus research,
in: Reuters Graphics, February 19, 2020.

<https://graphics.reuters.com/CHINA-HEALTH-RESEARCH/0100B5ES3MG/index.html>

153 studies have been published on the new coronavirus

92 were **not peer reviewed**

Guidelines • Guidance for COVID-19

- Chinese guidelines on Novel Coronavirus
<<https://www.evidenceaid.org/chinese-guidelines-on-novel-coronavirus/>>
- Italian guidelines on Novel Coronavirus
<<https://www.evidenceaid.org/italian-guidelines-on-novel-coronavirus/>>
- Japanese guidelines on Novel Coronavirus
<<https://www.evidenceaid.org/japanese-guidelines-on-novel-coronavirus/>>

CDC
2020

Interim Clinical Guidance for Management of Patients with Confirmed Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19).

Center for Disease Control and Prevention.

<<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/clinical-guidance-management-patients.html>>

GUÓJIĀ WÈISHÈNG JIÀNKĀNG WÈI BÀNGŌNGTĪNG 國家衛生健康委辦公廳 [GENERAL OFFICE OF THE NATIONAL HEALTH COMMISSION]

*°2020⁶ [pdf] *xīnxíng guānzhòng bìngdú fèiyán zhěnlíáo fāng'àn* 新型冠狀病毒肺炎診療方案 (*shìxíng dì liù bǎn* 試行第六版).
[New coronavirus pneumonia diagnosis and treatment plan (Trial version 6)]
February 18, 2020. [16p. title p. missing.]
<<http://www.nhc.gov.cn/zyygj/s7653p/202002/8334a8326dd94d329df351d7da8aefc2/files/b218cfeb1bc54639af227f922bf6b817.pdf>>

*°2020⁷ [pdf] *xīnxíng guānzhòng bìngdú fèiyán zhěnlíáo fāng'àn* 新型冠狀病毒肺炎診療方案 (*shìxíng dì qī bǎn* 試行第七版).
[New coronavirus pneumonia diagnosis and treatment plan (Trial version 7)]
March 3, 2020. [23p. title p. missing.]
<<http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/zhengceku/2020-03/04/5486705/files/ae61004f930d47598711a0d4cbf874a9.pdf>>

[JIN Ying-Hui *et al.* 2020:]

JIN Ying-Hui, CAI Lin, CHENG Zhen-Shun, CHENG Hong, DENG Tong, FAN Yi-Pin, FANG Cheng, HUANG Di, HUANG Lu-Qi, HUANG Qiao, HAN Yong, HU Bo, HU Fen, LI Bing-Hui, LI Yi-Rong, LIANG Ke, LIN Li-Kai, LUO Li-Sha, MA Jing, MA Lin-Lu, PENG Zhi-Yong, PAN Yun-Bao, PAN Zhen-Yu, REN Xue-Qun, SUN Hui-Min, WANG Ying, WANG Yun-Yun, WENG Hong, WEI Chao-Jie, WU Dong-Fang, XIA Jian, XIONG Yong, XU Hai-Bo, YAO Xiao-Mei, YUAN Yu-Feng, YE Tai-Sheng, ZHANG Xiao-Chun, ZHANG Ying-Wen, ZHANG Yin-Gao, ZHANG Hua-Min, ZHAO Yan, ZHAO Ming-Juan, ZI Hao, ZENG Xian-Tao, WANG Yong-Yan, WANG Xing-Huan & for the ZHONGNAN HOSPITAL OF WUHAN UNIVERSITY NOVEL CORONAVIRUS MANAGEMENT AND RESEARCH TEAM, EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE CHAPTER OF CHINA INTERNATIONAL EXCHANGE AND PROMOTIVE ASSOCIATION FOR MEDICAL AND HEALTH CARE (CPAM)

°2020 [pdf] *A rapid advice guideline for the diagnosis and treatment of 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) infected pneumonia (standard version),*
in: Military Medical Research volume 7, Article number: 4 (2020).

[23p., 10 figs. (CT imaging), 8 tables, 38 refs. Supplementary information: Additional file 1. A successful treatment case of the severe 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia patient. Additional file 2. Experience and lessons in hospital rescue for 2019-nCoV infections.]

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40779-020-0233-6>

[Abstract: In December 2019, a new type viral pneumonia cases occurred in Wuhan, Hubei Province; and then named “2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV)” by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 12 January 2020. For it is a never been experienced respiratory disease before and with infection ability widely and quickly, it attracted the world’s attention but without treatment and control manual. For the request from frontline clinicians and public health professionals of 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia management, an evidence-based guideline urgently needs to be developed. Therefore, we drafted this guideline according to the rapid advice guidelines methodology and general rules of WHO guideline development; we also added the first-hand management data of Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University. This guideline includes the guideline methodology, epidemiological characteristics, disease screening and population prevention, diagnosis, treatment and control (including traditional Chinese Medicine), nosocomial infection prevention and control, and disease nursing of the 2019-nCoV. Moreover, we also provide a whole process of a successful treatment case of the severe 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia and experience and lessons of hospital rescue for 2019-nCoV infections. This rapid advice guideline is suitable for the first frontline doctors and nurses, managers of hospitals and healthcare sections, community residents, public health persons, relevant researchers, and all person who are interested in the 2019-nCoV. –

14/23-16/23: **6.4 Traditional Chinese medicine treatment**

6.4.1 Guiding principles / 6.4.2 Prevention / 6.4.3 Treatment [12] / In medical observation period / Clinical treatment period / This period involving 7 stages (...)]

NATIONAL HEALTH COMMISSION (NHC) of the PRC; NATIONAL ADMINISTRATION OF TRADITIONAL CHINESE MEDICINE of the PRC (eds.)

°2020 [pdf]

Guidance for Corona Virus Disease 2019: Prevention, Control, Diagnosis and Management.

Edited by National Health Commission (NHC) of the PRC;
National Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicine of the PRC.
Compiled and Translated by Chinese Preventive Medicine Association.

Translators in Chief Xiaofeng LIANG, Zijian FENG, Liming Li.
Beijing: People’s Medical Publishing House.

[136p.; ISBN 978-7-117-29817-9.]

https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/7qy_oCfUuJB4erRtG47vvA

ZHŌNGGUÓ ZHĒNJIǔ XUÉHUÌ 中國針灸學會 [Chinese Acupuncture Society]

°2020 [pdf]

xīnxíng guānzhuàng bìngdú fēiyán zhēnjiǔ gānyù de zhǐdǎo yìjiàn 新型冠狀病毒肺炎針灸干預的指導意見 (dì èr bǎn 第二版).

[Guidance on Acupuncture Intervention for New Coronavirus Pneumonia (Second Edition)]

in: zhong zhen zi 中針字 2020, 5.

<https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/BCG1puilQJ7XDJnHqEqvmA>

Traditional Chinese medicine

BUHNER Stephen Harrod

°2020 [**pdf**]

Herbal Treatment for Coronavirus Infections.
[19p.] <<https://www.stephenharrodbuhner.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/coronavirus.txt.pdf>>

GARRAN Thomas Avery (tr.)

°2020 [**pdf**]

Hubei Province Integrated Chinese/Western Medicine Hospital.
Critical Viral Respiratory Disease Formulas.

GARRAN Thomas Avery (tr.) (+OCHS Shelley tr.)

°2020 [**pdf**]

Guangdong province. Chinese Medicine Protocol for Pneumonia Due to Novel Coronavirus. (Provisional First Edition January 24, 2020).

HSU Lori (comp.)

°2020 [**pdf**]

COVID-19 Formula Charts.
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1A3tws1CRyhomuK8b92vIVWF52kugCz_tIAH3XN_SwtU/edit#gid=0>
[Sources: (1) Hubei Provincial Hospital Formulas: <<https://www.elotus.org/article/how-covid-19-2019-ncov-currently-treated-china-tcm>>
(2) PRC COVID-19 recommendation tentative 6th English edition: <<https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/nOAmosQ4YqkXHKdJbBE9GA?fbclid=IwAR25Uzbc-hX4PwLiBLPrgSF6nNERCjbU7F3V8JCo12Wj4oX-myKboLhlfek>>
(3) PRC COVID-19 recommendation tentative 7th Chinese edition <<https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/IFXXreRWad-nGCUNzINOuw>>]

[JIN Ying-Hui *et al.* 2020:]

JIN Ying-Hui, CAI Lin, CHENG Zhen-Shun, CHENG Hong, DENG Tong, FAN Yi-Pin, FANG Cheng, HUANG Di, HUANG Lu-Qi, HUANG Qiao, HAN Yong, HU Bo, HU Fen, LI Bing-Hui, LI Yi-Rong, LIANG Ke, LIN Li-Kai, LUO Li-Sha, MA Jing, MA Lin-Lu, PENG Zhi-Yong, PAN Yun-Bao, PAN Zhen-Yu, REN Xue-Qun, SUN Hui-Min, WANG Ying, WANG Yun-Yun, WENG Hong, WEI Chao-Jie, WU Dong-Fang, XIA Jian, XIONG Yong, XU Hai-Bo, YAO Xiao-Mei, YUAN Yu-Feng, YE Tai-Sheng, ZHANG Xiao-Chun, ZHANG Ying-Wen, ZHANG Yin-Gao, ZHANG Hua-Min, ZHAO Yan, ZHAO Ming-Juan, ZI Hao, ZENG Xian-Tao, WANG Yong-Yan, WANG Xing-Huan & for the ZHONGNAN HOSPITAL OF WUHAN UNIVERSITY NOVEL CORONAVIRUS MANAGEMENT AND RESEARCH TEAM, EVIDENCE-BASED MEDICINE CHAPTER OF CHINA INTERNATIONAL EXCHANGE AND PROMOTIVE ASSOCIATION FOR MEDICAL AND HEALTH CARE (CPAM)

°2020 [**pdf**]

A rapid advice guideline for the diagnosis and treatment of 2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) infected pneumonia (standard version),
in: *Military Medical Research* volume 7, Article number: 4 (2020).
[23p., 10 figs. (CT imaging), 8 tables, 38 refs. Supplementary information: Additional file 1. A successful treatment case of the severe 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia patient. Additional file 2. Experience and lessons in hospital rescue for 2019-nCoV infections.] <<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40779-020-0233-6>>
[Abstract: In December 2019, a new type viral pneumonia cases occurred in Wuhan, Hubei Province; and then named “2019 novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV)” by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 12 January 2020. For it is a never been experienced respiratory disease before and with infection ability widely and quickly, it attracted the world’s attention but without treatment and control manual. For the request from frontline clinicians and public health professionals of 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia management, an evidence-based guideline urgently needs to be developed. Therefore, we drafted this guideline according to the rapid advice guidelines methodology and general rules of WHO guideline development; we also added the first-hand management data of Zhongnan Hospital of Wuhan University. This guideline includes the guideline methodology, epidemiological characteristics, disease screening and population prevention, diagnosis, treatment and control (including traditional Chinese

Medicine), nosocomial infection prevention and control, and disease nursing of the 2019-nCoV. Moreover, we also provide a whole process of a successful treatment case of the severe 2019-nCoV infected pneumonia and experience and lessons of hospital rescue for 2019-nCoV infections. This rapid advice guideline is suitable for the first frontline doctors and nurses, managers of hospitals and healthcare sections, community residents, public health persons, relevant researchers, and all person who are interested in the 2019-nCoV. –
 14/23-16/23: 6.4 Traditional Chinese medicine treatment
 6.4.1 Guiding principles / 6.4.2 Prevention / 6.4.3 Treatment [12] / In medical observation period / Clinical treatment period / This period involving 7 stages (...).]

LUO Hui, TANG Qiao-ling, SHANG Ya-xi, LIANG Shi-bing, YANG Ming, ROBINSON Nicola & LIU Jian-ping
 ©2020 [pdf]

Can Chinese Medicine Be Used for Prevention of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)? A Review of Historical Classics, Research Evidence and Current Prevention Programs,

in: Chinese Journal of Integrative Medicine (2020).

[8p., 2 figs., 2 tables, 34 refs.; supplementary material: 8p. Appendix 1. **Characteristics of Chinese Medicine Prevention Recommendations for COVID-19 Issued by 23 Provinces in Mainland China.**]

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11655-020-3192-6>

https://static-content.springer.com/esm/art%3A10.1007%2Fs11655-020-3192-6/MediaObjects/11655_2020_3192_MOESM1_ESM.pdf

[Abstract: Objective: Since December 2019, an outbreak of corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) occurred in Wuhan, and rapidly spread to almost all parts of China. This was followed by prevention programs recommending Chinese medicine (CM) for the prevention. In order to provide evidence for CM recommendations, we reviewed ancient classics and human studies.

Methods: Historical records on prevention and treatment of infections in CM classics, clinical evidence of CM on the prevention of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and H1N1 influenza, and CM prevention programs issued by health authorities in China since the COVID-19 outbreak were retrieved from different databases and websites till 12 February, 2020. Research evidence included data from clinical trials, cohort or other population studies using CM for preventing contagious respiratory virus diseases.

Results: The use of CM to prevent epidemics of infectious diseases was traced back to ancient Chinese practice cited in Huangdi's Internal Classic (Huang Di Nei Jing) where preventive effects were recorded. There were 3 studies using CM for prevention of SARS and 4 studies for H1N1 influenza. None of the participants who took CM contracted SARS in the 3 studies. The infection rate of H1N1 influenza in the CM group was significantly lower than the non-CM group (relative risk 0.36, 95% confidence interval 0.24–0.52; n=4). For prevention of COVID-19, 23 provinces in China issued CM programs. The main principles of CM use were to tonify qi to protect from external pathogens, disperse wind and discharge heat, and resolve dampness. The most frequently used herbs included *Radix astragali* (Huangqi), *Radix glycyrrhizae* (Gancao), *Radix saposhnikoviae* (Fangfeng), *Rhizoma Atractylodis Macrocephalae* (Baizhu), *Lonicerae Japonicae Flos* (Jinyinhua), and *Fructus forsythia* (Lianqiao).

Conclusions: Based on historical records and human evidence of SARS and H1N1 influenza prevention, Chinese herbal formula could be an alternative approach for prevention of COVID-19 in high-risk population. Prospective, rigorous population studies are warranted to confirm the potential preventive effect of CM.]

Figure 2. Frequency of Commonly Used Herbs in Preventive Formulae for COVID-19

China using Tibetan medicine to fight Covid-19 epidemic,
in: Tibetan Review, February 26, 2020 7:40 am.

[<https://www.tibetanreview.net/china-using-tibetan-medicine-to-fight-covid-19-epidemic/>](https://www.tibetanreview.net/china-using-tibetan-medicine-to-fight-covid-19-epidemic/)

[(full text) (TibetanReview.net, Feb24'20) – In a continued use in China of Tibetan medicine to fight the Covid-19 epidemic, the Beijing Hospital of Tibetan Medicine has prepared almost 10,000 bags of “Nine-flavor epidemic prevention powder” and is distributing them to those in need, reported China’s official globaltimes.cn Feb 25.

The report cited Feng Xin, deputy director of the Department of Medical Affairs at the Beijing Hospital of Tibetan Medicine, as saying some of the ingredients used to make the medicine were transported to Beijing from Tibet Autonomous Region (TAR).

The recipe was stated to have been made under the guidance of Tibetan medical master Cuoru Cilang.

Feng has said the recipe was the same as that used during the 2003 SARS epidemic of 2002-03.

The report also cited Qinghai provincial government officials as saying that 1,000 bags of the medicine had been sent to Central China’s Hubei Province, the epicenter of the epidemic, in January.

Also, TAR’s Administration Bureau of Traditional Tibetan Medicine was stated to have made a prevention and treatment plan for Covid-19 by using Tibetan medicine. The report cited the National Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicine as saying on its website that the pilot version was available in both Tibetan and Chinese languages.

The Beijing Hospital of Tibetan Medicine, built in 1992, was stated to be the only national-level ethnic hospital in China’s capital city.]

VANDERKLIPPE Nathan, Li Alexandra

°2020 [pdf]

At the epicentre of the coronavirus outbreak, Western medicine meets traditional Chinese remedies,

in: The Globe and Mail 28 January 2020.

[<https://www.theglobeandmail.com/amp/world/article-as-coronavirus-death-toll-rises-china-combines-western-and/?__twitter_impression=true>](https://www.theglobeandmail.com/amp/world/article-as-coronavirus-death-toll-rises-china-combines-western-and/?__twitter_impression=true)

Pharmacy workers wearing protective clothes and masks serve customers in Wuhan on Jan. 25, 2020.

HECTOR RETAMAL/AFP/Getty Images

<[https://www.theglobeandmail.com/resizer/gIhaeQtauPULIRfHvSHd0Q0tMRI=/760x0/filters:quality\(80\)/arc-anglerfish-tgam-prod-tgam.s3.amazonaws.com/public/RO2Z4JJ5M5G2ZCVB66CQCQSFZWM.jpg](https://www.theglobeandmail.com/resizer/gIhaeQtauPULIRfHvSHd0Q0tMRI=/760x0/filters:quality(80)/arc-anglerfish-tgam-prod-tgam.s3.amazonaws.com/public/RO2Z4JJ5M5G2ZCVB66CQCQSFZWM.jpg)>

[• Liutianbao Pharmacy, Wuhan.

• «Last Thursday, doctors at the Hubei Provincial Hospital of Traditional Chinese Medicine released a pair of “formulas for pneumonia prevention.” The recommended formulas clear away heat, detoxify, dry dampness, moisten and enhance physical immunity, Yang Yi, a senior Chinese medicine practitioner, told state media. “Citizens can decoct at home to prevent the disease,” the state-run People’s Daily reported.

The two recommended formulations include black atractylodes rhizome (used in Chinese medicine to dry dampness), along with extracts of honeysuckle (to clear inflammation), tangerine peel (to disperse phlegm), raw astragalus (to boost immune response) and several other herbs.

The recommendations are almost identical to a formulation promoted in 2003 in response to the spread of the SARS virus, which is a coronavirus genetically similar to the Wuhan virus.»

• SARS studies by Ping-Chung LEUNG: «But numerous studies have offered little conclusive evidence on their effectiveness. Prof. Leung reviewed 130 academic articles, 90 of which he deemed to have “sufficient information for the enlightenment of the situation.” Together, they “revealed positive but inconclusive indications.” The use of Chinese medicine could help control fevers, clear chest infection more rapidly and provide relief of some symptoms, he wrote.»]

WEI Tao 魏涛 [yīzhèng yīguǎn jú 医政医管局, gōnggòng wèishēng yīliáo guǎnlǐ chù 公共卫生医疗管理处]

°2020 [pdf]

xīnxíng guānzhhuàng bìngdú gǎnrǎn de fēiyán zhěnlíáo fāng'àn 新型冠状病毒感染的肺炎诊疗方案 (shìxíng dì sì bǎn 试行第四版),

in: guo weiban yihan 国卫办医函 77.

[pdf; 9p. «Medical Administration Authority, Public Health Medical Management Office, Wei Tao». Novel coronavirus infection pneumonia treatment program (Trial Version 4).

标题: 关于印发新型冠状病毒感染的肺炎诊疗方案(试行第四版)的通知

发文机关: 国家卫生健康委办公厅 国家中医药管理局办公室

发文字号: 国卫办医函〔2020〕77号

来源: 卫生健康委网站

主题分类: 卫生、体育\卫生

公文种类: 通知

成文日期: 2020年01月27日

发布日期: 2020年

Title: Notice on Printing and Distributing Pneumonia Diagnosis and Treatment Plan for New Coronavirus Infection (Trial Version 4)

Issuing authority: General Office of National Health and Health Commission Office of State Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicine

Issue the text number: National Health Office Medical Letter [2020] No. 77

Source: Health and Health Commission website

Category: Health, Sports \ Health

Type of document: notice

Written date: January 27, 2020

Release Date: 2020.]

<http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/zhengceku/2020-01/28/content_5472673.htm>

[7-8: TCM Treatments (四) 中医治疗。]

YANG Wanli, LIU Kun

°2020

TCM treatment effective against novel coronavirus, says official.

By Yang Wanli in Beijing and Liu Kun in Wuhan,

in: China daily, Updated: 2020-02-20 20:46.

<<https://www.chinadaily.com.cn/a/202002/20/WS5e4e7fafa31012821727915a.html>>

[(full text, except photo) Integrating traditional Chinese medicine with Western medicine to treat the novel coronavirus patients has been proven to be effective, a top official with the State Administration of Traditional Chinese Medicine said on Thursday.

“A large number of clinical practices have confirmed the effect of the combined treatment of TCM and Western medicine on new coronavirus pneumonia patients,” said Yu Yanhong [余

艳红], Party chief and deputy head of the administration, also a member of the central government work group guiding epidemic control work in Central China's Hubei province.

She said TCM can rapidly improve symptoms in patients with mild symptoms, shorten the course of illness for patients with severe symptoms, and reduce the possibility of mild infections from becoming severe.

Citing the latest clinical research on 102 patients with light symptoms, Yu said TCM treatment can shorten the average length of patient stay in the hospital by 2.2 days while enhancing the recovery rate by 33 percent compared with the control group.

The transfer rate from medium symptoms to severe symptoms dropped by 27.4 percent and the number of lymphocytes, an important indicator of the health condition of patients who are recovering, increased by 70 percent, according to the clinical research.

Yu said the central leadership has paid great attention to the epidemic control work and President Xi Jinping has made clear instruction to constantly improve the diagnosis and treatment plan, and integrate TCM with Western medicine in the treatment of novel coronavirus pneumonia.

"The early participation of TCM in the treatment of the novel coronavirus pneumonia has produced a notable effect," she said.

Administration data released on Monday showed that TCM had been prescribed to 60,107 infected patients, or 85.2 percent, of the total infections nationwide.

In South China's Guangdong province, 1,245 confirmed novel coronavirus patients – as many as 94 percent of all the patients in the province – had received TCM treatment apart from Western medicine methods by Tuesday, TCM experts said at a press conference in Guangzhou on Wednesday. And TCM proved effective in 89 percent of the cases, they added.

Apart from medicines, TCM treatment also included acupuncture, ear acupuncture point application and Baduanjin (a fitness practice with a history of 800 years), improving patients' sleep and facilitating their recovery, said Chen Ning, director of the Pulmonary Disease Department of the Guangdong Second Traditional Chinese Medicine Hospital.

Yu said one herbal concoction, known as Qingfei Paidu Soup, which mixes ephedra and licorice root among other ingredients, has emerged as an effective prescription and has been listed in the latest diagnosis and treatment guide book.

Official data shows that as of Thursday, 3,200 TCM-trained medical workers have participated in treating novel coronavirus patients in Hubei province.

Four batches of national-level TCM teams comprising 588 people are now stationed in four medical institutions in Hubei, including the newly-built Leishenshan Hospital in Wuhan.

Ten national-level TCM expert teams also have been organized to make regular visits in several major designated hospitals. Currently, each mobile cabin hospital in the province has two to three TCM doctors.

"We will deepen the cooperation with western medical treatment. Also, the treatment plan that mixes TCM with Western medicines will be further improved to form a mechanism and play a more important role to fight against the disease," Yu said.]

ZHANG Wenhong
2020

Zhang Wenhong: Little Chance Coronavirus Pandemic Will End This Summer,
in: Caixin, March 27, 2020 06:57 AM.

<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-27/zhang-wenhong-little-chance-coronavirus-pandemic-will-end-this-summer-101534591.html>

[ZHANG Wenhong, head of Shanghai's Covid-19 clinical expert team, and director of the infectious diseases department at Huashan Hospital of Fudan University in Shanghai. –

"Which is more effective, traditional Chinese medicine or Western medicine?"

Zhang: Shanghai used a combination of traditional Chinese and Western medicine in the treatment of Covid-19 patients, and the collaboration has been very effective. I don't think it makes sense to say which one is more effective. This is like a couple. When the life is good, why bother to distinguish who contributes more? And it's impossible to tell. If we have to tell who contributes more, it can only be done by comparison using traditional Chinese medicine only or Western medicine only without using any other treatments. It's ethically impossible to do such an experiment on patients. How could we risk people's lives to do such experiments? If a patient needs oxygen, but I only give him traditional Chinese medicine but not oxygen, this is not right. Both traditional Chinese medicine and Western medicine are medical science. The combination of traditional Chinese and Western medicine in the treatment of Covid-19 patients has achieved good results."]

ZHONGGUÓ ZHÈNJIǔ XUÉHUÌ 中國針灸學會 [Chinese Acupuncture Society]

°2020 [pdf]

xīnxíng guānzhòng bìngdú fēiyán zhēnjiǔ gānyù de zhǐdǎo yìjiàn 新型冠狀病毒肺炎針灸干預的指導意見 (dì èr bǎn 第二版).

[Guidance on Acupuncture Intervention for New Coronavirus Pneumonia

(Second Edition)]

in: zhong zhen zi 中針字 2020, 5.

<<https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/BCG1pui1QJ7XDJnHqEqvmA>>

Press reports

Updating thematic lists of news outlets

- CAIXIN WANG 財新網: *Xīnguān fèiyán fángyì quán jìlù* 新冠肺炎防疫全纪录 (shíshí gēngxīn zhōng 实时更新中) [Full record of the novel coronavirus-infected pneumonia epidemic prevention (Live update)]
<http://m.app.caixin.com/m_topic_detail/1473.html>
- Africanews.com
<<https://www.africanews.com/2020/02/25/ivory-coast-tests-suspected-coronavirus-case/>>
- Science Media Center [Expert opinions on COVID-19 issues]
<<https://www.sciencemediacentre.org/tag/COVID-19/>>
- Al Jazeera. China coronavirus outbreak: All the latest updates
<<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/02/cloneofchina-coronavirus-outbreak-latest-updates-200223232154013.html>>
- La Repubblica. Coronavirus in Italia: aggiornamento ora per ora.
<https://www.repubblica.it/cronaca/2020/02/22/news/coronavirus_in_italia_aggiornamento_ora_per_ora-249241616/>
- Süddeutsche Zeitung: COVID-19.
<<https://www.sueddeutsche.de/thema/Coronavirus>>
- Die Republik. Covid-19-Uhr-Newsletter.
Brauchbares zur Pandemie – immer wenn es dunkel wird. Informationen für alle.
<<https://www.republik.ch/maerzkampagne>>
- The Guardian: Coronavirus live.
<<https://www.theguardian.com/world/series/coronavirus-live>>
- The Atlantic: What You Need to Know About the Coronavirus. The Atlantic's guide to understanding COVID-19. <<https://www.theatlantic.com/category/what-you-need-know-coronavirus/>>

News articles

ADAM David
2020

Modelers Struggle to Predict the Future of the COVID-19 Pandemic.
Disease experts have largely focused on how we got to where we are now with coronavirus infections. Improved data collection and sharing can enhance projections of what's to come.
in: The Scientist, March 12, 2020.
<<https://www.the-scientist.com/news-opinion/modelers-struggle-to-predict-the-future-of-the-covid-19-pandemic-67261>>

AI Jingwen, ZHANG Haocheng & ZHANG Wenhong
2020

Zhang Wenhong: 18% to 31% of Coronavirus Cases Are Asymptomatic, (Opinion)
in: Caixin, April 02, 2020 05:46 AM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-04-02/zhang-wenhong-how-china-can-manage-risks-from-asymptomatic-cases-101537613.html>>

ALJAZEERA, NEWS AGENCIES
2020

China sends essential coronavirus supplies to Italy.
China steps in to help Italy in its time of need as wealthy businessman Jack Ma offers to donate supplies to the US.
in: Al Jazeera, 13 March, 2020.
<<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/03/china-sends-essential-coronavirus-supplies-italy-200313195241031.html>>

AYLWARD Bruce
*2020a

WHO-China Joint Mission on COVID-19 holds press conference in Beijing.
CGTN, 24 February 2020.
<<https://newsvideo.su/video/12313196>>
[Experts from China and the World Health Organization have given the latest updates on the coronavirus outbreak at a press conference in Beijing.
Liang Wannian, head of the Chinese expert panel on outbreak response and disposal, said that most patients have mild symptoms and will recover. The percentage of people showing mild, severe and critical symptoms is around 80, 13 and 6 percent respectively.
Bruce Aylward, head of WHO Experts Team, said the change in the graphic could mean hundreds of thousands of people have avoided infection. He also said that the world needs China's experience to control the epidemic and China has proved that it's done a great job.]

*2020b

Live from Geneva with Dr Bruce Aylward, lead of the #COVID19 international experts mission in #China.
<<https://www.pscp.tv/w/1yNxaQEYijjxj>>

BAO Zhiming, QIN Jianhang, GAO Yu, XIAO Hui & SHEN Timmy
°2020 [doc]

Update: Wuhan Doctors Say Colleagues Died in Vain Amid Official Cover-Up,
in: Caixin Mar 11, 2020 08:07 PM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-11/wuhan-doctors-say-colleagues-died-in-vain-amid-official-coverup-101526650.html>>

BBC News
2020

Coronavirus: Iran temporarily frees 54,000 prisoners to combat spread,
(Nazanin Zaghari-Ratcliffe case)
in: BBC News, 3 March 2020.
<<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-51723398>>

BEGLEY Sharon
*2020a

Experts envision two scenarios if the new coronavirus isn't contained,
in: STAT, February 4, 2020.
<<https://www.statnews.com/2020/02/04/two-scenarios-if-new-coronavirus-isnt-contained>>

*2020b

Who is getting sick, and how sick? A breakdown of coronavirus risk by demographic factors,
in: STAT, March 3, 2020.
<<https://www.statnews.com/2020/03/03/who-is-getting-sick-and-how-sick-a-breakdown-of-coronavirus-risk-by-demographic-factors>>

BELLUZ Julia
2020

China's cases of Covid-19 are finally declining. A WHO expert explains why. "It's all about speed": the most important lessons from China's Covid-19 response. / There's one country in the world that currently has the most knowledge of and experience with Covid-19: China.
in: Vox, March 2, 2020, 2:10pm EST.
<<https://www.vox.com/2020/3/2/21161067/coronavirus-covid19-china>>

BUCKLEY Chris & MYERS Steven Lee
°2020 [pdf]

As New Coronavirus Spread, China's Old Habits Delayed Fight.
At critical turning points, Chinese authorities put secrecy and order ahead of openly confronting the growing crisis and risking public alarm or political embarrassment,
in: The New York Times Published Feb. 1, 2020. Updated Feb. 3, 2020, 3:30 a.m. ET.
<<https://www.nytimes.com/2020/02/01/world/asia/china-coronavirus.html?action=click&module=RelatedLinks&pgtype=Article>>

CAIXIN WANG 財新網
°2010 [pdf]

Xīnguān fēiyán 'chuī shào rén' Lǐ Wénliàng quèzhěn, céng bèi jǐngfāng xùnjiè
新冠肺炎「吹哨人」李文亮確診，曾被警方訓誡 (*gēngxīn* 更新),
[Novel coronavirus-infected pneumonia “whistleblower” Li Wenliang was diagnosed, had been warned by police (update)]
in: Caxin wang 財新網, 2020 年 01 月 31 日 11:47.
<<http://china.caixin.com/2020-01-31/101509761.html>>
[武漢醫生李文亮率先披露不明肺炎有關情況，受到單位約談、警方訓誡。2月1日，他被確診患上新冠肺炎。他說，讓大家知道真相比自己平反更重要，一個健康的社會不應該只有一種聲音.]

CHANG Hsiung-feng & HSU Elizabeth

2020

WUHAN VIRUS / *Taiwan moves closer to developing COVID-19 rapid screening reagent,*

in: Focus Taiwan, CNA English News, 03/08/2020 06:06 PM.

[<https://focustaiwan.tw/sci-tech/202003080009>](https://focustaiwan.tw/sci-tech/202003080009)

CHANG Ping 长平

2020

Beijing Has Nothing But Good News for You in the Coronavirus Epidemic,

in: China Change, March 6, 2020.

[<https://chinachange.org/2020/03/06/beijing-has-nothing-but-good-news-for-you-in-the-coronavirus-epidemic>](https://chinachange.org/2020/03/06/beijing-has-nothing-but-good-news-for-you-in-the-coronavirus-epidemic)

On March 5, vice premier Sun Chunlan inspected the Qingshan Kaiyuan community in Wuhan. It's meant to showcase to the national and international audience Wuhan's success in coronavirus control. But things went off script: she was greeted by residents who came out on their balconies shouting, "Fake! It's all fake!" (Video clips from a social media group of Wuhan residents.) [假的! 假的!]

[<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EDHH460xAUg>](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EDHH460xAUg)

CHARISIUS Hanno, UHLMANN Berit

2020

Ist das Coronavirus noch zu stoppen?

in: Süddeutsche Zeitung, 14. Februar 2020, 18:58 Uhr.

[<https://www.sueddeutsche.de/gesundheit/coronavirus-pandemie-stoppen-1.4798146>](https://www.sueddeutsche.de/gesundheit/coronavirus-pandemie-stoppen-1.4798146)

[• Die Weltgesundheitsorganisation zeigt sich optimistisch, den Ausbruch von Covid-19 eindämmen zu können.

• Viele Experten aber zweifeln, dass er ganz zum Stillstand gebracht werden kann.

• Sie wären schon froh, wenn die weitere Ausbreitung deutlich verzögert würde.

“Auch RKI-Präsident Lothar Wieler mahnt, es müsse alles dafür getan werden, um eine Pandemie zumindest hinauszuzögern. Denn während einer normalen Grippezeit arbeiten bereits viele Krankenhäuser an den Grenzen ihrer Kapazität. “Im Winter 2017/2018 hatten wir eine schwere Grippezeit mit zehn Millionen Arztbesuchen in Deutschland”, sagt Wieler. “Das wurde vom Gesundheitssystem gestemmt.” Doch eine weitere Krankheit dieses Ausmaßes zur selben Zeit wäre extrem kritisch.”]

CHEN Stephen

2020

Coronavirus weaker than Sars but may share link to bats, Chinese scientists say.

Virus found in fruit bats is common ancestor of the two strains, study suggests. New strain has unusually high ability to bind to a human protein, researchers calculate,
in: South China Morning Post, 11:56am, 22 Jan, 2020.
<<https://www.scmp.com/news/china/science/article/3047114/coronavirus-weaker-sars-may-share-link-bats-chinese-scientists>>

CGTN [China Global Television Network] *

2020

Big Story: Epicenter – 24 hours in Wuhan.

Video 56:37, 17 February 2020.

<<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MnhTFjxRVUM>>

[It struck during China's busiest travel season and changed how many people celebrated the Lunar New Year. Millions who had set out across the country for family reunions during the holiday had to cut their vacations short or a completely change plans after the outbreak of COVID-19, a pneumonia caused by the novel #coronavirus, hit the city of Wuhan in central Hubei Province. CGTN's "Epicenter – 24 hours in Wuhan" documentary paints a human and compassionate story of the people fighting the outbreak in China.]

COHEN Elizabeth [CNN Senior Medical Correspondent]

2020

Disease detectives hunting down more information about 'super spreader' of Wuhan coronavirus,

in: CNN Health, Updated 1454 GMT (2254 HKT) January 23, 2020

<<https://edition.cnn.com/2020/01/23/health/wuhan-virus-super-spreader/index.html>>

COHEN Jon, KUPFERSCHMIDT Kai

2020

Strategies shift as coronavirus pandemic looms,

in: Science, 28 Feb 2020, 367(6481): 962-963.

DOI: 10.1126/science.367.6481.962.

<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/sci/367/6481/962.full.pdf>>

[963: "Yet China's domestic restrictions have come at a huge cost to individuals, says Lawrence Gostin, who specializes in global health policy at Georgetown University Law Center. He calls the policies "astounding, unprecedented, and medieval," and says he is particularly concerned about the physical and mental well-being of people in Hubei who are housebound, under intensive surveillance, and facing shortages of health services. "This would be unthinkable in probably any country in the world but China," he says. (Italy's lockdowns are for relatively small towns, not major cities.)"]

CYRANOSKI David

*2017

Inside the Chinese lab poised to study world's most dangerous pathogens.

Maximum-security biolab is part of plan to build network of BSL-4 facilities across China,

in: Nature 542(7642): 399-400. doi:10.1038/nature.2017.21487.

<<https://www.nature.com/news/inside-the-chinese-lab-poised-to-study-world-s-most-dangerous-pathogens-1.21487>>

[Editors' note, January 2020: Many stories have promoted an unverified theory that the Wuhan lab discussed in this article played a role in the coronavirus outbreak that began in December 2019. Nature knows of no evidence that this is true; scientists believe the most likely source of the coronavirus to be an animal market.]

*2020a

When will the coronavirus outbreak peak? Officials want to know but predictions vary wildly, from now to after hundreds of millions of people are infected,

in: Nature, News, 18 February 2020.

doi: 10.1038/d41586-020-00361-5.

<<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-00361-5>>

*2020b

Scientists question China's decision not to report symptom-free coronavirus cases.

Researchers say that excluding these people could conceal the epidemic's true extent, but others say the practice makes sense, in: Nature, News, 20 February 2020.
<<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-00434-5>>

*°2020c [pdf]

Mystery deepens over animal source of coronavirus.
Pangolins are a prime suspect, but a slew of genetic analyses has yet to find conclusive proof,
in: Nature 579: 18-19. doi: 10.1038/d41586-020-00548-w.
<<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-00548-w>>

DA Shiji 达史纪 (pseud.) [DA Shiji is the penname of a veteran journalist living in the city of Wuhan]
°2020 [doc]

The Truth About "Dramatic Action", (Media Beat)
in: China Media Project, January 27, 2020.
<<http://chinamediaproject.org/2020/01/27/dramatic-actions/>>

DEMOCRACY NOW!
2020

Iranian Infectious Disease Specialist [Kamiar ALAEI] on How the U.S. Should Address the Coronavirus Pandemic.
Democracy Now! Web Exclusive, March 02, 2020.
<https://www.democracynow.org/2020/3/2/iranian_infectious_disease_specialist_on_how>

DEUBER Lea
2020

Coronavirus: WHO singt Lobeshymnen auf China,
in: Süddeutsche Zeitung, 14. März 2020, 5:33 Uhr.
<<https://www.sueddeutsche.de/politik/coronavirus-china-who-1.4844104>>
[propaganda article.]

DOWLING Stephen
2020

Coronavirus: What can we learn from the Spanish flu?
In the aftermath of World War One, a flu pandemic swept the world, killing at least 50 million people. What lessons can it teach us about Covid-19?
in: BBC Future, 3rd March 2020.
<<https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20200302-coronavirus-what-can-we-learn-from-the-spanish-flu>>

EVERINGTON Keoni
2020

Taiwan scientists develop antibodies for 15-minute Wuhan virus test in 19 days.
Taiwan's Academia Sinica develops antibodies for rapid testing of Wuhan coronavirus in just 19 days,
in: Taiwan News, 2020/03/09 10:00.
<<https://www.taiwannews.com.tw/en/news/3893301>>
[On its Facebook page* at noon on Sunday, Academia Sinica announced that Dr. Yang An-suei (楊安綏) and his team at the Genomics Research Center had developed monoclonal antibodies that can identify the protein of SARS-CoV-2, the virus which causes COVID-19, within a "record-breaking" 19 days. Specifically, Yang said that the first monoclonal antibodies to bind the nucleocapsid protein (N protein) have been successfully tested and generated.
* <<https://www.facebook.com/sinicaedu/posts/2477979259184506>>]

FANG Fang 方方
*°2020a [doc]

zuòjiā Fāng Fāng 作家方方: Shéi néng xiǎngdào cì shēng zāihài huì luò dào hànǔ shàng?
谁能想到次生灾害会落到汉语上?

in: Caixin: zuòjiā Fāng Fāng de bókè 作家方方的博客 2020-03-08.
<<http://fangfang.blog.caixin.com/archives/223170>>

*°2020b [doc]

Opinion: Thank the Government for Controlling the Virus? No, They Should Be Thanking Us,

in: Caixin, March 12, 2020 08:18 PM.

<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-12/opinion-thank-the-government-for-controlling-the-virus-no-they-should-be-thanking-us-101527671.html>>

[On Sunday, well-known author Fang Fang posted a blog on Caixin's Chinese-language website lambasting the "arrogance" of top government officials in the central city of Wuhan, after they announced plans to roll out so-called "gratitude education" to make sure local residents properly thank the Communist Party for controlling the coronavirus epidemic that has so far killed nearly 2,500 people in the city, according to official figures.

Fang's article argues that rather than soliciting praise from their citizens, Chinese officials should thank the country's medical workers, sickened patients, and bereaved families for their self-sacrifice, restraint, and cooperation amid a grave human tragedy. / Below is a partial translation of Fang's article [FANG Fang 2020a], edited for length.]

FEUER William
2020

WHO chief addresses death threats, racist insults: 'I don't give a damn',

in: CNBC, Wednesday, April 8 2020 12:37 PM EDT, Updated
Thursday, April 9 2020 1:07 AM EDT.

<<https://www.cnbc.com/2020/04/08/who-chief-addresses-death-threats-racist-insults-i-dont-give-a-damn.html>>

[Key Points: • The leader of the World Health Organization, Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, said Wednesday he's received death threats and racist insults while running the global efforts to fight the coronavirus pandemic.

• Tedros was responding to a question about whether criticism from world leaders in the midst of a global pandemic makes it more difficult for the leader of the WHO to operate. –

"I can tell you personal attacks that have been going on for more than two, three months. Abuses, or racist comments, giving me names, black or Negro. I'm proud of being black, proud of being Negro," he told reporters on a conference call from the organization's Geneva headquarters on Wednesday. "I don't care, to be honest ... even death threats. I don't give a damn." Tedros was responding to a question about whether criticism from world leaders such as President Donald Trump in the midst of a global pandemic makes it more difficult to operate the WHO. Tedros commented specifically on insults that he said came from Taiwan.

"Three months ago, this attack came from Taiwan. We need to be honest. I will be straight today. From Taiwan," he said. "And Taiwan, the Foreign Ministry also, they know the campaign. They didn't disassociate themselves. They even started criticizing me in the middle of all that insult and slur, but I didn't care."]

FISCHER Doris & MAYER Maximilian

°2020 [pdf]

Vorurteile gefährden unser aller Gesundheit – es ist fahrlässig, Covid-19 durch die Systembrille zu betrachten.

In der Bekämpfung des neuen Coronavirus geht es auch um den Wettbewerb der Systeme. Während die gebeutelte chinesische Führung gern Heldentum und Hightech zelebriert, übt sich der Westen in Schuldzuweisung und Überheblichkeit. Kurzsichtig ist beides, (Gastkommentar)

in: Neue Zürcher Zeitung, 06.03.2020, 05.30 Uhr.

<<https://www.nzz.ch/meinung/es-ist-fahrlaessig-covid-19-durch-die-systembrille-zu-betrachten-ld.1544570>>

FRIEBE Richard
2020

Coronavirus erfolgreich bekämpft. Wie Taiwan den Covid-19-Ausbruch verhinderte – und die WHO davon nichts wissen will.

Taiwan hätte nach China eigentlich das Land mit den schlimmsten Epidemie-Ausmaßen sein müssen. Doch der Inselstaat hat schnell und konsequent reagiert,

in: Der Tagesspiegel, 05.03.2020, 16:14 Uhr.

<https://www.tagesspiegel.de/wissen/coronavirus-erfolgreich-bekaempft-wie-taiwan-den-covid-19-ausbruch-verhinderte-und-die-who-davon-nichts-wissen-will/25613942.html>

[Discussion of WANG C. Jason, NG, BROOK 2020; Compare re Vietnam: NGUYEN Sen 2020.]

GAO Yu, PENG Yanfeng, YANG Rui, FENG Yuding, MA Danmeng, MURPHY Flynn, HAN Wei & SHEN Timmy

°2020 [doc]

In Depth: How Early Signs of a SARS-Like Virus Were Spotted, Spread, and Throttled,

in: Caixin, February 29, 2020 09:19 PM.

<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-02-29/in-depth-how-early-signs-of-a-sars-like-virus-were-spotted-spread-and-throttled-101521745.html>

The Wuhan Institute of Virology, part of the Chinese Academy of Sciences. Photo: Ding Gang/Caixin

GARRETT Laurie

*2020a

Trump Has Sabotaged America's Coronavirus Response.

As it improvises its way through a public health crisis, the United States has never been less prepared for a pandemic,

in: Foreign Policy, January 31, 2020, 11:07 AM.

<https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/01/31/coronavirus-china-trump-united-states-public-health-emergency-response/>

*2020b

[Interview] Part 1: *Laurie Garrett on How Trump Has Sabotaged America's Response to the Coronavirus Pandemic.*

Democracy Now! February 3, 2020.

https://www.democracynow.org/2020/2/3/laurie_garrett_coronavirus_trump_admin_response

*2020c

[Interview] Part 2: *Laurie Garrett on Coronavirus: Racist Attitudes Could Aid & Abet the Spread of the Pandemic.*

Democracy Now! February 3, 2020.

https://www.democracynow.org/2020/2/4/laurie_garrett_on_coronavirus_racist_attitudes

GRAY Richard

*2020a

Covid-19: How long does the coronavirus last on surfaces?

We can pick up the Covid-19 by touching surfaces contaminated with the new coronavirus, but it is only just becoming clear how long the virus can survive outside the human body,
in: BBC Future, 17th March 2020.
<https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20200317-covid-19-how-long-does-the-coronavirus-last-on-surfaces>

*2020b

Will warm weather really kill off Covid-19?
Some people hope that outbreaks of the new coronavirus will wane as temperatures rise, but pandemics often don't behave in the same way as seasonal outbreaks. BBC Future looks at what we know,
in: BBC Future, 24th March 2020.
<https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20200323-coronavirus-will-hot-weather-kill-covid-19>

HAO Nicole
2020

China's Top Biowarfare Specialist Helms Efforts to Combat Coronavirus, Army Enters Wuhan to Deliver Supplies,
in: The Epoch Times, February 4, 2020 Updated: February 4, 2020.
https://www.theepochtimes.com/chinas-top-biowarfare-specialist-helms-efforts-to-combat-coronavirus-army-enters-wuhan-to-deliver-supplies_3227019.html

HARRISON Charlotte
2020

Coronavirus puts drug repurposing on the fast track.
Existing antivirals and knowledge gained from the SARS and MERS outbreaks gain traction as the fastest route to fight the current coronavirus epidemic.
China's biotech companies have been gearing up to repurpose existing drugs, approved in the West for other viruses, as treatments for the coronavirus outbreak originating in Wuhan,
in: Nature Biotechnology, 27 February 2020. [1 table.]
doi: 10.1038/d41587-020-00003-1.
<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41587-020-00003-1>

Drug or cocktail	Originator company	Status and mechanisms	Clinical trials (trial posting date)
ASC09/ritonavir, lopinavir/ritonavir, with or without umifenovir	Asclelis, AbbVie, Pharmstandard	ASC09 is an experimental HIV-1 protease inhibitor; ritonavir and lopinavir/ritonavir are approved protease inhibitors for HIV/AIDS; umifenovir is an approved entry inhibitor against influenza	At least three trials (e.g., ChiCTR2000029603, 2/6/20)
ASC09/oseltamivir, ritonavir/oseltamivir, oseltamivir	Asclelis, Gilead, AbbVie	See above; oseltamivir is a sialidase inhibitor approved for influenza	One trial (NCT04261270, 2/7/20)
Azvudine	Zhengzhou Granlen PharmaTech	Experimental reverse transcriptase inhibitor drug against HIV-1/AIDS	One trial (ChiCTR2000029853, 2/15/20)
Various combinations of baloxavir marboxil/favipiravir and lopinavir/ritonavir	Shionogi, Toyama Chemical	Baloxavir marboxil is a Cap-dependent endonuclease inhibitor and favipiravir is a guanine analog RNA-dependent RNA polymerase inhibitor approved for influenza A and B; see above	Two trials (ChiCTR2000029544, 2/3/20; ChiCTR2000029548, 2/4/20)
Various combinations of darunavir/cobicistat alone	Janssen, Gilead	Darunavir and cobicistat are, respectively, an HIV-1 protease inhibitor and inhibitor of cytochrome	Two trials (NCT04252274, 2/5/20;

or with lopinavir/ritonavir and thymosin α1		P450 (CYP)3A enzyme, approved as a combination against HIV-1/AIDS. Thymosin α1 is an immune response boosting agent	ChiCTR2000029541, 2/3/20)
Remdesivir	Gilead	Phosphoramidate prodrug of an adenine analog used for Ebola and Marburg virus outbreaks (similar structure to approved HIV reverse transcriptase inhibitors)	Two trials (NCT04252664, 2/5/20; NCT04257656, 2/6/20)
Chloroquine or hydroxychloroquine	Shanghai Zhongxi Pharmaceutical, Shanghai Ziyuan Pharmaceutical, Wuhan Wuyao Pharmaceutical	Endosomal acidification fusion inhibitor	At least ten trials (e.g., ChiCTR2000029826, 2/2/20; NCT04261517, 2/14/20)
Methylprednisolone	Generic	Synthetic corticosteroid that binds to nuclear receptors to dampen proinflammatory cytokines	One trial (NCT04263402, 2/10/20)
Interferon alfa-2b alone or in combination with lopinavir/ritonavir and ribavirin	Biogen, Merck	Interferon alfa-2b is a recombinant cytokine with antiviral properties; ribavirin is a guanine derivative; as above	Two trials (NCT04254874, 2/5/20; ChiCTR2000029308, 1/23/20)
Camrelizumab and thymosin	Incyte, Shanghai Hengrui Pharmaceutical	Camrelizumab is a humanized monoclonal antibody (mAb) targeting PD-1	Two trials (ChiCTR2000029806, 2/14/20; NCT04268537, 2/14/20)
Tocilizumab	Chugai Pharmaceutical, Zhejiang Hisun Pharmaceutical, Jiangsu Qyun Bio-Pharmaceutical	Humanized mAb targeting interleukin-6	One trial (ChiCTR2000029765, 2/13/20)
Last search run on 15 February using https://clinicaltrials.gov and http://www.chictr.org.cn . Excludes traditional Chinese medicines and blood-derived products, such as serum from recovered patients and stem cells. All trials are being conducted in China.			

HE Jingwei, MA Danmeng & JIA Denise

2020

U.K. Bets on Less-Reliable Form of Covid-19 Test in Scramble to Stop Pandemic,
in: Caixin, April 02, 2020 08:31 AM.

<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-04-02/uk-bets-on-less-reliable-form-of-covid-19-test-in-scramble-to-stop-pandemic-101537643.html>>

HSU Elizabeth

2020

Coronavirus. China study suggests 14-day COVID-19 quarantine too short for women,

in: Focus Taiwan, CNA English News, 03/06/2020, 10:35 PM.

<<https://focustaiwan.tw/sci-tech/202003060021>>

IWATA Kentaro

*2020a

Kentaro Iwata Explains Diamond Princess Cruise Experience.

Kentaro Iwata: Professor of Infectious Diseases at Kobe University.
February 18, 2020.

<<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t-JIOSg2hw8>>

*2020b

Kentaro Iwata: «Aboard the Diamond Princess» (via Skype broadcasting from remote place).

日本外国特派員協会 会見映像 オフィシャルサイト
FCCJchannel. February 20, 2020.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V29eNY_0kWQ>

KARIMI Nasser & GAMBRELL Jon

2020

Virus ravaging Iran kills confidant of its supreme leader,

in: Associated Press, AP News, March 2, 2020.

[<https://apnews.com/2ab5535d09074fd0e1c70fc78fef2fad>](https://apnews.com/2ab5535d09074fd0e1c70fc78fef2fad)

[“Aid has been reaching Iran, despite international firms worried about conducting business with Tehran after the U.S. unilaterally withdrew from Iran’s nuclear deal with world powers and imposed sanctions. Some 7.5 tons of aid from the World Health Organization flew into Iran from the United Arab Emirates.

The WHO said a team of experts flew into Tehran Monday evening to help local health workers respond to the outbreak and deliver medical supplies. It added a WHO worker in Iran was sick with the virus as well.

Meanwhile, France, Germany and the United Kingdom said they would urgently fly laboratory tests for the virus into Iran, as well as protective body suits and gloves. They also offered close to 5 million euros (\$5.5 million) in financial support.

Iranian Foreign Minister Mohammad Javad Zarif thanked those donating supplies and said Tehran still needed protective gear, ventilators and test kits.”]

KIM E. Tammy

2020

A South Korean Covid-19 Czar Has Some Advice for Trump.

“We need global cooperation,” says Min Pok-kee, who heads the response in the hard-hit city of Daegu. “Top government leaders don’t seem to get that yet.”

in: Wired, 03.26.2020, 02:57 PM.

[<https://www.wired.com/story/a-south-korean-covid-19-czar-has-some-advice-for-trump/>](https://www.wired.com/story/a-south-korean-covid-19-czar-has-some-advice-for-trump/)

[“The UK offers a cautionary tale. Its first response was to say that people would develop herd immunity, though it switched course a few days later. I’d already been concerned about the capacity of the British system, and this made me very worried. Herd immunity only works if you have a vaccine and 85 to 90 percent of the population is inoculated. Right now, in the face of an infectious disease with such a high mortality rate, for the UK to resist acknowledging the reality of the virus could translate into tens of thousands of deaths. It was unthinkable for a government to put out such nonsense. We in Korea were thinking, “Are these people in their right mind?””]

KIM Tong-Hyung

2020

COVID-19 Spreads in South Korean City as Thousands Are Screened,

in: Time, Updated: February 22, 2020 11:53 AM ET | Originally published: February 22, 2020 10:01 AM EST.

[<https://time.com/5789199/south-korea-coronavirus-cases/>](https://time.com/5789199/south-korea-coronavirus-cases/)

KÖPPE Julia

2020

Neues Coronavirus Suche nach Patient X.

Zwischen Mitte November und Anfang Dezember muss das Coronavirus Sars-CoV-2 den Sprung vom Tier zum Menschen geschafft haben. Nur wo? Und welches Tier war es? Wissenschaftler fahnden im Genom des Erregers nach Antworten.

Aus Seattle berichtet Julia Köppe,

in: Der Spiegel, 18.02.2020, 13:21 Uhr.

[<https://www.spiegel.de/wissenschaft/medizin/coronavirus-sars-cov-2-wissenschaftler-suchen-im-virenerbgut-nach-ursprung-von-covid-19-a-b4f5a5c8-9c3a-416f-b27f-8ffcb5ad64ae#>](https://www.spiegel.de/wissenschaft/medizin/coronavirus-sars-cov-2-wissenschaftler-suchen-im-virenerbgut-nach-ursprung-von-covid-19-a-b4f5a5c8-9c3a-416f-b27f-8ffcb5ad64ae#)

KUPFERSCHMIDT Kai

*2020a

Study claiming new coronavirus can be transmitted by people without symptoms was flawed,

in: Science Magazine, February 3, 2020, 5:30 PM.

[<https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/02/paper-non-symptomatic-patient-transmitting-coronavirus-wrong>](https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/02/paper-non-symptomatic-patient-transmitting-coronavirus-wrong)

[Correction to letter by ROTHE Camilla *et al.* 2020.]

*2020b *'A completely new culture of doing research.'* Coronavirus outbreak changes how scientists communicate,
in: Science Magazine, February 26, 2020, 2:05 PM.
<<https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/02/completely-new-culture-doing-research-coronavirus-outbreak-changes-how-scientists>>

KUPFERSCHMIDT Kai, COHEN Jon
2020 *Can China's COVID-19 strategy work elsewhere?*
in: Science 06 Mar 2020, 367(6482): 1061-1062.
DOI: 10.1126/science.367.6482.1061
<<https://science.sciencemag.org/content/367/6482/1061>>

LI Xiangyu 李想侯, LI Mingzi 李明子, PENG Danni 彭丹妮 & DU Wei 杜玮
*°2020a [pdf] *Wùhàn zhī hàn 武汉之憾: Huángjīn fáng kòng qī shì rúhé cuòguò de 黄金防控期是如何错过的?*
in: China News Weekly, February 10. [post-publication censorship.]
reposted: <<https://cfcnews.com/278261/封面一-武汉之憾：黄金防控期是如何错过的？/>>

*°2020b [pdf] *The Regret of Wuhan: How China Missed the Critical Window for Controlling the Coronavirus Outbreak.*
By Li Xiangyu (李想侯), Li Mingzi (李明子), Peng Danni (彭丹妮), and Du Wei (杜玮), in the February 10 issue of China News Weekly. ChinaChange.org.
<<https://chinachange.org/2020/02/09/the-regret-of-wuhan-how-china-missed-the-critical-window-for-controlling-the-coronavirus-outbreak/>>
[Out of mountains of reports about the coronavirus epidemic, we at China Change have taken a keen interest in two areas: the origins of the virus, and the decision making process. The cover story of China News Weekly (中国新闻周刊), published on February 5, put together a detailed timeline and asked the right questions. Within a day, the article was deleted from the magazine's own website as well as major Chinese news portals. Luckily, the report is preserved in various news aggregate sites outside China in both simplified and traditional Chinese (武汉之憾: 黄金防控期是如何错过的?)* The timeline it presented focuses on the discovery of early coronavirus cases, local government's responses in the seven weeks from December 1 to January 20, what the local and national Center for Disease Control and Prevention did in that period, and without directly raising the question, how the most critical decisions, especially the decision to downplay the outbreak in the first weeks, were made at the State Council and ultimately by the Communist Party leaders in Zhongnanhai. Unfortunately, we still don't know much about the first case of the 2019-nCoV. This is a translation of the censored article. We added notes at various points of the text to provide more details and context, and links are embedded for your easy reference. – The Editors.
* <<https://cfcnews.com/278261/封面一-武汉之憾：黄金防控期是如何错过的？/>>]

LIAN Yi-Zheng
2020 *Why Did the Coronavirus Outbreak Start in China? Let's talk about the cultural causes of this epidemic.*
Mr. Lian is a former chief editor of the Hong Kong Economic Journal and a contributing Opinion writer,
in: The New York Times, February 20, 2020.
<<https://www.nytimes.com/2020/02/20/opinion/sunday/coronavirus-china-cause.html>>

LICHTERBECK Philipp [Rio de Janeiro]
2020 *Virusbekämpfung in Brasilien. Lockdown oder Essen.*
Die Coronaquarantäne stellt die Menschen in den Favelas vor ein

Problem: Wenn sie nicht arbeiten, verlieren sie ihr Einkommen.
Statt auf den Staat zu warten, organisieren sie sich nun lieber selbst.
Ein Streifzug,
in: Die WochenZeitung, Nr. 14, 2. April 2020: 5.
<<https://www.woz.ch/2014/virusbekaempfung-in-brasilien/lockdown-oder-essen>>

MA Danmeng, DI Ning & SUN Huixia

°2020 [doc]

In Depth: How Shanghai Handled the Coronavirus Better Than Most of China,
in: Caixin, Mar 07, 2020 03:15 AM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-07/in-depth-how-shanghai-handled-the-coronavirus-better-than-most-of-china-101525054.html>>

MA Danmeng, HUANG Shulun, PENG Yanfeng, DI Ning & HAN Wei

°2020 [doc]

In Depth: The Maddening Mystery of Defeating the Covid-19 Epidemic,
in: Caixin, March 02, 2020 06:30 AM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-02/in-depth-the-maddening-mystery-of-defeating-the-covid-19-epidemic-101522570.html>>

MALLAPATY Smriti

*2020a

Why does the coronavirus spread so easily between people?
Researchers have identified microscopic features that could make the pathogen more infectious than the SARS virus — and serve as drug targets,
in: Nature, 06 March 2020. doi: 10.1038/d41586-020-00660-x.
<<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-00660-x>>
[Correction 11 March 2020: An earlier version of this story misstated a result from David Vessler's study on ACE2.]

An image of the new coronavirus taken with an electron microscope.

Credit: U.S. National Institutes of Health/AP/Shutterstock
[Regarding WRAPP *et al.* 2020; Li Hua *et al.* 2020.]

*2020b

How sewage could reveal true scale of coronavirus outbreak.
Wastewater testing could also be used as an early-warning sign if the virus returns,
in: Nature, 3 April 2020. doi: 10.1038/d41586-020-00973-x.
<<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-00973-x>>

MCKEEVER Amy

2020

Here's what coronavirus does to the body.
From blood storms to honeycomb lungs, here's an organ-by-organ look at how COVID-19 harms humans. (11 Minute Read)
in: National Geographic, February 18, 2020.
<<https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/2020/02/here-is-what-coronavirus-does-to-the-body/>>

MOLE Beth
*2020a

CDC tells Americans to brace for coronavirus. WHO's insights from China suggest that the virus can be contained,
in: ars technica 2/25/2020, 11:01 PM.
<<https://arstechnica.com/science/2020/02/coronavirus-spread-in-us-not-if-but-when-and-how-severe-cdc-says/>>

*2020b

WHO tries to calm talk of pandemic, says the word "does not fit the facts".
Meanwhile, US coronavirus cases hit 53 as more cruise passengers test positive,
in: ars technica 2/25/2020, 1:12 AM.
<<https://arstechnica.com/science/2020/02/who-tries-to-calm-talk-of-pandemic-says-the-word-does-not-fit-the-facts/>>

NG Teddy
2020

No link with seafood market in first case of China coronavirus, Chinese scientists revealed. Researchers into initial cases find first person with symptoms had no contact with market where disease is believed to have originated. Call for preparedness against airborne transmission, including fitted respirators and other personal protective equipment,
in: South China Morning Post, 4:27pm, 25 Jan, 2020.
<<https://www.scmp.com/news/china/society/article/3047646/no-link-seafood-market-first-case-china-coronavirus-chinese>>

NGUYEN Sen
2020

Coronavirus miracle? Vietnam says all its infected patients cured World Health Organization officials and health experts say swift response crucial in containing virus in the country,
in: AlJazeera, 29 February 2020.
<<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/02/infected-patients-vietnam-cured-coronavirus-miracle-200228035007608.html>>

NORMILE Dennis
2020

Scientist decries 'completely chaotic' conditions on cruise ship Japan quarantined after viral outbreak,
in: Science Magazine, Feb. 19, 2020, 2:45 PM.
<<https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/02/scientist-decries-completely-chaotic-conditions-cruise-ship-japan-quarantined-after>>

PARK Alice
2020

COVID-19 Vaccine Shipped, and Drug Trials Start,
in: Time, February 25, 2020.
<<https://time.com/5790545/first-covid-19-vaccine/>>

PILLING David
2020

Lunch with the FT Peter Piot. Ebola co-discoverer Peter Piot on how to respond to the coronavirus. The 'Mick Jagger of microbes' on a life of fighting disease – and the severity of the current crisis,
in: Financial Times, February 28, 2020.
<<https://www.ft.com/content/de0a7c9e-56ff-11ea-a528-dd0f971feb9c>>

PUEYO Tomas
2020

Coronavirus: Why You Must Act Now.

Politicians, Community Leaders and Business Leaders: What Should You Do and When?

in: Medium, March 10, 22 min read; Updated on 3/11/2020.

<<https://medium.com/@tomaspuoyo/coronavirus-act-today-or-people-will-die-f4d3d9cd99ca>>

PURANAM Elizabeth
2020

India's homeless shelters struggle to meet new demand.

For the millions of poor and daily wage earners in India, the threat of hunger looms larger than that of the virus.

Al Jazeera podcast. March 26, 2020.

<<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/03/indias-homeless-shelters-struggle-meet-demand-200325190150342.html>>

[India is under the biggest lockdown in history, with all 1.3 billion people ordered to stay home for three weeks. / While most are observing the order, homeless shelters are filling up with people who have lost their livelihoods. / Al Jazeera's Elizabeth Puranam reports from the capital, New Delhi.]

QIU Jane
2020 [pdf]

How China's "Bat Woman" Hunted Down Viruses from SARS to the New Coronavirus.

Wuhan-based virologist Shi Zhengli [石正麗] has identified dozens of deadly SARS-like viruses in bat caves, and she warns there are more out there,

in: Scientific American, March 11, 2020.

<<https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/how-chinas-bat-woman-hunted-down-viruses-from-sars-to-the-new-coronavirus/>>

Shi Zhengli, known as China's "bat woman" for her virus-hunting expeditions in bat caves, releases a fruit bat after taking blood and swab samples from it in 2004. Credit: Wuhan Institute of Virology.

• Shi Zhengli <http://sourcedb.whiov.cas.cn/zw/rck/200907/t20090718_2100074.html>

REGALADO Antonio
2020

This is what happens when you get the coronavirus.

Hospitals in China are reporting their experiences with hundreds of patients so far,

in: MIT Technology Review, February 11, 2020.

<https://www.technologyreview.com/s/615176/an-inside-report-of-what-happens-when-you-get-the-coronavirus>

ROGERS Adam
2020

The Asian Countries That Beat Covid-19 Have to Do It Again.
Singapore, Hong Kong, South Korea, and Taiwan had flattened the curve. Then travelers from the US and Europe began reimporting the virus,
in: Wired, 04.06.2020 07:00 AM.
<https://www.wired.com/story/the-asian-countries-that-beat-covid-19-have-to-do-it-again/>

SCIENCE MEDIA CENTER

*2020a

expert reaction to statement from South China Agricultural University that research has identified the pangolin as a possible coronavirus host.
Science Media Center, February 7, 2020.
<https://www.sciencemediacentre.org/expert-reaction-to-statement-from-south-china-agricultural-university-that-research-has-identified-the-pangolin-as-a-possible-coronavirus-host/>

*2020b

expert reaction to media questions about if we are 'reaching a tipping point' in the COVID-19 outbreak.
Science Media Center, February 24, 2020.
<https://www.sciencemediacentre.org/expert-reaction-to-media-questions-about-if-we-are-reaching-a-tipping-point-in-the-covid-19-outbreak/>

SHEIKH Knavul, WATKINS Derek, WU Jin & GRÖNDAHL Mika
2020

How Bad Will the Coronavirus Outbreak Get? Here Are 6 Key Factors,
in: The New York Times, Jan. 31, 2020.
<https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2020/world/asia/china-coronavirus-contain.html>

SMITH Shannon
2020

What the Coronavirus Means for Africa.
Given its fragile public health systems and close ties to China, Africa is vulnerable to the spread of the coronavirus, highlighting the continent's centrality to global health security.
Africa Center for Strategic Studies. February 4, 2020
<https://africacenter.org/spotlight/what-the-coronavirus-means-for-africa/>

SMITH Tara C.
2020

The Animal Origins of Coronavirus and Flu.
Zoonotic diseases like influenza and many coronaviruses start out in animals, but their biological machinery often enables them to jump to humans, (Quantized Columns)
in: Quanta Magazine, February 25, 2020.
<https://www.quantamagazine.org/how-do-animal-viruses-like-coronavirus-jump-species-20200225/>

SOY Anne
2020

Coronavirus: Are African countries ready?
in: BBC News, Nairobi, 14 February 2020.
<<https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-51403865>>

STEENHUYSEN Julie
2020

As pressure for coronavirus vaccine mounts, scientists debate risks of accelerated testing, (Health News)
in: Reuters, March 11, 2020 / 12:07 PM.
<<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-health-coronavirus-vaccines-insight/as-pressure-for-coronavirus-vaccine-mounts-scientists-debate-risks-of-accelerated-testing-idUSKBN20Y1GZ>>
[(intro) CHICAGO (Reuters) - Drugmakers are working as quickly as possible to develop a vaccine to combat the rapidly spreading coronavirus that has infected more than 100,000 people worldwide.]

SÜDDEUTSCHE ZEITUNG
°2020 [pdf]

Newsblog zu Covid-19: Coronavirus übersteht bis zu 72 Stunden auf Stahl und Kunststoff,
in: Süddeutsche Zeitung, 12. März 2020, 12:55 Uhr.
<<https://www.sueddeutsche.de/gesundheit/coronavirus-oberflaechen-symptome-forschung-1.4788734>>

SUN Liangzi & YANG Ge
2020

Jeers of 'Fake, It's All Fake' Greet Beijing VIP in Virus-Stricken Wuhan,
in: Caixin, March 06, 2020 09:24 PM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-06/jeers-of-fake-its-all-fake-greet-beijing-vip-in-virus-stricken-wuhan-101524933.html>>

VENKATA Nandini
*2020a

Caixin China Biz Roundup: Investigation Special – Lights Are On but No One's Working: How Local Governments Are Faking Coronavirus Recovery, (Podcast)
in: Caixin, March 05, 2020 06:47 PM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-05/caixin-china-biz-roundup-investigation-special-lights-are-on-but-no-ones-working-how-local-governments-are-faking-coronavirus-recovery-101524475.html>>

*2020b

Caixin China Biz Roundup: Quarantine Hotel Collapse Traps Dozens Under Rubble, (Podcast)
in: Caixin, March 09, 2020 06:41 PM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-09/caixin-china-biz-roundup-quarantine-hotel-collapse-traps-dozens-under-rubble-101525970.html>>

WANG Duan, WEN Simin & LI Isabelle

°2020 [doc]

Exclusive: Q&A With Hong Kong's Yuen Kwok-Yung, Who Helped Confirm Coronavirus's Human Spread,

in: Caixin, March 09, 2020 10:18 PM.

[https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-09/exclusive-qa-with-hong-kongs-yuen-
kwok-yung-who-helped-confirm-coronaviruss-human-spread-101526079.html](https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-09/exclusive-qa-with-hong-kongs-yuen-kwok-yung-who-helped-confirm-coronaviruss-human-spread-101526079.html)

[YUEN Kwok-Yung: “We can only rely on telling everyone to wear a mask, wash their hands frequently, use alcoholic sanitizer. I had called for everyone to wear a mask when I was in Beijing, but many people disagreed, saying that the World Health Organization (WHO) said healthy people don't need to wear masks unless they go to crowded places. Nevertheless, if people wear masks only when they feel sick, then the eight infected people on the Diamond Princess would have transmitted it to others because they were not feeling uncomfortable. Wear a mask to protect not only yourself but also others, because if you are infected but asymptomatic, you could still stop the spread by wearing a mask.

In our experiments previously, we found 100 million virus strands in just one milliliter of a patient's saliva. Therefore, scenarios with the potential for exchanging saliva are generally quite dangerous. The temporary success of virus control in Hong Kong this time is not only due to population controls, but also contributed by the early advocacy for mask-wearing, hand-washing, and social distancing. Otherwise, with such a dense population in Hong Kong, the epidemic would very likely have spread the same way as in Italy or Daegu in South Korea.”]

WEN Simin, YANG Ge & MURPHY Flynn

°2020 [doc]

A Hong Kong Dog Tested Positive for Coronavirus, And That's All Anyone Can Agree On,

in: Caixin, March 05, 2020 08:33 PM.

[https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-05/a-hong-kong-dog-tested-positive-for-
coronavirus-and-thats-all-anyone-can-agree-on-101524525.html](https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-05/a-hong-kong-dog-tested-positive-for-coronavirus-and-thats-all-anyone-can-agree-on-101524525.html)

WHO

2020

Latest updates – Live press conference (Geneva).

WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19 – 8 April 2020.

<https://youtu.be/k1nf8kk7aHc>

WONG John E.L., LEO Yee Sin, TAN Chorh Chuan

2020

COVID-19 in Singapore—Current Experience. Critical Global Issues That Require Attention and Action, (Viewpoint)

in: JAMA. February 20, 2020. doi:10.1001/jama.2020.2467.

<https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2761890>

XIAO Hui; SUN Huixia, YIN Dave (tr.) *

*°2020a [pdf]

Reporter's Notebook: Life and death in a Wuhan coronavirus ICU.

Translated by SUN Huixia and Dave YIN,

in: Caixin Global, February 06, 2020 07:40 AM

[https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-02-06/reporters-notebook-we-interview-
front-line-coronavirus-doctor-101512020.html](https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-02-06/reporters-notebook-we-interview-front-line-coronavirus-doctor-101512020.html)

[(press report on clinical study) Interview with PENG Zhiyong, director of acute medicine at the Wuhan University South Central Hospital, with 66-bed Intensive Care Unit (ICU); clinical study based on 138 cases. (See now the study WANG Dawei *et al.* 2020.)

“Lately I've been spending the daytime seeing patients in the ICU, then doing some research in the evenings. I just wrote a thesis. I drew on data from 138 cases that South Central Hospital had from Jan. 7-28 and attempted to summarize some patterns of the novel coronavirus.

A lot of viruses will die off on their own after a certain amount of time. We call these self-limited diseases. I've observed that the breakout period of the novel coronavirus tends to be three weeks, from the onset of symptoms to developing difficulties breathing. Basically going from mild to severe symptoms takes about a week. There are all sorts of mild symptoms: feebleness, shortness of breath, some people have fevers, some don't. Based on studies of our 138 cases, the most common symptoms in the first stage are fever (98.6% of cases), feebleness (69.6%), cough (59.4%), muscle pains (34.8%), difficulties breathing (31.2%), while less common symptoms include headaches, dizziness, stomach pain, diarrhea, nausea, vomiting.

But some patients who enter the second week will suddenly get worse. At this stage, people should go to the hospital. Elderly with underlying conditions may develop complications; some may need machine-assisted respiration. When the body's other organs start to fail, that's when it becomes severe, while those with strong immune systems see their symptoms decrease in severity at this stage and gradually recover. So the second week is what determines whether the illness becomes critical.

The third week determines whether critical illness leads to death. Some in critical condition who receive treatment can raise their lymphocyte, a type of white blood cell, and see an improvement in their immune systems, and have been brought back, so to speak. But those whose lymphocyte numbers continue to decline, those whose immune systems are destroyed in the end, experience multiple organ failure and die.

For most, the illness is over in two weeks, whereas for those for whom the illness becomes severe, if they can survive three weeks they're good. Those that can't will die in three weeks.”]

*°2020b [pdf]

Reporter's Notebook: Life and death in a Wuhan coronavirus ICU.

Translated by SUN Huixia and Dave YIN,

in: The Straits Times, February 6, 2020, 4:40 pm SGT

<https://www.straitstimes.com/asia/east-asia/reporters-notebook-life-and-death-in-a-wuhan-coronavirus-icu?>

[(press report on clinical study) Interview with PENG Zhiyong, director of acute medicine at the Wuhan University South Central Hospital, with 66-bed Intensive Care Unit (ICU); clinical study based on 138 cases. (see XIAO Hui 2020a.)]

XINHUA

°2020

Update: Pangolins a potential intermediate host of novel coronavirus: study,

in: Xinhua 2020-02-07 16:12:55 | Editor: huaxia.

http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/2020-02/07/c_138763741.htm

[(full text) Researchers found that the genome sequence of the coronavirus strain separated from pangolins was 99 percent identical to those in infected people.

GUANGZHOU, Feb. 7 (Xinhua) -- The genome sequence of the novel coronavirus strain separated from pangolins was 99 percent identical to that from infected people, indicating pangolins may be an intermediate host of the virus, a study has found.

The study was led by the South China Agricultural University. According to Liu Yahong, president of the university, the research team analyzed more than 1,000 metagenome samples of wild animals and found pangolins as the most likely intermediate host.

Molecular biological detection revealed that the positive rate of Betacoronavirus in pangolins was 70 percent. Researchers further isolated the virus and observed its structure with an electron microscope. They found that the genome sequence of the coronavirus strain was 99 percent identical to those in infected people.

Results showed that pangolins are a potential intermediate host of the novel coronavirus, Liu said, adding that the study will support the prevention and control of the epidemic, as well as offer scientific reference for policies on wild animals.

Photo shows the novel coronavirus separated from pangolins under an electron microscope. (Photo provided to Xinhua)]

YIN Dave, MA Danmeng, ZHANG Yang

- 2020 *China's Controversial Quarantine Measures Worked, Prominent Epidemiologist*
[ZHONG Nanshan] *Argues*,
in: Caixin Mar 10, 2020 09:42 PM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-10/chinas-controversial-quarantine-measures-worked-prominent-epidemiologist-argues-101526645.html>>
- YUAN Shawn
2020 *Wuhan turns to social media to vent anger at coronavirus response.*
Residents of virus-hit city accuse government of withholding information and downplaying severity of viral outbreak,
in: Al Jazeera News, February 3, 2020.
<<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/02/wuhan-turns-social-media-vent-anger-coronavirus-response-200203085324619.html>>
- ZHANG Fan & JIA Denise
2020 *Travelers Begin Importing Coronavirus to China From Other Hard-Hit Countries*,
in: Caixin, Mar 03, 2020 04:09 AM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-03/travelers-begin-importing-coronavirus-to-china-from-other-hard-hit-countries-101523130.html>>
- ZHANG Taisu
°2020 [pdf] *How Much Could a New Virus Damage Beijing's Legitimacy?*
in: China File, January 29, 2020.
<<http://www.chinafile.com/reporting-opinion/viewpoint/how-much-could-new-virus-damage-beijings-legitimacy>>
- ZHANG Wenhong
2020 *Zhang Wenhong: Little Chance Coronavirus Pandemic Will End This Summer*,
in: Caixin, March 27, 2020 06:57 AM.
<<https://www.caixinglobal.com/2020-03-27/zhang-wenhong-little-chance-coronavirus-pandemic-will-end-this-summer-101534591.html>>
[ZHANG Wenhong, head of Shanghai's Covid-19 clinical expert team, and director of the infectious diseases department at Huashan Hospital of Fudan University in Shanghai. –
“Which is more effective, traditional Chinese medicine or Western medicine?
Zhang: Shanghai used a combination of traditional Chinese and Western medicine in the treatment of Covid-19 patients, and the collaboration has been very effective. I don't think it makes sense to say which one is more effective. This is like a couple. When the life is good, why bother to distinguish who contributes more? And it's impossible to tell. If we have to tell who contributes more, it can only be done by comparison using traditional Chinese medicine only or Western medicine only without using any other treatments. It's ethically impossible to do such an experiment on patients. How could we risk people's lives to do such experiments? If a patient needs oxygen, but I only give him traditional Chinese medicine but not oxygen, this is not right. Both traditional Chinese medicine and Western medicine are medical science. The combination of traditional Chinese and Western medicine in the treatment of Covid-19 patients has achieved good results.”]
- ZHŌNGYĀNG YÁNJIÙYUÀN 中央研究院 • ACADEMIA SINICA
2020 *Rapid Virus Detection! Academia Sinica develops antibodies for rapid immune-based test kit of SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus*,
in: Facebook, March 8, 2020 05:05.
<<https://www.facebook.com/sinicaedu/posts/2477979259184506>>
[(full English text) *Rapid Virus Detection! Academia Sinica develops antibodies for rapid immune-based test kit of SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus*
Currently available RT-PCR-based SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus diagnostic tests take about 4 hours to obtain results, with throughput limited by availability of laboratory facilities and trained personnel. To prevent the pandemic spread of the coronavirus, a faster way to detect infected patients is urgently needed. Today, Academia Sinica (AS) proudly announced that the first group of monoclonal antibodies specifically binding the coronavirus nucleocapsid protein

(N protein) has been successfully generated and tested by Dr. An-Suei Yang [YANG An-Suei 楊安綏] and his team at the Genomics Research Center in AS. If successfully manufactured and validated, the rapid immune-based test kit could detect coronavirus in only 15 minutes, just like a rapid influenza test.

His team produced N proteins from 7 different viral species and screened against these to obtain a few dozen monoclonal antibodies. Out of these few dozen, one antibody against only SARS-CoV-2 N protein, 9 against only SARS-CoV N protein, and 36 against both SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV N proteins were developed. One additional advantage, said Dr. Yang, is that none of these monoclonal antibodies bind any N proteins of the other 5 strains of coronavirus, thus cross-reactivity will not be a problem for the rapid SARS-CoV-2 detection kit.

With the help of the Ministry of Economic Affairs, Dr. Yang's team is working with manufacturers on the development and production of prototypes. In the coming months, they will discuss product validation and certification with the Taiwan Food and Drug Administration. They will then work with the Ministry of Health and Welfare to bring a rapid coronavirus test kit to Taiwan to combat this devastating epidemic.]

ZHOU Xun
2020

Coronavirus: how health and politics have always been inextricably linked in China,

in: The Conversation, February 4, 2020 3.03pm GMT.

<<https://theconversation.com/coronavirus-how-health-and-politics-have-always-been-inextricably-linked-in-china-130720>>

ZIMMER Katarina
2020

Why Some COVID-19 Cases Are Worse than Others.

Emerging data as well as knowledge from the SARS and MERS coronavirus outbreaks yield some clues as to why SARS-CoV-2 affects some people worse than others.

in: The Scientist, February 24, 2020.

<<https://www.the-scientist.com/news-opinion/why-some-covid-19-cases-are-worse-than-others-67160>>

- Coronavirus Social Science Resources
<<https://www.sonar-global.eu/?topic=coronavirus>>
- #coronavirussyllabus | a crowdsourced cross-disciplinary resource.
*open access / contributors? see #coronavirussyllabus + click notification button on top right of the page
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1dTkjmhWQ8NcxhmjeLp6ybT1_YOPhFLx9hZ43j1S7DjE/edit>
- Teaching COVID-19: An Anthropology Syllabus Project.
<<http://teachinglearninganthro.com/teaching-covid-19-an-anthropology-syllabus-project/>>
- Dispatches from the Pandemic.
<<http://somatosphere.net/series/dispatches-from-the-pandemic/>>

BASHFORD Alison
2020

Beyond Quarantine Critique.
COVID-19 Forum.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/beyond-quarantine-critique/>>

BENTON Adia
2020

Border Promiscuity, Illicit Intimacies, and Origin Stories: Or what Contagion's Bookends Tell us About New Infectious Diseases and a Racialized Geography of Blame.
COVID-19 Forum.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/border-promiscuity-racialized-blame/>>

BENUSSI Teo & ZHU Ruiyi
2020

Diasporic Cassandras: time, space, and ethos among transnational Chinese and Italians at the time of COVID-19.
COVID-19 Forum II.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/diasporic-cassandras-covid19/>>

BILLÉ Franck
2020

Containment.
COVID-19 Forum II.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/containment/>>

COURTNEY Chris
2020

COVID-19 and China's Health Code System.
COVID-19 Forum II.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/covid-19-china-health-code-system/>>
[(intro) “The health code system ([*jiànkāng mǎ*] 健康码) that the Chinese government has developed in response to COVID-19 builds upon long established traditions of population surveillance and control. No region in the world has a longer and more sustained history of gathering population data than China. The various regimes that have ruled this region have used civil registers to monitor their populations since ancient times. They had already developed sophisticated systems of community-based surveillance a thousand years ago.[i] Modern governments have been no less zealous in their pursuit of information for the purposes of governance. Since 1949, the Chinese Communist Party have conducted numerous data gathering projects, using information compiled by work teams to divide citizens into taxonomies of class, ethnicity, and household registration.[ii]”]

DELAPLACE Gregory
2020

Neglecting the Dead in Times of Epidemics.
COVID-19 Forum II.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/neglecting-dead-epidemics-covid19/>>

EISENBERG Merle, MORDECHAI Lee, ALPERT Robert
°2020 [**docx**]

Why treating coronavirus like Black Death is so dangerous.
Our standard outbreak narrative conceals the reality of pandemic diseases,
in: The Washington Post, February 6, 2020.
<<https://www.washingtonpost.com/outlook/2020/02/06/why-treating-coronavirus-like-black-death-is-so-dangerous/>>

ENGELMANN Lukas
2020

#COVID19: The Spectacle of Real-Time Surveillance.
COVID-19 Forum.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/covid19-spectacle-surveillance/>>

FEARNLEY Lyle
2020

The Pandemic Epicenter: Pointing from Viruses to China's Wildlife Trade.
COVID-19 Forum.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/wild-virus/>>
[See also LYNTERIS & FEARNLEY 2020; GILES-VERNICK Tamara 2020.]

GAY Y BLASCO Paloma & RODRIGUEZ CAMACHO Maria Félix
2020

COVID-19 and its Impact on the Roma Community: The Case of Spain.
COVID-19 Forum II.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/covid-19-roma-community-spain/>>

GEISSLER P. Wenzel & PRINCE Ruth J.
2020

Frontline. Primary Health Care and COVID-19 in Kenya.
COVID-19 Forum II.
<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/primary-health-care-covid-19-kenya/>>

GILES-VERNICK Tamara
2020

Should Wild Meat Markets Be Shut Down?
COVID-19 Forum.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/wild-meat-markets/>
[See also Fearnley 2020; LYNTERIS & FEARNLEY 2020.]

HAN DUYI
2020 [pdf]

duyi han pays homage to coronavirus medical workers with chapel mural in hubei province.

<https://www.designboom.com/art/duyi-han-coronavirus-medical-workers-chapel-mural-hubei-province-02-07-2020/>

[project info: project name: the saints wear white
location: hubei province, china
design: duiyi han

(intro) with the outbreak and spread of coronavirus dominating news headlines across the globe, designer duiyi han decided to pay tribute to the medical workers who are risking their lives to help those in need. the project sees the walls and ceilings of a historic church in china's hubei province – where the epidemic began – transformed into a large mural depicting figures dressed in white decontamination suits. / dubbed 'the saints wear white', the project by han takes inspiration from the traditional style of church paintings and frescos. however, instead of illustrating biblical scenes of saints or deities, the mural shows the everyday medical workers who are selflessly putting themselves at the front line of the virus. covered by masks, gloves and full-body suits, the work pays homage to the anonymous doctors and nurses who are crucial in aiding those infected with coronavirus]

HINCHLIFFE Steve
2020

Model Evidence – the COVID-19 Case.
COVID-19 Forum II.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/model-evidence-covid-19/>

JONES Stephen ✨
2020 [pdf]

Coronavirus: Mourning Li Wenliang, and blind bards.
Posted on 15/02/2020 by StephenJones.blog.

<https://stephenjones.blog/2020/02/15/coronavirus/>

[Nota bene: “A tribute to Li Wenliang, posted on WeChat on 8th February and only deleted by the 13th, featured a folk-song movingly performed by none other than Zuoquan blindman

Liu Hongquan. / The lyrics were written by Peking University economist Zhang Weiyong, a native of Shaanbei who in 2019 composed, and sang, a Xintianyou folk-song in defence of dissident law professor Xu Zhangrun (see this article in a lengthy series by Geremie Barmé; for his translation of Xu's essay on the virus, see here

<<http://www.chinafile.com/reporting-opinion/viewpoint/viral-alarm-when-fury-overcomes-fear>>, and here <<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/feb/11/coronavirus-outspoken-academic-blames-xi-jinping-for-catastrophe-sweeping-china>>; cf. this article <<https://cn.nytimes.com/opinion/20200211/zhang-qianfan-constitutional-cure-coronavirus-china-democracy/>> in Chinese by Zhang Qianfan, another righteous scholar).

Here are Zhang Weiyong's lyrics for the new song commemorating Li Wenliang:"

左权民歌《元宵节哭文亮》

词：张维迎

演唱：刘红权

黑夜里划过一颗星，
普天同哭（兄弟呀）你一人。
三千里外雪花飞，
第一次难眠（兄弟呀）都为了谁？
鸡蛋壳儿点灯一坨些些明，
先封你嘴巴（兄弟呀）后封了城。
天下百姓有苦情，
说真话甚时（兄弟呀）还难为情？
腊月里你吹哨没人听，
正月里红火（兄弟呀）断了歌声。
元宵节点灯送你一程，
大江南北（兄弟呀）像过清明。
青天蓝天老皇天，
全国都醒了呀（兄弟呀）你已走远。
全国都醒了呀（兄弟呀）你已走远。

<<https://freewechat.com/a/MzA5MDM0Nzg3NA==/2652605358/1>>]

JUST Barbara
2020

Weltweite Pandemie. Heilige Corona, hilf!

Die Angst vor dem Coronavirus lähmt Deutschland und die Welt.
Was die wenigsten wissen: "Corona" ist nicht nur die Bezeichnung für einen gefährlichen Erreger, es ist auch der Name einer frühchristlichen Heiligen. Die weitgehend unbekannte Märtyrerin gilt auch noch ausgerechnet als himmlische Helferin gegen Seuchen!

in: Katholische Sonntagszeitung, 17. März 2020.

<<https://www.katholische-sonntagszeitung.de/Im-Blickpunkt/Heilige-Corona-hilf-Dienstag-17.-Maerz-2020-16-03-00/>>

KECK Frédéric
2020

Sentinels and Whistleblowers: Lessons from Wuhan.

COVID-19 Forum.

<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/sentinels-and-whistleblowers/>>

LEACH Melissa
2020

Echoes of Ebola: Social and Political Warnings for the COVID-19 Response in African Settings.

COVID-19 Forum.

<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/echoes-of-ebola/>>

LEE Christine
2020

Covid-19, Sinicisation, and the Roman Catholic Church in China.

COVID-19 Forum.

<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/covid-19-sinicisation-roman-catholic-church-china>>

LYNTERIS Christos

*2020a

The epidemic control measures in China from a historical perspective.

[Audio; audio transcript.]

<<https://www.sonar-global.eu/keyreadings/the-epidemic-control-measures-in-china-from-a-historical-perspective/>>

*2020b

COVID-19 Forum: Introduction.

<<http://somatosphere.net/2020/covid-19-forum-introduction.html/>>

Since its emergence in December 2019, COVID-19 has led to a global pandemic, in everything but name. To date, over 100,000 people have been infected across the globe, with the vast majority of burden of the infection and of the 3,400 deaths so far being borne by China, where the disease originally emerged. There the epidemic has led to the adoption of quarantine and isolation measures at a historically unprecedented scale, as well as to the controversial employment of smartphone apps and other digital technologies in community containment. At the moment, with the disease having made significant in-ways in South Korea, Japan, Iran, and Italy, we are still no wiser as to the zoonotic origins of the disease, whereas information about its modes of transmission, basic reproduction number, incubation period, asymptomatic transmission (or not) and other key clinical and epidemiological aspects are constantly being debated and revised, leading to an environment of epistemic uncertainty and flux. At the same time, as scientists have been racing to provide real-time information on the epidemic, the social media have once again proved to be the insidious breeding grounds of fake-news, conspiracy theories, misinformation and disinformation about the virus, thus contributing to a broader environment of xenophobia, fear, and panic about the disease.

Somatosphere's COVID-19 Forum brings together seventeen anthropologists and historians in an effort to share ideas, analytical frameworks and concerns about the ongoing epidemic from interdisciplinary perspectives. Unlike the recent Ebola epidemic in West Africa, where anthropological intervention on the ground and direct engagement with affected communities and response teams flourished between 2014 and 2016, in the case of COVID-19, such activities remain virtually a political and practical impossibility, at least as far as China is concerned. However, an analytical and critical engagement with the epidemic, both in China and across the globe, is still pertinent, not only so that ethnographic and historical context can be provided (and such context is indeed urgently needed in many cases), but also so that the wider social impact of the epidemic and of epidemic containment measures is understood, and critical tools are developed for engaging with the epidemic crisis in its complex social reality. The contributions to this Forum thus aim to examine the epidemic in itself, but also in comparison to other epidemics and epidemic-control processes. It is hoped that the Forum will foster interdisciplinary discussion and collaboration in response to the ongoing COVID-19 epidemic, and that it will inspire new critical and analytical approaches to the ways in which the new coronavirus epidemic is conceptualised, discussed, experienced and contained.

The COVID-19 Forum was edited by: Christos LYNTERIS.

*2020c

Didactic Historicism and the Historical Consciousness of Epidemics.

COVID-19 Forum.

<<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/didactic-historicism-historical-consciousness-epidemics>>

*2020d

COVID-19 Forum II: Introduction.

COVID-19 Forum II.

<<http://somatosphere.net/2020/covid-19-forum-ii-introduction.html/>>

LYNTERIS Christos, FEARNLEY Lyle

2020

Why shutting down Chinese 'wet markets' could be a terrible mistake,

in: *The Conversation*, January 31, 2020 10.13am GMT.

<<https://theconversation.com/why-shutting-down-chinese-wet-markets-could-be-a-terrible-mistake-130625>>

[See also FEARNLEY 2020; GILES-VERNICK Tamara 2020.]

MACGREGOR Hayley

2020

Novelty and Uncertainty: Social Science Contributions to a Response to COVID-19.

COVID-19 Forum.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/novelty-and-uncertainty/>

MELLQUIST LEHTO Heather

2020

Coronavirus, Cults, and Contagion in South Korea.

COVID-19 Forum II.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/coronavirus-cults-contagion-south-korea/>

MORENO LOZANO Cristina

2020

Seeing COVID-19, or a Visual Journey Through the Epidemic in Three Acts.

COVID-19 Forum II.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/visual-journey-epidemic-covid-19/>

NAPIER David

2020

I Heard it Through the Grapevine: On Herd Immunity and Why it is Important.

COVID-19 Forum II.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/herd-immunity-covid19/>

PECKHAM Robert

2020

Coronavirus: The Low Tech of the High Tech.

COVID-19 Forum.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/coronavirus-low-tech-high-tech/>

SALM Mel

2020

Anthropocene Diseased: A Provocation.

COVID-19 Forum II.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/anthropocene-covid-19/>

SINHA Ria

2020

COVID-19: Social Distancing in Context.

COVID-19 Forum II.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/covid-19-social-distancing-in-context/>

SONG Priscilla & WALLINE Joseph

2020

Virtual Technologies of Care in a Time of Viral Crisis: An Ethnographic View from Hong Kong.

COVID-19 Forum.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/virtual-technologies-of-care/>

STEINMULLER Hans

2020

Shame and Complicity in the Reactions to the Coronavirus.

COVID-19 Forum.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/shame-and-complicity/>

STREET Alice & KELLY Ann H.

2020

Counting coronavirus: delivering diagnostic certainty in a global emergency.

COVID-19 Forum.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/counting-coronavirus-diagnostic-certainty-global-emergency>

TAO Anthony

2020

“Coronavirus in China” by Anthony Tao, (Poems)

in: *The Rattle*, February 23, 2020.

<https://www.rattle.com/coronavirus-in-china-by-anthony-tao/>

XIANG Biao
2020

From Chain Reaction to Grid Reaction: Mobilities and Restrictions During the Epidemics of SARS and COVID-19.

COVID-19 Forum.

<http://somatosphere.net/forumpost/from-chain-to-grid-reaction/>

Pandemic memes

KOONTZ Dean R. [orig. publ. NICHOLS Leigh (pseudonym)]

*1981

The Eyes of Darkness.

(Pocket books, 82784.7)

New York: Pocket. [312p.; ISBN: 0671827847.]

KOONTZ 1989: 250

*1989

The eyes of darkness: a novel.

By Dean R. KOONTZ; illustrated by Phil PARKS.

Arlington Hts., Ill.: Dark Harvest.

[257p.; Originally written as 'by Leigh NICHOLS.']

*1996, 2016

The eyes of darkness.

London: Headline. [324p.; Revised version; ISBN: 9781472240293.]

[Tina Evans dreams that her son Danny is still alive. And when she wakes, she finds a message scrawled on Danny's chalkboard: not dead. Tina searches for the truth and learns that there are some things worse than death.]

1996 revisions: "I'm not interested in the philosophy or morality of biological warfare," Tina said. "Right now I just want to know how the hell Danny wound up in this place." / "To understand that," Dombey said, "you have to go back twenty months. It was around then that a [*1981, 1989: Russian →] Chinese scientist named [* Ilya Poparopov →] Li Chen defected to the United States, carrying a [* microfilm →] diskette record of [* the Soviet's →] China's most important [* , →] and dangerous new biological weapon in a decade. [* The Russians →] They call the stuff [* Gorki-400 →] 'Wuhan-400' because it was developed at their RDNA labs outside of [* Gorki →] the city of Wuhan, and it was the fourhundredth viable strain of man-made microorganisms created at that research center. / " [* Gorki-400 →] Wuhan-400 is a perfect weapon. It afflicts only human beings. No other living creature can carry it. And like syphilis, [* Gorki-400 →] Wuhan-400 can't survive outside a living human body for longer than a minute, which means it can't permanently contaminate objects or entire places the way anthrax and other virulent microorganisms can. And when the host expires, the [* Gorki-400 →] Wuhan-400 within him perishes a short while later, as soon as the temperature of the corpse drops below eighty-six degrees Fahrenheit. Do you see the advantage of all this?" / Tina was too busy with Danny to think about what Carl Dombey had said, but Elliot knew what the scientist meant. "If I understand you, the [* Russians →] Chinese could use [* Gorki-400 →] Wuhan-400 to wipe out a city or a country, and then there wouldn't be any need for them to conduct a tricky and expensive decontamination before they moved in and took over the conquered territory." / "Exactly," Dombey said. "And [* Gorki-400 →] Wuhan-400 has other,

equally important advantages over most biological agents. For one thing, you can become an infectious carrier only four hours after coming into contact with the virus. That's an incredibly short [* gestation →] incubation period. Once infected, no one lives more than twenty-four hours. Most die in twelve. [* →] It's worse than the Ebola virus in Africa—indefinitely worse. [* Gorki-400's →] Wuhan-400's kill-rate is one hundred percent. No one is supposed to survive. The [* Russians →] Chinese tested it on God knows how many political prisoners. They were never able to find an antibody or an antibiotic that was effective against it. The virus migrates to the brain stem, and there it begins secreting a toxin that literally eats away brain tissue like battery acid dissolving cheesecloth. It destroys the part of the brain that controls all of the body's automatic functions. The victim simply ceases to have a pulse, functioning organs, or any urge to breathe.”

• Memes: (1) Russian moved to Chinese biowarfare meme; (2) precision meme; (3) missing cure meme.]

“prediction” discussion:

• WHITEHEAD Kate 2020a: *A virus called Wuhan-400 causes outbreak ... in a Dean Koontz thriller from 1981. How is it that some books appear to prophesy events?*

The Eyes of Darkness features a Chinese military lab in Wuhan that creates a virus as a bioweapon; civilians soon become sick after accidentally contracting it / In fact, the one lab in China able to handle the deadliest viruses is in Wuhan and helped sequence the novel coronavirus the world is currently battling,
in: South China Morning Post, 6:21pm, 13 Feb, 2020.

<https://www.scmp.com/lifestyle/arts-culture/article/3050481/virus-called-wuhan-400-makes-people-terribly-ill-dean-koontz>

• WHITEHEAD Kate 2020b: *China wasn't original villain in book 'predicting' coronavirus outbreak – it was Russia*, Dean Koontz's *The Eyes of Darkness* originally contained details of a man-made virus called Gorki-400 from the Russian city of Gorki / The change to Wuhan came when the book was released in hardback under Koontz's own name in 1989 – at the end of the Cold War,
in: South China Morning Post, 9:00pm, 20 Feb, 2020.

<https://www.scmp.com/lifestyle/arts-culture/article/3051619/china-wasnt-original-villain-book-predicting-coronavirus>

[“Meanwhile, readers are also pointing to a passage in a book by the late Sylvia Browne, an American author who claimed to be psychic, that predicted an international outbreak of a virus this year. / “Around 2020, a severe pneumonia-like illness will spread throughout the globe, attacking the lungs and the bronchial tubes and resisting all known treatments,” Browne wrote in the book *End of Days*. “Almost more baffling than the illness itself will be the fact that it will suddenly vanish as quickly as it arrived, attack 10 years later, and then disappear completely.””]

• INDIA TODAY WEB DESK 2020: *Novel predicted Wuhan virus 40 years before Coronavirus outbreak. Internet is stumped*, in: India Today, New Delhi, February 17, 2020; UPDATED: February 21, 2020 14:09 IST.

<https://www.indiatoday.in/trending-news/story/-novel-predicted-wuhan-virus-40-years-before-coronavirus-outbreak-internet-is-stumped-1647261-2020-02-17>

SODERBERGH Steven (director)
2011

Contagion.

Action, Science Fiction, Thriller, Drama; 1 Std. 55 Min. USA/UAE.

<https://www.imdb.com/title/tt1598778/>

[Als Beth Emhoff zu ihrer Familie zurückkehrt, ist es schon zu spät: Ein tödlicher Virus, mit dem sie sich auf einer Geschäftsreise im Fernen Osten infiziert hat, rafft sie innerhalb weniger Tage dahin. Mit diesem besetzungstechnischen Paukenschlag, der ein wenig an Hitchcocks Psycho erinnert, beginnt Steven Soderberghs neuer Thriller Contagion. Während der Ehemann und Vater Thomas Emhoff noch mit der persönlichen Tragödie zu kämpfen hat, kämpft ein internationales Ärzteteam unter Federführung der C.D.C. bestehend aus Dr. Leonora Orantes, Dr. Erin Mears und Dr. Ellis Cheever u.a. im Wettlauf mit der Zeit gegen die weitere Ausbreitung des aggressiven Virus und die Zersetzung der gesellschaftlichen Strukturen. Denn im Angesicht des Todes ist sich jeder selbst der Nächste – und zwar weltweit. Actors: Matt Damon; Kate Winslet; Marion Cotillard; Gwyneth Paltrow; Laurence Fishburne; Armin Rohde; Jude Law; Bryan Cranston; Jennifer Ehle; Elliott Gould; Rebecca Spence; Amr Waked; Anna Jacoby-Heron; Enrico Colantoni; Larry Clarke; Demetri Martin; Sanaa Lathan; Monique Gabriela Curnen; John Hawkes; Chin Han; Josie Ho; Grace Rex; ...

- Memes: (1) Forsythia remedy, (2) conspiracy of CDC/WHO; *cf.* BENTON Adia 2020.]

Rumours • disinformation • propaganda war

Anti-racist stance

- CHANG Jason Oliver (comp.)
2020 *Treating Yellow Peril: Resources to Address Coronavirus Racism.*
<https://docs.google.com/document/u/0/d/1-DLnAY5r-f4DRLZgndR_Bu47nqHVtAOKem5QRmbz7bg/mobilebasic>
- Resources for Asian and AAPI Students Experiencing COVID-19 Related Harassment
<<https://calc.fas.harvard.edu/news/resources-asian-and-aapi-students-experiencing-covid-19-related-harassment>>
- Christine YANO: *Asian Studies in a Time of Pandemic.* (President's Column)
<<https://www.asianstudies.org/asian-studies-in-a-time-of-pandemic/>>
[with remarks on anti-Asian racism.]

Notification on false information

- LYTVYENKO Jane
2020 *Here's A Running List Of Disinformation Spreading About The Coronavirus.*
There are plenty of fake videos and unsourced claims of how many people have been affected.
Jane Lytvynenko, BuzzFeed News Reporter.
BuzzFeed News.
Last updated on January 29, 2020, at 12:07 p.m. ET.
Posted on January 24, 2020, at 6:21 p.m. ET.
<<https://www.buzzfeednews.com/article/janelytvynenko/coronavirus-disinformation-spread>>

新型冠状病毒肺炎 谣言排行榜

- *xinxing guanzhuang bingdu feiyan 新型冠状病毒肺炎. yaoyan paixingbang 谣言排行榜.*
<https://ncov.dxy.cn/ncovh5/view/pneumonia_rumors?from=dxy>
- *Misinformation related to the 2019–20 coronavirus outbreak.* Wikipedia.
<https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Misinformation_related_to_the_2019%E2%80%9920_coronavirus_outbreak>
- WHO Coronavirus scam alert: *Beware of criminals pretending to be WHO.*
<<https://www.who.int/about/communications/cyber-security>>
- Correctiv: *Recherchen für die Gesellschaft: Neuste Faktenchecks zum Coronavirus.*
<<https://correctiv.org/faktencheck/coronavirus/>>

Discussion of propaganda articles • Infodemic • Desinformation

CALISHER Charles, CARROLL Dennis, COLWELL Rita, CORLEY Ronald B., DASZAK Peter, DROSTEN Christian, ENJUANES Luis, FARRAR Jeremy, FIELD Hume, GOLDING Josie, GORBALENYA Alexander, HAAGMANS Bart, HUGHES James M., KARESH William B., KEUSCH Gerald T., LAM Sai Kit, LUBROTH Juan, MACKENZIE John S., MADOFF Larry, MAZET Jonna, PALESE Peter, PERLMAN Stanley, POON Leo, ROIZMAN Bernard, SAIF Linda, SUBBARAO Kanta, TURNER Mike

2020

Statement in support of the scientists, public health professionals, and medical professionals of China combatting COVID-19, (Correspondence)

in: *The Lancet* 395(10226): Pe42-e43, March 07, 2020.

[2p., 14 refs.; Supplementary material: Chinese translation of full text, 2p.]

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30418-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30418-9)

[Excerpt: “We stand together to strongly condemn conspiracy theories suggesting that COVID-19 does not have a natural origin. Scientists from multiple countries have published and analysed genomes of the causative agent, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2),¹ and they overwhelmingly conclude that this coronavirus originated in wildlife,^{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10} as have so many other emerging pathogens.^{11, 12} This is further supported by a letter from the presidents of the US National Academies of Science, Engineering, and Medicine¹³ and by the scientific communities they represent. Conspiracy theories do nothing but create fear, rumours, and prejudice that jeopardise our global collaboration in the fight against this virus. We support the call from the Director-General of WHO to promote scientific evidence and unity over misinformation and conjecture.¹⁴ We want you, the science and health professionals of China, to know that we stand with you in your fight against this virus.”]

CYRANOSKI David

°2017 [pdf]

Inside the Chinese lab poised to study world’s most dangerous pathogens.

Maximum-security biolab is part of plan to build network of BSL-4 facilities across China,

in: *Nature* 542(7642): 399-400. doi:10.1038/nature.2017.21487.

<https://www.nature.com/news/inside-the-chinese-lab-poised-to-study-world-s-most-dangerous-pathogens-1.21487>

[Editors’ note, January 2020: Many stories have promoted an unverified theory that the Wuhan lab discussed in this article played a role in the coronavirus outbreak that began in December 2019. Nature knows of no evidence that this is true; scientists believe the most likely source of the coronavirus to be an animal market.]

EVANS Nicholas G.

2020

*Where the Coronavirus Bioweapon Conspiracy Theories Really Come From
Whenever a disease emerges, claims that it has spread too quickly to be natural soon follow,*

in: *Slate*, February 27, 2020, 4:09 PM.

<https://slate.com/technology/2020/02/coronavirus-bioweapon-conspiracy-theories.html>

HAO Karen & BASU Tanya

2020

The coronavirus is the first true social-media “infodemic”.

Social media has zipped information and misinformation around the world at unprecedented speeds, fueling panic, racism ... and hope.

in: *MIT Technology Review*, February 12, 2020.

<https://www.technologyreview.com/s/615184/the-coronavirus-is-the-first-true-social-media-infodemic/>

HANAGE Bill, LIPSITCH Marc

2020

How to Report on the COVID-19 Outbreak Responsibly.

Remember, the virus doesn’t follow the news and doesn’t care about

Twitter,

in: Scientific American, February 23, 2020.

[<https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/how-to-report-on-the-covid-19-outbreak-responsibly/>](https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/observations/how-to-report-on-the-covid-19-outbreak-responsibly/)

[“To help in this effort, we think reporting should distinguish between at least three levels of information: (A) *what we know is true*; (B) *what we think is true*—fact-based assessments that also depend on inference, extrapolation or educated interpretation of facts that reflect an individual’s view of what is most likely to be going on; and (C) *opinions and speculation*.” (...) “Emergencies like this one lead to extreme pressure on both scientists and journalists to be the first with news. And there are perverse incentives arising from the attention economy we now inhabit—exacerbated by social media—that may provide short-term rewards for those willing to accept lower standards. Accurate reporting should be aware of this risk, seek to avoid contributing to it and rapidly correct falsehoods when they become clear. We have a common responsibility to protect public health. The virus does not read news articles and doesn’t care about Twitter.”]

LING Justin
°2020 [pdf]

The Wuhan Virus Is Not a Lab-Made Bioweapon.

Conspiracy theories are spreading faster than the coronavirus itself,

in: Foreign Policy, January 29, 2020, 11:27 AM.

[<https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/01/29/coronavirus-china-lab-mortality-virology-wuhan-virus-not-bioweapon/>](https://foreignpolicy.com/2020/01/29/coronavirus-china-lab-mortality-virology-wuhan-virus-not-bioweapon/)

[(...) The only basis for the claim is a quote from former Israeli intelligence officer Dany Shoham, who has expertise in biological warfare.

“Certain laboratories in the institute have probably been engaged, in terms of research and development, in Chinese [biological weapons], at least collaterally, yet not as a principal facility of the Chinese BW alignment,” Shoham told the *Times*.

While Shoham never backed up the claim made in the story that the outbreak stemmed from a biological weapon, other outlets nevertheless picked up the idea and ran with it.

The Texas radio station KPRC posted the story to its site, concluding “some intelligence experts believe the Chinese military’s biowarfare department may be responsible.” A speculation by a single former officer had become “intelligence experts.” The *Toronto Sun* columnist Candice Malcolm pumped the theory on her YouTube show, asking: “Why isn’t the mainstream media talking about the origins of this deadly virus? Could it be linked to China’s biological warfare program?”

All this on the guesswork of one man—and it’s not the first time Shoham has pumped the tires on a theory without much merit. In 2017, he went on Radio Sputnik, a propaganda arm of the Russian government, to suggest the Islamic State had likely passed on chemical weapon capabilities to its sleeper cells in the West.

GreatGameIndia, a small conspiracy website—which, among other things, has reported that British intelligence was responsible for the downing of Malaysia Airlines Flight 17 over Ukraine in 2014—began publishing reports last week claiming that Canadian researchers had sold this strain of coronavirus to China. The co-founder and editor of the website has also written extensively for the Centre for Research on Globalization, a Montreal-based site that has been identified by NATO as a peddler of Russian and Syrian propaganda. (...) While the claims made on *GreatGameIndia* are demonstrably untrue—the supposed shipment of the coronavirus in 2018 was for, in fact, for the MERS strain, not the novel coronavirus currently seen in Wuhan—it nevertheless got picked up by fellow conspiracy site *ZeroHedge*, which has a massive following (about 670,000 Twitter followers and millions of visitors to its blog). Its post on the baseless theory has been shared more than 6,000 times on Facebook and tweeted by hundreds of accounts, including by *Toronto Sun* columnist Tarek Fatah. The claims have since spread to a network of other less-than-reputable sites.]

MAI Jun
2020

Chinese research lab denies rumours of links to first coronavirus patient.

Speculation that a woman supposedly at the institute is ‘patient zero’ is false, laboratory says. Authorities maintain that the most likely source was a market in Wuhan,

in: South China Morning Post, 9:00pm, 16 Feb, 2020.

[<https://www.scmp.com/news/china/society/article/3050872/chinese-research-lab-denies-rumours-links-first-coronavirus>](https://www.scmp.com/news/china/society/article/3050872/chinese-research-lab-denies-rumours-links-first-coronavirus)

[(patient zero) “In a statement on Sunday, the Wuhan Institute of Virology denied that one of its employees was the outbreak’s “patient zero”. / “Recently there has been fake information about Huang Yanling [黄燕玲], a graduate from our institute, claiming that she was patient

zero in the novel coronavirus,” the institute said. / It said it had verified that the claim was not true. / It said Huang was a graduate student at the institute until 2015, when she left the province and had not returned since. Huang was in good health and had not been diagnosed with disease, it added.” [Original notice in Chinese, February 16, 2020:

<http://www.whiov.cas.cn/tzgg_105342/202002/t20200216_5500201.html>]

(leak from Wuhan Institute of Virology; SHI Zhengli 石正麗) “Frustrated and angry at the authorities’ response to the outbreak, some members of the public have been unwilling to accept the official line about the probable source. Much of the speculation has been focused on the Wuhan Institute of Virology, the only laboratory to be graded Biological Security Level 4, the highest level of biosafety precautions, on the Chinese mainland. The laboratory was designed to treat infectious diseases such as Ebola. / ~~The unverified theory of a biological leak from the institute so widely shared online that Shi Zhengli, a lead researcher at the institute on bat-related viruses, said on her social media account that she “guaranteed with her own life” that the outbreak was not related to the facility.”]~~

SHMERLING Robert H.

2020

Be careful where you get your news about coronavirus,

in: Harvard Health Blog, February 01, 2020, 10:30 am,

Updated March 16, 2020, 5:22 pm.

<<https://www.health.harvard.edu/blog/be-careful-where-you-get-your-news-about-coronavirus-2020020118801>>

SIMONITE Tom

2020

The Professors Who Call ‘Bullshit’ on Covid-19 Misinformation.

Jevin West and Carl Bergstrom are policing Twitter feeds, Medium posts, and other sources of bad data and misleading charts,

in: Wired, 03.24.2020, 08:00 AM.

<<https://www.wired.com/story/professors-call-bullshit-covid-19-misinformation/>>

YUAN Shawn

2020

China in coronavirus propaganda push as US ties worsen.

State media lauds China as global leader in fight against disease in bid to defuse criticism it allowed virus to spread.

Al Jazeera, March 25, 2020.

<<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2020/03/china-coronavirus-propaganda-push-ties-worsen-200325085419818.html>>

Enfer • Propaganda articles

GERTZ Bill
2020

Coronavirus may have originated in lab linked to China's biowarfare program,
in: The Washington Times, Sunday, January 26, 2020.

[<https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2020/jan/26/coronavirus-link-china-biowarfare-program-possible/>](https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2020/jan/26/coronavirus-link-china-biowarfare-program-possible/)

[(intro) The deadly animal-borne coronavirus spreading globally may have originated in a laboratory in the city of Wuhan linked to China's covert biological weapons program, said an Israeli biological warfare analyst.

Radio Free Asia last week rebroadcast a Wuhan television report from 2015 showing China's most advanced virus research laboratory, known the Wuhan Institute of Virology. The laboratory is the only declared site in China capable of working with deadly viruses.

Dany Shoham, a former Israeli military intelligence officer who has studied Chinese biological warfare, said the institute is linked to Beijing's covert bio-weapons program.]

BOYLE Francis
*2020a

Francis Boyle: Wuhan Coronavirus is an Offensive Biological Warfare Weapon.

[<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TsuyjtitOFM>](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TsuyjtitOFM) (30/01/2020)

[Dr. Francis Boyle discusses the coronavirus outbreak in Wuhan, China and the Biosafety Level 4 laboratory (BSL-4) from which he believes the infectious disease escaped. He believes the virus is potentially lethal and an offensive biological warfare weapon or dual-use biowarfare weapons agent genetically modified with gain of function properties, which is why the Chinese government originally tried to cover it up and is now taking drastic measures to contain it. The Wuhan BSL-4 lab is also a specially designated World Health Organization (WHO) research lab and Dr. Boyle contends that the WHO knows full well what is occurring.—

• Wuhan Institute of Virology, CAS • 中国科学院武汉病毒研究所:

[<http://english.whiov.cas.cn/>](http://english.whiov.cas.cn/)]

*2020b

Transcript: Bioweapons Expert Dr. Francis Boyle On Coronavirus,
in: GreatGameIndia • Journal on Geopolitics & International Relations, February 5, 2020.

[<https://greatgameindia.com/transcript-bioweapons-expert-dr-francis-boyle-on-coronavirus/>](https://greatgameindia.com/transcript-bioweapons-expert-dr-francis-boyle-on-coronavirus/)

DURDEN Tyler
*2020a

Senator Cotton Demands Beijing Prove Coronavirus Isn't A Bioweapon As Another 'Conspiracy Theory' Goes Mainstream,

in: Zerohedge, Tue, 02/11/2020 - 13:25.

[<https://www.zerohedge.com/geopolitical/tom-cotton-demands-beijing-prove-ncov-isnt-bioweapon-another-conspiracy-theory-goes>](https://www.zerohedge.com/geopolitical/tom-cotton-demands-beijing-prove-ncov-isnt-bioweapon-another-conspiracy-theory-goes)

*2020b

Sudden Militarization Of Wuhan's P4 Lab Raises New Questions About The Origin Of The Deadly Covid-19 Virus,

in: Zerohedge, Thu, 02/13/2020 - 09:11.

[<https://www.zerohedge.com/geopolitical/sudden-militarization-wuhans-p4-lab-raises-new-questions-about-origin-deadly-covid-19>](https://www.zerohedge.com/geopolitical/sudden-militarization-wuhans-p4-lab-raises-new-questions-about-origin-deadly-covid-19)

MOSHER Steven W.
2020

Don't buy China's story: The coronavirus may have leaked from a lab,

in: New York Post, February 22, 2020 | 11:18am | Updated.

[<https://nypost.com/2020/02/22/dont-buy-chinas-story-the-coronavirus-may-have-leaked-from-a-lab/>](https://nypost.com/2020/02/22/dont-buy-chinas-story-the-coronavirus-may-have-leaked-from-a-lab/)

WADHAMS Nick & JACOBS Jennifer [Bloomberg]
2020

US officials: China concealed COVID-19 deaths and infections.

US intelligence says China's numbers on coronavirus deaths and cases

are fake, sources tell Bloomberg,

in: Al Jazeera, April 2, 2020.

<https://www.aljazeera.com/ajimpact/officials-china-concealed-covid-19-deaths-infections-200401161145292.html>

[(intro) China has concealed the extent of the coronavirus outbreak in its country, under-reporting both total cases and deaths it's suffered from the disease, the U.S. intelligence community concluded in a classified report to the White House, according to three U.S. officials. –

(no reliable source cited)]

WANG Fuhua
2020

10 questions for the U.S.: Where did the novel coronavirus come from?

CGTN, Opinion 19:48, 19-Mar-2020.

<https://news.cgtn.com/news/2020-03-19/10-questions-for-the-U-S-Where-did-the-novel-coronavirus-come-from--OZrgRTSZfa/index.html>